

School of Business & Creative Industries

**Entrepreneurs' Perceptions Towards University Incubation
Programmes: A Qualitative Study of the Experiences of Tenant
Entrepreneurs in the UK University Business Incubators**

A thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the University of the
West of Scotland for the award of Doctoral in Business Administration

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Table of Contents

<i>LIST OF TABLES</i>	8
<i>LIST OF FIGURES</i>	8
<i>ABSTRACT</i>	9
<i>DECLARATION</i>	2
<i>ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS</i>	3
<i>ABBREVIATIONS</i>	4
1. INTRODUCTION	5
1.1. Background of the Study	5
1.1.1. Entrepreneurship as a tool for economic development.....	7
1.1.2. Entrepreneurial Landscape in the UK.....	8
1.1.3. Business Incubators and University Business Incubators as a Tool for Entrepreneurship Development.....	9
1.2. Research Problem	11
1.3. Research Aim, Objectives, and Questions	14
1.4. Rationale	17
1.5. Brief Descriptions of the Research Methodology	19
1.6. Limitations of the Study	20
1.7. Contributions of the Research	20
1.8. Thesis Structure	22
1.9. Summary of the Chapter	25
2. LITERATURE REVIEW	27
2.1. Introduction	27
Part I: Entrepreneurial Learning	28
2.2. Entrepreneurship: An Introduction	28
2.2.1. Characteristics of an Entrepreneur.....	29
2.2.2. Importance of Entrepreneurship.....	30

2.2.3.	Start-ups	31
2.3.	Entrepreneurial Learning.....	41
2.3.1.	Key Developments in Entrepreneurial Learning Literature.....	42
2.3.2.	Significance of Entrepreneurial Learning.....	46
2.3.3.	Processes of entrepreneurial learning.....	49
2.3.4.	Facilitators of Entrepreneurial Learning.....	54
Part II: Business Incubation.....		57
2.4.	Business Incubators and Business Incubation	57
2.4.1.	Introduction to Business Incubators	57
2.4.2.	History and Evolution of Business Incubators	60
2.4.3.	Classifications of Business Incubators	63
2.4.4.	Business incubation Process and Configuration.....	65
2.4.5.	Impacts of Business Incubation on Start-ups.....	68
2.4.6.	Roles of Business Incubators on the Development of Incubatees	71
2.4.7.	Entrepreneurial Learning of Incubatees.....	72
2.5.	University Business Incubation	73
2.5.1.	Introduction to University Business Incubators	73
2.5.2.	Key Activities of University Business Incubators.....	75
2.6.	Knowledge Gap and Conceptual Framework.....	78
2.6.1.	Conceptual framework	79
2.7.	Summary of the Chapter	82
3.	<i>RESEARCH METHODOLOGY</i>.....	85
3.1.	Introduction	85
3.2.	Research Framework	85
3.3.	Philosophical Assumptions	87
3.3.1.	Subjectivism vs Objectivism.....	88
3.4.	Research Philosophy	90
3.4.1.	Positivism.....	90
3.4.2.	Interpretivism	91
3.4.3.	Pragmatism.....	92
3.4.4.	Selected Research Philosophy and Justifications	92

3.5.	Research Approach	94
3.5.1.	Deductive Approach.....	94
3.5.2.	Inductive Approach.....	96
3.5.3.	Selected Research Approach and Justifications	97
3.6.	Research Strategy	98
3.6.1.	Case Study Research	99
3.7.	Research Design.....	102
3.7.1.	Justifications for using Qualitative Design.....	105
3.8.	Data Collection.....	106
3.8.1.	Sample Composition	106
3.8.2	Sample Size and Data Saturation	109
3.8.3	Data Collection Process	111
3.8.4	Pilot Study.....	113
3.9	Main Data Collection and Analysis.....	115
3.9.1	Main Data Collection Process	116
3.10	Data Analysis.....	122
3.11	Reliability, Validity, and Research Quality	126
3.11.1	Reliability and Validity	126
3.11.2	Research Quality	128
3.12	Ethical Consideration.....	130
3.13	Summary of the Chapter	132
4.	<i>FINDINGS</i>.....	133
4.1	Introduction	133
4.2	Participants for the Study.....	133
4.3	Findings	137
4.3.1	Objective 1: To explore the views and experiences of tenant entrepreneurs regarding the support and resources provided by University Business Incubation programmes.....	139
4.3.2	Objective 2: To explore views and experiences of tenant entrepreneurs regarding the shared work environment	150
4.3.3	Objective 3: To identify any challenges that entrepreneurs experience whilst	

participating in university business incubation programmes	154
4.3.4 Objective 4: To explore suggestions of tenant entrepreneurs on making the current business incubation programmes more effective.....	161
4.4 Summary of the Chapter	165
5. DISCUSSIONS OF THE FINDINGS	167
5.1 Introduction	167
5.2 Objective 1: To explore the views and experiences of tenant entrepreneurs regarding the support and resources provided by university business incubation programmes	167
5.2.1 Simplification and acceleration of new venture creation process.....	169
5.2.2 Learning from the experience of managers and advisers enabled entrepreneurs to move forward in the right direction.....	170
5.2.3 An efficient incubator manager ensures a productive incubation experience	171
5.2.4 Entrepreneurs' Responsibility.....	172
5.2.5 Source of encouragement and motivation.....	173
5.2.6 Source of getting practical experience	174
5.2.7 Access to free or affordable office space and funding opportunities provided cost saving opportunities for entrepreneurs	175
5.2.8 Access to university resources provide cost saving opportunities	176
5.3 Objective 2: To explore views and experiences of tenant entrepreneurs regarding the shared work environment provided by the university business incubation programmes	177
5.3.1 Peer learning and support	178
5.3.2 Learning through social interactions.....	180
5.3.3 Acquiring clients and services from within the cohort.....	181
5.3.4 Peer-rivalry	182
5.4 Objective 3: To identify any challenges that entrepreneurs experience whilst participating in university business incubation programmes. 	184
5.4.1 Incubator bias	185
5.4.2 Hidden motives of incubators and external stakeholders	186
5.4.3 Lack of inclusion.....	187
5.4.4 Investor's reluctance to take risks	188
5.4.5 Lack of industry specific information	189

5.4.6	Tenant entrepreneurs’ financial struggles during the incubation stage	190
5.5	Objective 4: To seek suggestions of tenant entrepreneurs on making the current business incubation programmes more effective.	191
5.5	Summary of the Chapter	194
6.	<i>CONCLUSIONS, CONTRIBUTIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS</i>	195
6.1	Introduction	195
6.2	A Brief Overview of the Research.....	195
6.3	Achieving Research Aim and Objectives.....	198
6.3.1	Objective One	199
6.3.2	Objective Two	200
6.3.3	Objective Three	201
6.3.4	Objective Four	202
6.3.5	Objective Five.....	202
6.4	Contributions of the Research.....	203
6.4.1	Theoretical Contributions	203
6.4.2	Practical Contributions	204
6.5	Recommendations.....	207
6.5.1	Recommendations to the business incubator organisers.....	207
6.5.2	Recommendation to the UK universities	209
6.5.3	Recommendation to the policymakers.....	210
6.5.4	Recommendations to the tenant entrepreneurs	210
6.6	Limitations of the Research	211
6.6.1	Access to data	211
6.6.2	Researcher’s lack of practical experience in the business incubation industry	212
6.7	Future Research.....	212
6.8	Summary of the Chapter	213
7.	<i>REFERENCES</i>.....	215
8.	<i>APPENDICES</i>	268
	Appendix 1: Participant Information Sheet.....	268
	Appendix 2: Participant Consent Form	271

Appendix 3: Ethical Approval.....	273
Appendix 4: Evidence Related to Data Analysis.....	274
A: Interview transcript and coding.....	274
B: Initial Codes and Themes.....	279
C: Diagram of Themes and Codes	282

LIST OF TABLES

Table 2-1: Start-up Types.....	33
Table 3-1: Definitions of Case Study Research	99
Table 3-2: Profile of the Respondents for Pilot Study	114
Table 3-3: Interview Guide	119
Table 3-4: Stages of Thematic Analysis.....	124
Table 3-5: Verification Strategies	127
Table 4-1: Profile of the Respondents.....	135
Table 4-2: Findings of the Research	138

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1-1: Thesis Structure.....	24
Figure 2-1: Start-up journey.....	34
Figure 2-2: Reasons for start-up failures.....	36
Figure 2-3: Critical Success Factors of Start-ups.....	41
Figure 2-4: The Evolution of Business Incubators.....	62
Figure 2-5: Conceptual Framework	80
Figure 3-1: The Research Onion Model.....	86
Figure 3-2: Deductive Approach.....	95
Figure 3-3: Inductive Approach	97
Figure 3-4: Research Design.....	104
Figure 5-1: Tenant entrepreneurs' views and perspectives regarding the support and resources provided by UBIs	168
Figure 5-2: Tenant entrepreneurs' views and perspectives of cohort involvement.....	178
Figure 5-3: Challenges faced by entrepreneurs whilst participating in UBIs	184
Figure 5-4: Tenant entrepreneurs' suggestions for improving the current business incubation programmes	191

ABSTRACT

The focus of this doctoral research is to explore tenant entrepreneurs' experiences and perspectives towards UBIs in the UK. In doing so, this study investigates the business incubation process from the perspective of tenant entrepreneurs and employs entrepreneurial learning theory. Contrary to previous studies that have adopted output-oriented approach to assess the effectiveness of business incubation programmes, this study has chosen a process-oriented approach. An extensive review of the existing literature revealed that incubatees' perspectives has been overlooked in the literature. This study takes an incubatee-centred approach and sheds light on entrepreneurs' experiences of establishing start-ups in UBIs, identifies challenges faced by the entrepreneurs and provides recommendations to the UK business incubation industry for improving the current business incubation programmes.

This study followed an interpretivist-inductive approach and utilised a qualitative research design. In order to collect the data, fourteen entrepreneurs from the UK UBI sector were interviewed with each interview lasting between forty-five to one hour and fifteen minutes. A manual thematic analysis of the collected data revealed that nascent entrepreneurs greatly benefitted from the services and resources provided by UBIs; managerial assistance and cohort participation were regarded as major contributors to the tenant entrepreneurs' learning, whilst access to financial resources, university resources, office space and access to networking opportunities also contributed to entrepreneurs' productive incubation experience. The lack of industry-specific information and personalised support was regarded as the main challenge. Few respondents also reported concerns such as incubator's bias towards alumni start-ups and favouritism in terms of additional support, hidden motives of external stakeholders, entrepreneurs' struggles to feel included, risk-averse culture, and entrepreneurs' financial struggle during the R&D stage.

The findings of this research make significant contributions to the literature by conceptualising the challenges faced by entrepreneurs while participating in UBI and by making contributions to the Entrepreneurial Learning Theory. Study findings support different approaches of ELT, namely experiential, situated, cognitive-affective and collaborative learning. The study also makes significant contributions to the professional practice by providing recommendations for improving the current UK business incubation programmes, such as enhanced

academics' involvement in incubator activities, equal support and opportunities for all tenant entrepreneurs, peer collaborations, training opportunities for incubator managers, effective mentorship, small and industry specific cohorts, informal networking opportunities and financial incentives for the entrepreneurs during the research phase.

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this work has not previously been accepted in substance for any degree and is not being concurrently submitted for any other degree.

This thesis is the result of my own investigations, except where otherwise stated. Other sources are acknowledged by explicit references.

Signature:

Date: 28-08-2021

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviations Meanings

<i>BI</i>	Business Incubation
<i>UBI</i>	University Business Incubation
<i>UK</i>	United Kingdom
<i>BA</i>	Business Accelerators
<i>R&D</i>	Research and Development
<i>UKBI</i>	United Kingdom Business Incubation
<i>NBIA</i>	National Business Incubation Association
<i>NESTA</i>	National Endowment for Science, Technology and Arts

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background of the Study

Business Incubators (BIs) are start-up support programmes designed to support nascent innovative start-ups (Autio *et al.*, 2018; Spigel, 2017; CSES, 2002) by offering them a wide array of services and resources (Bruneel *et al.*, 2012; Dee *et al.*, 2015). The concept of business incubation has gained popularity all over the world in the last few decades (Chandra *et al.*, 2012; Hausberg and Korreck, 2018) as policy makers are utilising these start-up support mechanisms to foster entrepreneurship and economic growth. University Business Incubators (UBIs) are a form of BIs (Hassan, 2020), that serves the same role as conventional business incubators (Grimaldi and Grandi, 2005). There are currently around 130 incubators and accelerators¹ organised by UK universities, with £20-30 million in public funds being spent on these start-up support mechanisms each year (Bone *et al.*, 2017). However, there is a scarcity of compelling evidence about their impact on tenant start-ups (Bennett *et al.*, 2017).

Success indicators are frequently established on funding agreements and generally need numerical data on tenant firm's survival and success rates, profitability, and job creation (Jones *et al.*, 2021). The impact of business incubators on tenant start-ups has been the focus of researchers for many years (Albort-Morant and Ribeiro-Soriano, 2016; Baraldi and Havensvid, 2016). Several studies have been conducted to determine the effectiveness of these start-up support mechanisms (Such as Amezcua *et al.*, 2013; Bone *et al.*, 2019; Colombo and Delmastro, 2002; Lasrado *et al.*, 2016; Rothaermel and Thursby, 2005; Schwartz 2009; Sehitoglu and Ozdesmir, 2013; Voisey *et al.*, 2013, etc.). However, the results have been contradictory (Patton, 2014), and the impact of incubation programmes on tenant start-ups has been a subject of disagreement among business incubation researchers for years.

¹ Business accelerator (BA) performs the same function as business incubators. Incubators and accelerators both have the same objective of assisting nascent start-ups in their early and vulnerable stages of growth. Hence both are part of the wider definition of business incubation (Dee *et al.*, 2015).

Vanderstraeten and Matthyssens (2010) argue that confining the success evaluation of BIs to simply limited success metrics is a miscalculation as this can restrict the comprehension of the BIs phenomenon.

Nevertheless, business incubation researchers have extensively emphasised evaluating the effectiveness of business incubators in terms of quantifiable measures such as tenant firm's performance, profitability, and survival, while ignoring intangible variables such as tenant entrepreneurs' learning and experience during the incubation stage. The literature on the use of quantifiable measures to understand BI's role is clearly disputed. Some scholars (Lukes *et al.* 2019; Mian *et al.*, 2016; Theodorakopoulos *et al.*, 2014) criticise this output-oriented approach and advocate for a more comprehensive and process-oriented approach that involves soft metrics such as tenant entrepreneurs' learning and development to assess the effectiveness of business incubation programmes.

Although widely ignored in the business incubation literature, the intangible metrics of success, such as the learning and experience of tenant entrepreneurs during the incubation stage are potentially just as essential in the development of entrepreneurship (Politis and Gabrielsson, 2015). Entrepreneurs take part in the business incubation programmes to acquire essential knowledge, resources and connections that may assist them in their entrepreneurial endeavours. BIs encourage entrepreneurial learning for nascent start-ups by offering various services and resources (Bergek and Norrman, 2008; Peters *et al.*, 2004). It is helpful to understand how the incubation process equips them for their entrepreneurial journey.

The main focus of this research is to investigate the perceptions of tenant entrepreneurs towards the services and resources provided by UBIs, which is a type of BIs with the same objective as BIs. In doing so, this study investigates the business incubation process from the perspective of incubatees² or tenant entrepreneurs in the context of UBI, as incubatee-perspective has been widely overlooked in the literature. It is important to understand incubates perceptions as it

² The tenant start-ups or entrepreneurs that are registered or enrolled in an incubator are referred to as incubatees (Hackett and Dilts, 2004b).

can substantially help in improving the current services provided by UBIs and BIs. Perception is defined by Kleiger and Weiner (2021) as the cognitive judgement or interpretation that individuals make about their experiences. This study uses the term perception in describing perspectives or views and experiences of tenant entrepreneurs towards different aspects of incubation programmes.

1.1.1. Entrepreneurship as a tool for economic development

Entrepreneurs have a crucial role to spark economic development by starting new ventures, creating employment opportunities, contributing to the GDP and exports, contributing to regional and community development (Jones et al, 2021; Glancey and McQuaid, 2000). From Schumpeter to modern-day economists, entrepreneurs starting new ventures are seen as a driving force for economic growth (Audretsch *et al.*, 2006; Dutta and Crossan, 2005; Fritsch, 2011; Hekkert *et al.*, 2006;). In today's open economies, entrepreneurship is more crucial than ever for economic growth (Klotz *et al.*, 2014) because start-ups drive innovation and economic growth (Diakanastasi *et al.*, 2018), especially tech start-ups due to their innovation-driven environment play a vital role in the economy (Levie and Autio, 2008; Yu *et al.*, 2009; Schneider and Veugelers, 2010, Veugelers, 2009).

There is a strong connection between a country's economic development and its national innovation structure (Intarakumnerd *et al.*, 2002; Nelson, 1993). Start-ups drive innovation and economic growth (Diakanastasi *et al.*, 2018). According to Forsman (2011) and McKeever, Anderson and Jack (2014), entrepreneurial activity is crucial for long-lasting economic growth and development to prevail. Governments around the world are promoting entrepreneurial graduates in order to build entrepreneurial economies that include competition, growth, innovation, and creativity (Peckernell *et al.*, 2011). The United Kingdom is committed to supporting graduates to become entrepreneurs and establish new businesses (Costa-David 2004; Jones *et al.*, 2014).

Several government policies have been developed all around the world to encourage entrepreneurial activity and small enterprises (Blok *et al.*, 2017). These policies, despite being well-intended and broadly applicable, have been the subject of researchers' criticism (Acs *et al.*, 2016; Shane, 2009). BIs and UBIs seek the same purpose as these public policies which is to promote entrepreneurship (Mian, 1996;

NBIA, 2011). A business incubator is a facility that offers affordable physical space to new ventures along with other shared facilities and support (Dee *et al.*, 2015).

1.1.2. Entrepreneurial Landscape in the UK

The number of enterprises in the United Kingdom in 2018 was 5.7 million, dropping 27,000 from 2017 (Department of Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy³, 2019). Business birth rates increased consistently from 269,000 in 2012 to 414,000 in 2016 but dropped to 381,000 in 2018 (Office for National Statistics⁴, 2019). For six consecutive years, business birth rates outpaced 'death rates,' implying stock of firms continually increase (Jones *et al.*, 2021). Given that small firms provide an influx of new jobs in the UK, business start-ups are critical to the UK's job creation and economic prosperity (Anyadike-Danes *et al.*, 2015), just as they are in any other country. Yet relatively few UK start-ups mature into fast-growing enterprises with the capacity to have a significant impact on the long-term economic expansion (Jones *et al.*, 2014).

Since the start of the 21st century, the UK government has been devoted to supporting graduate entrepreneurs to launch start-ups (Jones *et al.*, 2014). There are around 130 incubators and accelerators organised by universities in the UK, with £20-30 million in public funds spent on these start-up support mechanisms each year (Bone *et al.*, 2019). In addition, participation in European or domestic R&D initiatives allows university incubators to obtain additional funding (Barbero *et al.*, 2012). University business incubation programmes help nascent start-ups by providing structural resources, knowledge, new technologies, consultations, financial sources, and network access (Andreassi and Fujino, 2016).

Incubators are not a recent development in the UK; as the oldest incubator, St John's Innovation Centre was established in 1987 in Cambridge (Bone *et al.*, 2019). Over the last few decades, the UK has seen a substantial rise in the number of business

³ <https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/business-population-estimates>.

⁴

<https://www.ons.gov.uk/businessindustryandtrade/changestobusiness/businessbirthsdeathsandsurvivalrates>.

incubators and accelerators and according to BEIS⁵ report, in 2017 there were more than 200 incubators and 163 accelerators active in the UK (Bone *et al.*, 2017). A number of incubators are to some extent self-funded by membership fees or rent paid by tenants incubates, although they are frequently sponsored by universities or public funding (Bone *et al.*, 2017). According to the authors, in the UK, 72% of the business incubators are partly funded by rent or membership fees, 43% are funded by public money and 34% are funded by universities. Furthermore, the association between incubators and universities is not just limited to funding as a vast majority of incubators in the UK are directly operated by universities. According to an analysis of the BEIS business incubator and accelerator directory, more than 90 % of mentioned affiliation with the university (Bone *et al.*, 2017).

In the UK, approximately 6,900 companies are supported by incubators at a time. Incubators are fairly equally spread across the United Kingdom, mostly in university campuses or in outlying research and business parks, and most of the incubators primarily support tech start-ups (Bone *et al.*, 2019). Given the significant amount of funding that goes into these start-up support programmes each year, it is critical to learn about the incubation experiences of the incubatees, as this can help the UBIs to enhance the services and add value propositions to their business model.

1.1.3. Business Incubators and University Business Incubators as a Tool for Entrepreneurship Development

BIs and UBIs are enterprise development tools, designed to foster innovative start-ups by providing a supportive and controlled work environment (Autio *et al.*, 2018; European Commission, 2002; Lalkaka and Bishop, 1996; UKBI, 2013). The creation of UBIs in the United Kingdom is based on the government's presumption that entrepreneurs attempting to commercialise innovations into business projects face obstacles, often referred to as 'liability of newness' (Aldrich and Fiol, 1994;

5

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/608409/business-incubators-accelerators-uk-report.pdf

Jayawarna *et al.*, 2011; Shepherd *et al.*, 2000; Shane and Khurana, 2003). Policy makers in the UK have focused on knowledge as the core competitive differentiator and as a result, several business incubators have been established in collaboration with universities aiming to promote entrepreneurship and innovation (Hannon and Chaplin, 2003; Jones *et al.*, 2014; Reid and Garnsey, 1998).

Business incubation is a structural mechanism that focuses on cultivating an entrepreneurial ecosystem in a region (UKBI, 2012; 2013). Incubation is the process of assisting a start-up in order to maximise its chances of surviving and becoming an established business (European Commission, 2002; National Business Incubation Association, 2011). This process intends to equip the entrepreneurs with the necessary knowledge, as well as provide a controlled environment to ensure their venture smoothly goes through the early stages of its formation (Theodorakopoulos *et al.*, 2014), nevertheless, it is the entrepreneur's ultimate responsibility to keep their venture afloat. Business incubation's notion is based on the proposition of enhancing the survival chances and development of new innovative ventures with great potential by establishing support and resources (Ayatse *et al.*, 2017). Incubation seeks to achieve a number of crucial goals, aiming at improving the overall economic development by creating new employment opportunities, promoting entrepreneurship in the community, commercializing the technology and encouraging technology advancement (Al- Mubarak and Busler, 2011; Bizzotto, 2003; Nicholls-Nixon, 2020).

Incubators fulfil the purpose of business incubation by providing physical space and infrastructure, business support and guidance, networking and funding opportunities to new ventures (Stal *et al.*, 2016; Ayatse *et al.*, 2017). These start-up support mechanisms play a crucial role in the entrepreneurial ecosystem by integrating different parties such as entrepreneurs, investors, mentors, universities and tech professionals on one platform (Al- Mubarak and Busler, 2011; Levakova, 2012).

Several universities in the UK provide business incubation programmes to promote entrepreneurship by assisting recent graduates to initiate entrepreneurial paths (Voisey *et al.*, 2013). It is not easy for recent graduates to pursue entrepreneurial paths due to their lack of enterprise and industry experience and the burden of student loans, and not to mention their lack of credibility with investors and resource

providers, and limited social networks (Jones *et al.*, 2021). However, incubators can assist in overcoming such disadvantages in a variety of ways (Jones *et al.*, 2021), such as connecting them with the wider entrepreneurial ecosystem (Van Weele *et al.* 2018) and providing them access to funding opportunities (McAdam *et al.*, 2016).

Due to the growing interest in business incubation around the world, there has been an intensified demand to learn more about the function of incubators in assisting emerging start-ups (Mian *et al.*, 2016). There is a plethora of studies assessing the impact of business incubation programmes on tenant firms, but the results are varied. While some studies indicate that incubator backed start-ups have a better survival rate (such as Bone *et al.*, 2019; Cabello *et al.* 2007; Voisey *et al.*, 2013), others show contradictory results (Hansen *et al.*, 2000; Hughes *et al.*, 2007; Patton, 2014; Schwartz, 2012). The incubator's success is determined by its aim or goal, and it does not always equate to the success of the incubatee, and thereby the elements that drive an incubator's success differ from those that enable incubatees to prosper (Bacalan *et al.*, 2019). Entrepreneurs take part in business incubation programmes to acquire essential knowledge, resources and connections that can assist them in their entrepreneurial endeavour (Mattushek, 2020). It is essential to understand how the incubation process equips them for their entrepreneurial journey. Ayatse *et al.* (2017) and Lewis *et al.* (2011) considered incubator's practices and services as the most pivotal determinant of its incubator's effectiveness. Understanding the incubation process from the perspective of tenant entrepreneurs can provide valuable insight that can help incubation programmes become more effective.

1.2. Research Problem

Several studies have attempted to determine the impact of business incubation on tenant start-ups; however, they have either adopted a quantitative approach (i.e., Almeida *et al.*, 2021; Bacalan *et al.* 2019; Breznitz and Zhang 2019; Khalid *et al.*, 2017; Lasrado *et al.* 2016; Scillitoe and Chakrabarti, 2010; Soetanto and Jack 2016; Wann *et al.* 2017) or qualitative studies that have adopted a cross-sectional study design focusing on different stakeholders' perspectives (Ahmad and Thornberry 2018; Kakabadse *et al.* 2020; Nair and Blomquist 2019; Patton, 2014). In addition,

some studies have attempted to investigate the business incubation process from the standpoint of incubator managers (Mian 2014; Redondo and Camarero, 2019). Researchers have primarily focused on assessing and describing the success of business incubators in terms of tangible metrics such as firm's performance, profitability, survival, etc., however, the intangible metrics of success, such as learning and experience of tenant entrepreneurs during the incubation stage are potentially just as essential in the development of entrepreneurship (Politis and Gabrielsson, 2015). This approach of measuring success in terms of quantifiable metrics while ignoring the soft metrics fails to capture entrepreneurs' journey of the incubation period (Mian, 2014). Measuring the success and effectiveness of incubation programmes in purely tangible and quantifiable outputs overlooks the intangible or soft metrics for instance the experience, knowledge and learning of tenant entrepreneurs. To address this gap, recent studies (Mian *et al.*, 2016; Theodorakopoulos *et al.*, 2014) have advocated for more process- based research that investigates softer indicators of business incubation success.

Besides, the literature on the use of quantifiable measures to understand BI's role is clearly disputed. Since universities receiving public funding to operate incubation programmes, they face the immense public and government scrutiny to illustrate outcomes of the incubation; however, the outcomes are frequently ambiguous, as the configuration of appropriate measures to determine effectiveness is mainly unsettled (Lubik, 2016). As the literature on the employment of quantifiable metrics to comprehend the effectiveness of incubators is controversial (Torun *et al.*, 2018), it is critical to understand the effectiveness of these programmes using soft measures as the success of start-up businesses are said to be influenced by the results of entrepreneurial learning (Deakins and Freel, 1998; Man, 2007; Olugbola, 2017). Despite this incubatee-perspective is conspicuously missing from discussions of the business incubation effectiveness. This study addresses this gap by adopting an incubatee-perspective approach to explore tenant entrepreneurs' perceptions towards business incubation programmes.

Moreover, a review of the literature also revealed that, despite a rapid increase in the number of business incubators over the last few decades, the success rate of start-ups that participate in these programmes is undetermined. Success is overstated in

the business incubator industry, while failures are understated (Dee *et al.*, 2011; Voisey *et al.*, 2006). Most business incubators do not keep track of their results beyond the number of ventures that graduate, and the data is unreliable for those that track the results (Alpenidze *et al.*, 2019) as failures are often unreported. The reason for the unreliability of incubator data, according to Hackett and Dilts (2004b), is that non-profit incubators' financing decisions are based on their success. Also, universities have immense pressure to ensure that the public funds provided to them for the promotion of their business incubation operations are being used effectively (Nicholls-Nixon, 2020). It is no surprise that unsuccessful start-ups go unreported. Moreover, the incubator's success is determined by its aim or goal, and it does not always equate to the success of the incubatee, and thereby the elements that drive an incubator's success differ from those that enable incubatees to prosper (Bacalan *et al.*, 2019). Exploring tenant entrepreneurs' experiences of business incubation, as well as investigating the challenges they face and collecting their suggestions for improving business incubation programmes, can help to better understand the incubation process and thereby provide excellent insight into making improvements that can contribute positively to enhancing the current incubation programmes.

1.3. Research Aim, Objectives, and Questions

This study aims to explore tenant entrepreneurs' perspectives and experiences of participating in a university business incubator and analyse how it assist them during the start of their entrepreneurial journey.

In order to fulfil this aim, the following research objectives are formulated:

- To explore the views and experience of tenant entrepreneurs regarding the support and resources provided by UBIs.
- To understand the perspectives and experience of tenant entrepreneurs regarding the shared work environment provided by the UBIs.
- To identify any challenges that tenant entrepreneurs experience during the incubation process.
- To explore the suggestions of the tenant entrepreneurs on making the current business incubation programmes more effective.
- To provide recommendations to the UK business incubation industry for enhancing the current UBI programmes.

As previously stated, the goal of this study is to address the primary research question: 'How do entrepreneurs benefit by taking part in a university incubation programme, and what can be done to further enhance their experience?' The following sub-questions are devised in order to address the primary research question and the research objectives.

RQ1: What do tenant entrepreneurs perceive about the services, support, and resources provided by the university's business incubation programmes?

This research question, which relates to the first research objective, is designed to explore tenant entrepreneurs' experiences regarding the services and resources provided by UBIs. Previous studies have primarily focused on assessing and describing the success of business incubators in terms of tangible or quantifiable metrics such as start-up performance, profitability, survival, etc., however, the soft or intangible metrics of success, such as learning and experience of tenant entrepreneur, are potentially just as essential in the development of entrepreneurship. Researchers (such as Ayatse *et al.*, 2017; Lewis *et al.*, 2011) have considered incubator's practices and services as the most pivotal determinant of incubator's effectiveness. However, few studies have examined the business incubation process from the perspective of tenant entrepreneurs (such as Cohen, 2013; Meckel, 2014; Martínez *et al.*, 2018). This research question is designed to examine incubatees' perceptions regarding the university business incubation process in the UK.

RQ2: What do tenant entrepreneurs perceive about the shared work environment provided by the university incubation programmes?

UBIs offer tenant entrepreneurs an opportunity to work with other like-minded individuals who have the same entrepreneurial aspirations. This is a unique aspect of business incubators since it offers entrepreneurs access to the entrepreneurial network. This research question relates to the second research objective and is developed to conduct an in-depth examination of associations among tenant entrepreneurs in the cohort, rather than investigating the correlation between business incubator facilities and services and the achievement of tenant start-ups, which had been the focus of several previous studies (such as Al-Mubarak and

Wong, 2011; Ayatse *et al.*, 2017; Hannon 2003; Hackett and Dilts 2008; Khalid *et al.*, 2017; Lee and Osteryoung 2004; Todorovic and Moenter 2010; Zhang and Sonobe 2011). The purpose of this research question is to learn about entrepreneurs' experiences of working in a cohort and evaluate how it helped them in their entrepreneurial journey.

RQ3: What are the challenges or obstacles experienced by tenant entrepreneurs during the incubation phase?

This research question, which relates to the third research objective, is designed to identify any challenges experienced by tenant entrepreneurs during the incubation stage. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, no prior study has been conducted to conceptualise the obstacles faced by incubatees during the incubation stage. According to BEIS (2017) report, the UK devotes a significant amount of funds to business incubation programmes each year. Therefore, it is crucial to identify any issues encountered by entrepreneurs that may have a detrimental influence on their incubation experience.

RQ4: What measures can be taken to mitigate the challenges faced by tenant entrepreneurs during the incubation stage?

This research question links to the previous question and the fourth objective of the study which is to seek entrepreneurs' opinions on addressing the challenges faced by them during the incubation stage. No previous study, to the best of the researcher's knowledge, has aimed at seeking incubatees views on improving the current business incubation programmes. This research question is intended to elicit tenant entrepreneurs' perspectives on how to address issues that arise during the incubation period.

RQ5: What steps can be taken by the UK university business incubation industry to enhance the current business incubation programmes?

The final research question, which pertains to the study's fifth objective, is intended to provide recommendations to the UK business incubation industry and its stakeholders, based on the findings of the study, on how to improve the present incubation process in order to achieve optimum outcomes.

1.4. Rationale

Start-ups and SMEs are the backbones of any economy. However, most start-ups fail during the first five years of their existence (Cantamessa *et al.*, 2018; Eisenmann, 2021). In order to reduce start-up failures as well as to promote innovative entrepreneurship, governments around the world have introduced various business incubation programmes. As highlighted in section 1.1 of this thesis, numerous studies have been conducted to examine the effectiveness of such programmes on start-up performance, and the vast majority of the studies focus on the quantifiable measures of incubator's success, ignoring the soft measures such as entrepreneur's learning and experience. Some studies have also been conducted from incubatees perspectives (i.e., as Bacalan *et al.*, 2019; Cohen, 2013; Mattushek, 2020; Meckel, 2014; Scillitoe and Chakrabarti, 2010), with their primary focus being on identifying the effectiveness of these programmes. An extensive review of the literature revealed that no previous study was conducted to conceptualise the challenges faced by incubatees whilst participating in business incubation programmes, particularly in the context of the UK university business incubation.

The present study addresses this gap by examining the incubation process from the perspective of tenant entrepreneurs rather than the incubator managers and organisers, as incubatees' perspectives have been widely overlooked in the business incubation literature. This unique approach enables a more in-depth examination of the business incubation process in a UBI context from the viewpoint of tenant entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurs take part in the university business incubation programmes to acquire essential knowledge, resources and connections that can assist them in their entrepreneurial endeavour. It is essential to understand how these incubation processes equip them for their entrepreneurial journey, as incubator's practices and services are considered as the most pivotal determinant of its effectiveness (Ayatse *et al.*, 2017; Lewis *et al.*, 2011).

A business incubator provides a controlled work environment for the development of innovative start-ups (Autio *et al.*, 2018; Lalkaka and Bishop, 1996) which implies that a business incubator can influence the growth of tenant start-ups by altering the service's content, form, and level of service (Wang *et al.*, 2008). The incubator's services are very likely to impact the success of tenant start-ups, such as the survival

rate and growth rate (Sehitoglu and Ozdemir, 2013; Wang *et al.*, 2008). According to Ayatse *et al.* (2017) and Lewis *et al.* (2011), the most critical determinant of an incubator's effectiveness is its best practice. Erikson and Gjellan (2003) argued that the training provided by the business incubator increases the learning efficiency of tenant entrepreneurs. Therefore, it is important to understand the incubation experience of the tenant entrepreneurs, as well as how the incubation process takes place and how it assists the entrepreneurs in setting up a new venture. Understanding the business incubation process from the perspective of tenant entrepreneurs can substantially help in improving the services provided by incubators and further improve the process. Furthermore, the business model of incubators has been constantly evolving in order to meet the demands of the sector (Grimaldi and Grandi, 2005; Hansen *et al.*, 2000; Lalkaka and Bishop, 1996), and understanding the perceptions of tenant entrepreneurs can help the UBI industry to extend their value proposition.

Furthermore, every year around £20-30 million of public funds is dedicated to business incubators and accelerators in the UK (Bone *et al.*, 2017). However, there is a scarcity of compelling evidence about their impact on tenant start-ups (Bennett *et al.*, 2017). Hence, understanding the tenant entrepreneurs' experience of the current incubation process can aid in the development of an incubation programme that meets the needs of entrepreneurs. Furthermore, because an incubator itself is an entity, the success of its services is critical not only for the tenant start-ups' development but also for the incubator's own promotion (Rice, 2002; Wang *et al.*, 2008).

In regard to personal motivations for the research, the researcher noticed that very few studies have been undertaken on investigating the perspective of incubatees regarding the business incubation process, providing the researcher with a unique opportunity to contribute to the knowledge. In addition, the researcher's career aspiration, which is to pursue a career as a researcher developer, prompted her to choose business incubation as a research topic as it is gaining increasing popularity and universities around the world are establishing business incubators and accelerators. The researcher believes that gaining research experience in this emerging field can lead to a variety of career prospects in academia as well as in

industry.

1.5. Brief Descriptions of the Research Methodology

This research investigates the perceptions of current and former tenant entrepreneurs of the university business incubation programmes in the UK. In order to explore the views and experiences of the entrepreneurs towards the current university business incubation programmes, the interpretivist research philosophy was considered appropriate as it would allow the researcher to subjectively investigate respondents' experiences, feelings, and emotions. The interpretivist research philosophy was also considered relevant as little academic work has been previously done in the area of business incubation, particularly from incubatees' perspectives.

A qualitative research method was used for collecting the primary research data and semi-structured interviews with fourteen current and former tenant entrepreneurs were conducted with each interview lasting between forty-five minutes to one hour and fifteen minutes. A qualitative method was considered most appropriate as the purpose of the study was to investigate tenant entrepreneurs' experience of the support and resources provided by UBI programmes in the UK rather than confirming any existing theories or hypotheses. Research data was collected using an interview guide comprising of semi-structured and open-ended questions; the interview sample was selected purposively after carefully considering factors such as time, accessibility, and resources, and data was acquired and analysed concurrently. Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-step thematic analysis was used to analyse the interview data. During the analysis process, the research findings were constantly evaluated in order to interpret and generate the meaning of respondents' perspectives of university business incubation programme experience. A detailed discussion of research methodology is provided in chapter 3 of this thesis.

1.6. Limitations of the Study

This study focuses on university business incubation programmes in the United Kingdom and aims to explore tenant entrepreneurs' perceptions of the services and resources provided by these programmes. The participants in this study are entrepreneurs who have participated in a university business incubation programme in the UK, and the findings of this study are applicable to university and commercial business incubation programmes across the country. This study seeks to provide rich insights into tenant entrepreneurs' perspectives of the university business incubation process. However, there are certain possible limitations to this study, such as generalisability constraints due to a rather limited sample size. Although a number of findings were consistent with current literature and repeated by many respondents, it is probable that a larger sample of people might have led to additional themes. Due to time restrictions and unforeseen data gathering challenges, it was decided not to use a quantitative method. In addition, the researcher intended to use observations for triangulation purposes in this study, but due to restrictions imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic and the subsequent unexpected shift to working remotely from home, as well as time constraints, the researcher was unable to use observations in the incubator setting. Moreover, the researcher's decision to choose the research topic is motivated by a sense of curiosity and a desire to learn more about the subject and contribute to current knowledge. Hence, the findings were totally relied on interviewee responses due to the researcher's lack of practical expertise and experience in the business incubation field. However, the majority of the findings were in accordance with previous studies.

1.7. Contributions of the Research

As the tenant entrepreneur's perspective has been widely overlooked in the extant literature, this study fills the research gap and makes an original contribution to the knowledge by providing a rich insight into entrepreneurs' experiences of participating in UBIs, identifying challenges faced by entrepreneurs during the incubation phase, seeking entrepreneurs perspectives on mitigating those challenges, and finally devising recommendations for the business incubation

industry based on the findings of the study. The study makes contributions to theory and practice by exploring entrepreneurs' perceptions of UBIs using the entrepreneurial learning theory as a theoretical framework. The contributions of this study are highlighted in detail in Chapter 6, section 6.4, and are briefly mentioned in this section.

First, this research makes contributions to the knowledge by adopting an incubatee-centred approach and focusing primarily on perspectives and experiences of the tenant entrepreneurs rather than the incubator managers and organisers. This research sheds light on entrepreneurial learning in the business incubation context and the study findings support different approaches of the entrepreneurial learning theory, including experiential learning, situated learning, cognitive-affective learning and collaborative learning. The findings of the study indicate that business incubation programmes support entrepreneurial learning by providing tenant entrepreneurs with a shared environment where they not only learn from experienced managers and mentors but also acquire useful knowledge from one another. Findings of the study also emphasised the importance of the role of incubator manager, suggesting that the incubator manager is not only a critical success factor for tenant start-ups, but also has a significant impact on the incubator's overall performance. Second, no previous study, to the best of the researcher's knowledge, has sought to identify challenges encountered by tenant entrepreneurs during the incubation phase, or to solicit suggestions from them on how to improve the incubation experience. The findings of this research, therefore, make contributions to the body of knowledge by revealing the challenges entrepreneurs face whilst participating in UBI. This research identified numerous challenges such as unconscious bias, incubator's preference to sponsor university start-ups over other start-ups, a risk-averse culture in the incubator industry, generalised information in the incubators, and entrepreneurs financial struggle during the R&D phase.

In terms of practical contributions, this study provides practical recommendations to business incubator organisers and directors, universities and policy makers. This study suggests that business incubators should be associated with local universities since it could provide incubatees with cost-effective alternatives while also providing students with various opportunities to obtain work experience. This study

also stresses the importance of providing equal support and opportunities to all tenant start-ups regardless of their affiliation with home university, as the findings indicate that UBIs are biased towards sponsoring university alumni start-ups, and start-ups that are more likely to succeed. The study also highlights the importance of peer support and recommends peer collaborations among current and former incubatees to foster regional entrepreneurship and innovation. In addition, the study emphasises the importance of effective mentoring and proposes that formal peer mentoring opportunities be made available to incubatees. Findings of the study also indicate that the Y-Combinator business model, which allows for a large number of start-ups in a cohort, does not offer adequate and tailored support to tenant entrepreneurs, and that incubators should have small industry-specific cohorts. The outcomes of this study are valuable to both theory and practice and offer valuable recommendations to the business incubation organisers and directors as the business model of incubators has been constantly developing ever since the first business incubator came into being, and the understanding of the tenant entrepreneurs' perspectives of current UBI services and resources is a significant contribution as it can help the business incubation industry create excellent value propositions.

1.8. Thesis Structure

This thesis consists of six chapters and figure 1.1 depicts the outline of the thesis.

Chapter 1: Introduction has set the scene and established the context of this thesis by shedding light on the background of the research topic, the rationale behind the choice of the topic, aim and objectives of the research, scope, expected contributions and possible limitations, and a brief description of research methodology.

Chapter 2: Following the introduction chapter, the next chapter consists of a review of relevant literature and this chapter is divided into two parts. The first part reviews the key literature related to entrepreneurial learning, whereas the second part examines the business incubation literature. The chapter concludes with a discussion of interpretations from the review of the literature and the development of a conceptual framework.

Chapter 3: This chapter discusses the research methodology and contains a discussion on the research philosophy and justification for the research paradigm and methodology, research process and design, research population and sample. It also presents the process of data collection starting from the pilot interview process, modifications made as a result of the pilot study, recruitment of the participants of the research and interview process. The data analysis process and ethical considerations are also discussed in this chapter.

Chapter 4: This chapter presents the findings of the thematic analysis in alignment with the research objectives. Emerging themes are presented in this chapter, along with corroborating quotes from the participants, to convey a comprehensive picture of incubatees' experiences of UBIs.

Chapter 5: This chapter consists of a discussion of the findings of this study in relation to research objectives. It discusses the key findings with reference to objectives one, two, three and four. The findings are related and compared with the extant literature.

Chapter 6: The final chapter concludes this thesis and starts with a summary of the research. It presents practical and theoretical contributions of the thesis, recommendations to stakeholders such as business incubator organisers, universities, policy makers and tenant entrepreneurs. It also identifies the limitations of the study and presents future research recommendations.

Chapter one: Introduction
<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 10px; text-align: center;"> Background of the study Research problem Aim and objectives Rationale of the research </div>
Chapter two: Literature Review
<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 10px; text-align: center;"> Review of entrepreneurial learning literature Review of business incubation literature Summary and conceptual framework </div>
Chapter three: Research Methodology
<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 10px; text-align: center;"> Research philosophy Research approach Research strategy Research method </div>
Chapter four: Findings
<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 10px; text-align: center;"> Research Findings </div>
Chapter five: Discussion
<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 10px; text-align: center;"> Discussion of findings in relation to research objectives </div>
Chapter six: Conclusion, Contributions and Recommendations
<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 10px; text-align: center;"> Conclusion and summary of research Contributions of the research Recommendations to stakeholders Limitations and call for future research </div>

Figure 1-1: Thesis Structure

Source: Researcher

1.9. Summary of the Chapter

Start-ups have always been seen as a force that drives the economy and have substantial impacts on regional development, however, start-ups have to overcome substantial hurdles to bring their new successful ideas to the market. Incubation programmes are designed to help nascent entrepreneurs during the initial and fragile stages of venture creation and development by providing training and development, access to funding, networking opportunities and a range of other support. The overall goal of an incubator is to improve the new venture's odds of surviving its early years. University business incubators UBIs are a form of BIs and have a similar role as the conventional business incubators. Recent decades have witnessed substantial development in the field of academic entrepreneurship as universities are widely seen as a tool to foster entrepreneurship and enhance regional economic growth.

Over the last few decades, the UK has seen a substantial rise in the number of business incubators and accelerators. There are currently around 130 incubators and accelerators organised by universities in the UK, with £20-30 million in public funds spent on these start-up support mechanisms each year. However, there is a scarcity of compelling evidence about their impact on tenant start-ups. Although there are a plethora of studies on measuring the impact of BIs, researchers have primarily focused on assessing the success of business incubators in terms of tangible metrics such as firm's performance, profitability, survival, etc.; however, the intangible metrics of incubator success, such as learning and incubation experience of tenant entrepreneur, are potentially just as essential in the development of entrepreneurship. Although researchers have considered incubator's practices and services as the most pivotal determinant of its effectiveness, and previous studies have emphasised the importance of understanding the incubation process from the perspective of tenant entrepreneurs, few attempts have been made to investigate the incubatee perspective of the incubation process. This research aims to address this gap by exploring tenant entrepreneurs' perceptions regarding the services and resources offered by UBI, and identify any challenges encountered by entrepreneurs during the incubation process, seek and evaluate their suggestions on mitigating those challenges and finally offer recommendations to the business incubation

industry to enhance the current business incubation programmes.

Entrepreneurs join the incubator programme with the aim to advance their start-up idea and with the expectation that such development will require learning. It is important to investigate entrepreneurs' perspective of the business incubation process as the success of start-ups depends on these individuals and the skills and experience, they gain during the incubation phase. This study employs a qualitative method and intends to achieve its goals by employing an incubatees-centred approach and concentrating exclusively on the perspectives of the tenant entrepreneurs instead of the incubator managers and directors.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Introduction

This chapter extensively reviews the existing literature on business incubation and entrepreneurial learning. The literature review adopted a traditional narrative approach (Hammersley, 2001), and is divided into two sections. As this study focuses on the incubatees or entrepreneurs in the incubators, the first part of the literature review discusses the literature related to entrepreneurial learning, whereas the second part sheds light on the concept of business incubation, outlines the evolution of the business incubator idea and relevant academic literature. The latter part of the chapter presents a research conceptual framework.

This chapter critically reviews business incubation literature, in order to demonstrate the knowledge gap, establish a theoretical baseline, and improve knowledge of the research topic. In order to identify the relevant literature, the researcher used databases such as EBSCO, Google Scholar, IEEE Xplore, Scopus, Emerald Insights, and Science Direct. It was observed in the literature that scholars have labelled business incubators under a variety of interchangeable terms over the years, making the business incubation phenomenon challenging to study. To find relevant literature for the study, the researcher used terms and phrases such as business incubators, business incubation, technology business incubators, start-up incubators, academic entrepreneurship, university business incubators and incubation, university spin-offs, and entrepreneurial or incubatee learning in business incubation programmes.

Part I: Entrepreneurial Learning

This part of the chapter discusses the literature related to entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial learning. The purpose of nascent entrepreneurs who attend incubators and accelerators is to advance their start-up idea, with the premise that this advancement will require some aspect of learning (Mattushek, 2020). Therefore, a discussion of business incubation involves a discussion of entrepreneurial learning.

2.2. Entrepreneurship: An Introduction

Schumpeter (1949) described the entrepreneurial process of instigating spectacular structural transformation and development through "creative destruction" (Schumpeter, 1949 cited in Cumming *et al.*, 2014, p.164). Without entrepreneurs, capital, manpower, and innovation would be unable to stimulate economic development (Cumming *et al.*, 2014). Entrepreneurs play a critical role in igniting economic growth by establishing new businesses, creating jobs, adding to GDP and exports, and contributing to regional and community development (Cumming *et al.*, 2014; Jones et al, 2021; Glancey and McQuaid, 2000).

Entrepreneurship literature has considerably evolved over the years (Wang, 2014). Shane and Venkataraman (2000, 2001) significantly contributed to the development and popularity of entrepreneurship literature. The concept of entrepreneurship has gained significant attention over the last two decades (McMullen *et al.*, 2020). During this time scholars with similar perspectives on entrepreneurship drew toward one another, resulting in rigorous academic conversations and the formation of research communities; consequently, the entrepreneurial phenomenon became more contextualised and different aspects of entrepreneurship, such as corporate entrepreneurship, social entrepreneurship, and most recently academic entrepreneurship, began to emerge (McMullen *et al.*, 2020).

Scholars researching entrepreneurship are becoming more intrigued in the setting in which it occurs (Parkinson *et al.*, 2017). Researchers have traditionally focused on individual traits and behaviours of entrepreneurs (Cardon *et al.*, 2009); however,

over time, the concept of entrepreneurs as individuals who generate ideas and carry out their activities while embedded in social and professional environments has emerged (Bhansing *et al.*, 2018) and the image of the entrepreneur as a solo hero has faded. Entrepreneurship research has focused to learn how opportunities are recognized, developed, and utilised, by whom, and with what outcomes (Shane and Venkataraman, 2000; Venkataraman, 1997). Over the past decades, a significant proportion of the studies are focusing on the entrepreneurs themselves and their attributes as a critical factor of the success of a start-up.

2.2.1. Characteristics of an Entrepreneur

The term entrepreneur is frequently used to describe the founder of a new enterprise or someone who established an innovative enterprise when none existed before (Gartner, 1985). According to this definition, someone who inherits a business purchases an established company or oversees a turnaround as an employee is not an entrepreneur (Cunningham and Lischeron, 1991). Others limit the use of the term to the innovator's creative endeavours which concurs with the definition of Schumpeter's (1934) entrepreneur (Cunningham and Lischeron, 1991). Peterson (1985) refers to the process of identifying and exploiting a business opportunity as entrepreneurial.

Entrepreneurs vary from passionate, risk-taking individuals who are open to all experiences and willing to chase any business opportunity to those who are cautious and meticulous individuals who only take calculated risks (Kolb, 2015; Rupčić, 2019). Despite the fact that entrepreneurs are fundamental to the formation of new businesses, they are rarely explicitly taken into consideration in formal models of new venture formation (Jones *et al.*, 2021; Markman *et al.*, 2002). Erdélyi (2010) highlighted that in academic practice, new venture formation and small business management is often conflated under the term 'entrepreneurship,' while 'innovation' is frequently used as a synonym for 'entrepreneurship'. A similar ontological debate is reflected in the two classical entrepreneurship theories i.e., Schumpeter and Kirznerian. Schumpeter subtly recognized that an entrepreneur is an innovative individual. "Schumpeterian opportunities are innovative and break away from existing knowledge" (De Jong and Marsili, 2010 p.11), while Kirznerian argued that "opportunities are less innovative and replicate existing business or product

concepts” (Shane, 2003 p. 21). For the present research, participating nascent entrepreneurs fall into both categories. Delmar and Davidsson (2000) define nascent entrepreneurs as individuals attempting to start their own firm. It also refers to entrepreneurs who are still planning and gathering resources, as well as taking the necessary steps to establish their own venture (Hayek, 2012; Kim *et al.*, 2003).

Entrepreneurial activities, irrespective of the organisation in which they are conducted, are marked by excessive stress, volatility, uncertainty, and risk of failure. It is widely known that some entrepreneurial endeavours flourish and thrive, whereas others never reach the point of delivering any significant profit, leaving their founders disheartened and sometimes even bankrupt (Davidsson and Honig, 2003). The process of learning that occurs in entrepreneurial activities is considered one of the potentially defining elements between such outcomes. To put it another way, it's vital to research how learning takes place in entrepreneurial endeavours, what conditions help or impede it, who is participating, and what the desired outcomes are (Rupčić, 2019). Given the substantial financial risk that challenges the existence of both start-ups and their entrepreneurs, as well as the need to construct an ecosystem and a strong resource base (Brush, 2001), learning is unquestionably critical in that early and precarious period of entrepreneurial development (Rupčić, 2019).

2.2.2. Importance of Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship has long been recognised as a vital contributor to job creation, innovation, and long-term economic prosperity and development (Aparicio *et al.*, 2016; Intarakumnerd *et al.*, 2002; Langevang and Gough, 2012; Meyer and Meyer, 2017; Nelson, 1993). However, after the 1980s period of global economic stagnation and severe unemployment, a heightened focus was centred on the significance of entrepreneurship and small enterprises (Toma *et al.*, 2014). Since then, it has been evident that the contributors to economic growth are no longer primarily the giant organisations, but rather small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), which add significantly to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of various economies (Meyer and Jongh, 2018; Toma *et al.*, 2014).

Several studies have discovered substantial links between entrepreneurial activity and a country's economic progress (Almodovar-Gonzalez *et al.*, 2019; Fairlie and

Chatterji, 2013; García-Rodríguez *et al.*, 2017; Meyer and Jongh, 2018). Entrepreneurial activity has a positive impact on a country's GDP, exports, job creation, as well as its overall economic development. (Cumming *et al.*, 2014; Studdard *et al.*, 2013; Jones *et al.*, 2021). Governments around the world are promoting entrepreneurial graduates in order to build entrepreneurial economies that include competition, growth, innovation, and creativity (Peckernell *et al.*, 2011). Several government policies have been developed all around the world to encourage entrepreneurial activity and innovation (Blok *et al.*, 2017), such as providing entrepreneurial funding (Wang and Wang, 2012), implementing favourable regulations (Armour and Cumming, 2008), establishing business incubation programmes (Autio *et al.*, 2018; Mian *et al.*, 2016; NBIA, 2011; UKBI, 2013). Since the early 2000s, government sponsorship of entrepreneurship has become a popular policy instrument all over the world (Motoyama and Knowlton, 2016). The United Kingdom is committed to supporting graduates to become entrepreneurs and establish new businesses (Costa-David 2004; Jones *et al.*, 2014). For the past two decades, the UK government has been devoted to supporting graduate entrepreneurs to launch start-ups (Jones *et al.* 2014).

2.2.3. Start-ups

This study investigates entrepreneurs' experiences of initiating a start-up in a UBI. A discussion about incubators involves a discussion about start-ups, as incubation programs are meant to foster start-ups. A start-up goes through various stages of development in an incubator and simultaneously the learning and understanding of the entrepreneurs develop (Mattushek, 2020). Therefore, it is essential to discuss what a start-up is.

2.2.3.1. Defining Start-ups

Even though the term 'start-up' frequently appears in mainstream media, academic communities, and economic policies (Cockayne, 2019), it was observed in the literature that there is no universally accepted definition of a start-up. However, there are commonalities in each definition (Luger and Koo, 2005), such as 'innovative idea or enterprise', 'operating in the uncertain and volatile environment' and 'struggling for existence'. Below are some widely acknowledged definitions of start-ups.

Ries (2011) defines a start-up as a human organisation formed to develop a new product or service in the face of great uncertainty, which is similar to Hoffman and Radojevich-Kelley's (2012) definition. They define start-ups as organizations founded in an unpredictable and fraught environment with the goal of creating a new market opportunity. Salamzadeh and Kawamorita's (2015) definition of a start-up is consistent with both of the preceding definitions. Start-up companies, according to them, are businesses that are still in their infancy and are fighting for survival. These organisations are typically founded on promising ideas and grow to be successful.

Usually, the early-stage nascent ventures in the technology and innovation industry are referred to as 'start-ups'. Unlike small and medium enterprises, start-ups are not characterised by size but by their innovative nature (Cockayne, 2019; Stone, 2018). Gale and Brown (2013) observed that start-ups are nascent firms of inventive nature that are often operating in uncertain and unpredictable environments, such as with innovative technology or a novel business model. Start-ups are not SMEs and the policies and programmes designed to encourage innovative nascent ventures and future high-growth companies are likely to vary from policies designed to aid existing small and medium-sized businesses (Blake, 2019). Bone *et al.* (2017) adds to this that due to their innovative nature and novel business model, the support that start-ups demand is not the same as SMEs.

The distinction between a start-up and a small firm is analogous to the distinction between an entrepreneur and a businessman. An entrepreneur disrupts the market (Rabideau *et al.*, 2016; Wang and Chugh, 2014) and pursues a unique idea, whereas a businessman follows a predetermined route and pursues a non-innovative business idea. However, in the long run, entrepreneurs evolve into businessmen but always stay market leaders (Robehmen, 2013) because their pioneering approaches serve as a model for other businessmen. Furthermore, field research and review of the archival data of UBIs revealed that start-ups should have an element of technology (Cockayne, 2019) and innovativeness (Gale and Brown, 2013) in order to be classified as 'start-ups'.

Steve Blank, a Silicon Valley pioneer, defines start-ups into six types as presented in table 2.1:

Table 2-1: Start-up Types

Start-up Type	Description
Lifestyle Start-up	Entrepreneurs who live the life they want to live, work for no one but themselves, and pursue their passion are referred to as a lifestyle entrepreneur. The counterpart in Silicon Valley is a freelance developer or webmaster who thoroughly enjoys technology and works in coding and user interface design since it is a passion.
Small Business Start-up	Convenience stores, hair stylists, consultancy firms, electricians, etc. fall under this category. Small business entrepreneurship is not geared to expand.
Scalable Start-up	Silicon Valley entrepreneurs and venture capitalists seek to create scalable start-ups. Google, Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram are only a few of the most recent instances. From the beginning, the founding members were convinced that their idea could have a global impact.
Buyable Start-up	Over the last decade, start-ups that deliver web and mobile app solutions have been sold to big corporations. This concept is getting prominence. The goal of such start-ups is to be bought out by a larger corporation for a decent sum of money, rather than to establish a million-dollar company.
Large Company Start-up	Big corporations have restricted lifespans. These cycles have shortened during the past few years. Most companies expand by continuing to innovate and introducing new products that are variations of their main offerings. Customer preferences, digital breakthroughs, laws, competitive pressures, and other considerations can place stress on big corporations to design innovative products that are marketed to new customers in new marketplaces. Google, Apple and Android are some of the recent examples.
Social Start-up	Such start-ups are committed to making a difference and are enthusiastic in their efforts. Contrary to the scalable start-ups, their objective is to improve the world through a concept rather than profit. These start-ups can be non-profit, for-profit, or dual in nature.

Source: Blank (2011)

Incubation programmes support almost all start-up categories defined by Blank (2019). Most of the UBIs in the UK welcome different types and sectors of start-ups in the same cohort (Bone *et al.*, 2017). The sample in the present study contains

all start-up types except for the large company start-ups as those start-ups, probably due to their affiliation with big organisations, do not usually seek UBIs' support.

2.2.3.2 Different stages of start-ups

Sullivan (2000) suggest that Churchill's (1983) lifecycle model would be beneficial in trying to understand the development of entrepreneurs and their ventures since it would represent the sorts of problems businesses face as they progress. Small businesses, according to Churchill (1983), go through a life cycle during which the management demands change and, as a result, the type of assistance required change. Dee *et al.* (2015) identified the different development stages a start-up goes through. From an idea to a new venture, the start-up journey goes through the following phases.

Figure 2-1: Start-up journey

Source: Dee et al. (2015)

Pre Strat-up is the stage where an individual aspires and intends to be an entrepreneur and generates an idea (Dee *et al.*, 2015). This phase includes all activities that occur from when the entrepreneur first conceptualised the start-up to when the company is officially registered (LeBrasseur *et al.*, 2003). The following stage, the *start-up stage*, is where the idea is transformed into a product or service; however, the product is not marketed commercially at this stage (Dee *et al.*, 2015). At the subsequent phase, *early-stage venture*, product development has occurred, and the entrepreneur is in the process of commercial manufacturing (Dee *et al.*, 2015). At the final stage, *late-stage venture*, the start-up has stabilised its growth rate, demonstrated the viability and is most likely started to generate some profit (Dee *et al.*, 2015)

Entrepreneurs typically apply to incubators or accelerators when they have several needs, rather than just the need for training and advice or the need for funding (Isabelle, 2013). As a start-up has various stages, different incubators support

different stages of start-up development, for example, some incubators accept start-ups at the pre-start-up stage whereas others cater for late-stage ventures (Bone *et al.*, 2017).

For this study, the sample consists of entrepreneurs who joined the UBI at the pre-start-up or start-up stage. It is important to learn entrepreneurs' experience of business incubation and how it aids them during these critical stages, as well as what are the areas of improvement. A better understanding of their experiences would be beneficial in providing more efficient support in future.

2.2.3.3. Common challenges faced by start-ups

While innovative start-ups are lauded for their contributions to economic development (Fritsch, 2011; Klotz *et al.*, 2014), they are fraught with difficulties and significant risks of failure (Jayawarna *et al.*, 2011). These start-ups encounter varying challenges such as problems in identifying, capturing and incorporating required resources including technical expertise, enterprise skills and knowledge, financial and human capital (Colombelli *et al.*, 2016; Shepherd *et al.*, 2015; Symeonidou and Nicolaou, 2018) which can result in despondency and entrepreneurs doubting their abilities. Others include a lack of credibility with investors and resource providers, and limited access to social networks (Jones *et al.*, 2021).

Understanding the factors of start-up failure has long been a focus of interest of entrepreneurship researchers, particularly for tech start-ups, which pursue innovative ideas that can lead to failure or massive success (Cantamessa *et al.*, 2018). This body of literature is inexhaustibly extensive, classifying the causes of start-up failure into internal and external elements (Akter and Iqbal, 2020; Cantamessa *et al.*, 2018). Lack of funding, managerial abilities, industry knowledge, social capital, and network access are examples of key internal challenges, whereas primary external challenges include intense competition and a lack of product or service demand. Figure 2.2 presents the reasons for start-up failures:

Figure 2-2: Reasons for start-up failures

Source: Researcher

2.2.3.3.1 Internal challenges

Lack of funding has been highlighted by many studies as a key reason for start-up failure (Akter and Iqbal, 2020; Cantamessa *et al.*, 2018; CB Insights, 2015). This factor is usually related to one or more of the other reasons, such as a result of poor resource and investment management, or inadequate market research, etc. (Cantamessa *et al.*, 2018). Also, to establish a successful start-up, not only finance but also fund management is crucial (Battistella *et al.*, 2017). Furthermore, difficulty in obtaining funding because of a lack of credibility in the eyes of investors is linked to this factor (Yang and Aldrich, 2017).

In addition, founders of tech start-ups generally have hard skills and highly technical backgrounds but lack cross-domain and business experience. This results in a well-developed product or service, however, a lack of a business plan and business development (Cantamessa *et al.*, 2018). The highly technical personnel risk a lack of business development and strategic planning, which can result in a lack of a commercial viewpoint, which involves researching how to grow customers, sales, and profits, making the firm more profitable and self-sustaining. Also, in most cases,

a start-up is a volatile workplace. As a result, rules, roles, and duties must be adequately organised and given to all team members in order to efficiently manage all activities (Cantamessa *et al.*, 2018).

Furthermore, the decision-making of nascent entrepreneurs can be hampered due to a lack of industry awareness on recognising and capitalising on potential possibilities (Alvarez and Barney, 2010). Inadequate industry knowledge and practical experience can result in a lack of marketing and sales initiatives, and ineffective business strategy (Akter and Iqbal, 2020). Lack of technical skills can also lead to the collapse of a start-up when entrepreneurs are forced to outsource costly engineers or product developers due to their insufficient technical competencies (Eisenmann, 2021).

Another prominent reason for start-up failure is a lack of human capital. Many firms fail when their founders do not have access to the right stakeholders and connections. The dearth of such human capital aspects is likely to have a negative impact on the creation and development of a new venture (Grimaldi *et al.*, 2013; Van Gelderen *et al.*, 2006). According to Eisenmann (2021), even when a competent entrepreneur leads a new start-up, other stakeholders' input is critical. Personnel, strategic associates, and investors, among others, all could contribute to the failure or success of an enterprise. A successful start-up does not merely require a phenomenal founder; other stakeholders such as experienced advisers, competent personnel in the founding team can offset the inadequacies of the entrepreneur and can offer valuable advice and industry contacts (Eisenmann, 2021).

Lastly, the establishment of commercial ties has been identified as a critical aspect in the success of a start-up (Eftekhari and Bogers, 2015). Networks are crucial for a small firm's survival and growth because they provide access to useful information, guidance, and influence, and also resources owned by others (Rothschild and Darr, 2005). The absence of such useful networks can cause a start-up to fail (Battistella *et al.*, 2017). As the concept of entrepreneurial networks for the success of start-ups has significantly emerged over time, entrepreneurs are no longer considered as lone heroes, but as team players who create ideas and carry out their operations while immersed in social and professional surroundings (Bhansing *et al.*, 2018).

2.2.3.3.2 External challenges

In addition to internal issues, external variables such as intense competition and insufficient product demand, among others, can contribute to a start-up's demise. Other external influences, such as unstable political situations or unfavourable government policies (Pompa, 2013), are also existent but are less relevant in the context of developed countries. Starting a new firm entails developing a unique product or service, and even attempting to develop a market breakthrough in an environment fraught with uncertainty and intense competition (Trimi and Berbegal-Mirabent, 2012). This highly competitive environment can also be a cause of start-up failure, as it can be challenging for new start-ups to invade the market (Battistella *et al.*, 2017; Lukason and Hoffman, 2015). Similarly, a lack of demand for the product or service in the market can also have a detrimental effect on the venture's survival and growth. This start-up failure factor is related to incorrect product placement, market maturity, or positioning in a specialised market, among other things (Cantamessa *et al.*, 2018). All of these aspects may determine the reach of only a tiny proportion of clients, which is insufficient for the firm's long-term viability (Battistella *et al.*, 2017; Schilling and Shankar, 2019). Before putting a product or service into the market, it is critical to undertake preliminary research to validate demand, as premature launches are also common among entrepreneurs who lack technical knowledge (Eisenmann, 2021). They keep hearing how important it is to have a quality product; hence they recruit expensive developers at a very early stage. Consequently, amid the stress to keep such high-priced experts occupied, they hasten their product or service into premature development (Eisenmann, 2021).

Research shows a high ratio of unsuccessful start-ups (Aerts *et al.*, 2007; Cantamessa *et al.*, 2018; Diakanastasi *et al.*, 2018). More than 60% of high-tech start-ups fail within six years (Santarelli and Vivarelli, 2007). However, addressing the challenges entrepreneurs endure in establishing start-ups can result in significant public and private benefits, including achieving entrepreneurial targets, creating employment opportunities, and contributing to economic development (Dee *et al.*, 2015). While some believe that uncertainty and high failure rates are endemic in entrepreneurship and innovation, and cannot be completely avoided, others disagree (Acs *et al.*, 2016). In fact, governments and policy makers all over the world have been introducing systems and mechanisms to promote entrepreneurship and

innovation (Jones et al, 2021; Skawińska and Zalewski, 2020).

Since the process of setting up a successful and sustainable start-up is fraught with uncertainty and volatility (Colombelli *et al.*, 2016; Diakanastasi *et al.*, 2018; Morris *et al.*, 2012; Symeonidou and Nicolaou, 2018), entrepreneurs are required to develop entrepreneurial skills and competencies such as recognising and exploiting opportunities by leveraging available resources and social networks (Morris *et al.*, 2013). Entrepreneurship education and training programmes (Jones and Matlay, 2011; Balan and Metcalfe, 2012), as well as business incubation programmes, are believed to help participants develop entrepreneurial skills (Jones *et al.*, 2014; Mian *et al.*, 2016; Robinson *et al.*, 2016).

2.2.3.4 Critical Success Factors of Start-ups

Entrepreneurs are viewed as the leaders and key participants in the development of robust and successful start-up communities, as well as in the maintenance of the ecosystem's stability (Feld, 2012; Stam, 2015). Several researchers have highlighted leadership abilities as critical to the success of a start-up (Felix *et al.*, 2019; Harrison *et al.*, 2018; van Hemmen *et al.*, 2013). According to studies, entrepreneurship and leadership are inextricably linked, and in order to identify and capitalise on opportunities, and hence establish a successful venture, entrepreneurs must be endowed with leadership qualities (Felix *et al.*, 2019). In addition to entrepreneurs' strong leadership qualities, the role of effective intermediaries in connecting entrepreneurs to the larger ecosystem of start-up assistance is critical for their success (Felix *et al.*, 2019). Mentors, successful business tycoons, and well-known retired professionals ready to give back to the community could play the role of intermediaries. According to studies, intermediaries can play a significant part in the success of start-ups because they can connect nascent entrepreneurs to a larger support system that is critical to their survival (Agogué *et al.*, 2013; Ngongoni *et al.*, 2017). A strong network of investors, mentors, corporations and other like-minded entrepreneurs is vital for the success of start-ups (Albourini *et al.*, 2020).

Studies suggest that the success of start-ups is largely dependent on access to social capital as experienced and competent stakeholders such as team members, personnel and advisors can all contribute to a venture's success (Eisenmann, 2021; Grimaldi *et*

al., 2013; Van Gelderen *et al.*, 2006). Additionally, entrepreneurs' active involvement with the start-up community in order to form valuable business relations is essential for the success of their start-ups (Battistella *et al.*, 2017; Eftekhari and Bogers, 2015), as networks are essential for start-up survival and growth because start-ups can access useful information, guidance, and critical resources (Rothschild and Darr, 2005).

The success of a start-up is also largely determined by the state's assistance, as favourable government policies are essential for fostering and promoting entrepreneurship (Feld, 2012; Skawińska and Zalewski, 2020). Several studies indicate a positive impact of government support on the development of entrepreneurial culture (Akinyemi and Adejumo, 2018; Nguyen *et al.*, 2015). In addition, active involvement and support of large organisations in the region can also play a substantial role in the promotion of entrepreneurial communities (Feld, 2012).

This can lead to the provision of adequate funding for the start-ups. Lack of finance is one of the leading causes of start-up failure, therefore access to funding and capital is critical for survival (Akter and Iqbal, 2020; Cantamessa *et al.*, 2018; Feld, 2012).

Literature suggests that the aforementioned factors can determine the successful formation and development of start-ups. Due to the substantial role start-ups play in the economy, governments and policy makers all over the world are promoting entrepreneurship and innovation (Audretsch *et al.*, 2020; Jones *et al.*, 2021; Skawińska and Zalewski, 2020) by implementing entrepreneurship education and training programs (Jones and Matlay, 2011; Balan and Metcalfe, 2012), as well as business incubation programmes, that can enhance start-up survival rates (Jones *et al.*, 2014; Mian *et al.*, 2016; Robinson *et al.*, 2016). The figure below summarises the findings of the literature:

Figure 2-3: Critical Success Factors of Start-ups

Source: Researcher

As this research seeks to explore how entrepreneurs in UBI learn from their mentors and peers, the next section of this chapter now reviews the existing literature on entrepreneurial learning.

2.3. Entrepreneurial Learning

As entrepreneurship is action-oriented (McMullen and Shepherd 2006), the education, training and support provided by business incubators align with the concept of experiential learning (Breuer and Mahdjour, 2012; Bergmann and Sams, 2014), and provide tenant entrepreneurs with the space and environment to learn from experience (Kassean *et al.*, 2015; Piperopoulos and Dimov, 2015).

According to Erdélyi (2010), entrepreneurial learning is significant as is an observable phenomenon that entrepreneurs participate in or are linked with, and it is a central policy target in advanced Western countries that is accomplished through sponsored programmes aimed at entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurial activities,

irrespective of the organisation in which they are conducted, are marked by excessive stress, volatility, uncertainty, and risk of failure. It is widely known that some entrepreneurial endeavours flourish and thrive, whereas others never reach the point of delivering any significant profit, leaving their founders disheartened and sometimes even bankrupt (Davidsson and Honig, 2003; Spiegel *et al.*, 2016). The process of learning that occurs in entrepreneurial activities is considered one of the potentially defining elements between such outcomes (Rupčić, 2019). To put it another way, it's vital to research how learning takes place in entrepreneurial endeavours, what conditions help or impede it, who is participating, and what the desired outcomes are. Given the substantial financial risk that challenges the existence of both start-ups and their entrepreneurs, as well as the need to construct an ecosystem and a strong resource base (Brush, 2001), learning is unquestionably critical in that early and precarious period of entrepreneurial development (Rupčić, 2019).

2.3.1. Key Developments in Entrepreneurial Learning Literature

Entrepreneurship literature has mainly attempted to investigate the qualities of seasoned entrepreneurs or the attributes of their successful and rapidly developing start-up enterprises. However, since the 1990s, when the attention turned to a more process-oriented perspective of entrepreneurship, more attention has been focused on understanding entrepreneurship as a continual learning process (Politis, 2008). This approach recognises entrepreneurship as a skill that develops over time in the professional lives of ambitious people (Minniti and Bygrave, 2001; Politis, 2005). The transition has underlined the need for past professional experience for improving an entrepreneur's capacity to manage the entrepreneurial process from opportunity identification through opportunity monetization among other things (Politis, 2008). Entrepreneurs gain specific abilities, interests, and attitudes as a result of their engagement in various start-ups, according to this viewpoint (Anderson and Ronteau, 2017; Westhead *et al.*, 2005).

According to Minniti and Bygrave (2001, p.7), "*entrepreneurship is a process of learning...*" Entrepreneurial learning is also a theoretical idea that has developed from the intersection of entrepreneurship studies and the literature on organisational learning and knowledge (Harrison and Leitch 2005). According to Wang and Chugh

(2014), understanding of the entrepreneurial process hinges on how and when entrepreneurs learn. Entrepreneurial learning research has gain momentum over the past few years, and it exhibits a number of aspects. Since entrepreneurial learning is widely poised at the intersection of entrepreneurship and organisational learning, previous research has drawn on a variety of theoretical perspectives, such as experiential learning (Cope, 2003; Minniti and Bygrave 2001), organisational learning (Covin *et al.* 2006; Wang, 2008), social cognitive theory (i.e., Erikson 2003) etc., using a variety of methodologies to investigate various entrepreneurial environments. Entrepreneurial learning is commonly described as learning within the entrepreneurial process (Politis 2005; Ravasi and Turati 2005), however, its definitions range from “venture learning” (Berglund *et al.* 2007, p.178), “learning to recognise and act on opportunities”, as well as socially interacting to establish, “organise, and manage ventures” (Rae 2005, p.324), to “the variety of experiential and cognitive processes used to acquire, retain and use entrepreneurial knowledge” (Young and Sexton, 2003, p.156).

While the concept of entrepreneurial learning as a whole is considered relatively new (dating back to Deakins and Freel's 1998 study), the use of intellectual analogies like learning and knowledge to envision entrepreneurship and innovation dates back to Joseph Schumpeter's (1934) classic book, 'The Theory of Economic Development'. Much of the research influenced by Schumpeter has included an indirect or direct connection between entrepreneurship and learning (Erdélyi, 2010). Some researchers addressed the spread of innovation (Attewell 1992; Van De Ven and Polley, 1992), and the significance of networks in the entrepreneurial process as some kind of learning (Birley 1985; Dubini and Aldrich, 1991; Larson, 1991), however, a branch of study dedicated to the phenomenon of entrepreneurial learning and the application of entrepreneurial learning as a concept did not arise until the late 1990s. The study by Deakins and Freel (1998) seems to be the first to identify entrepreneurial learning as a distinct feature of the entrepreneurial process in the domain of SME (Erdélyi, 2010). The phenomenon started to get researchers attention afterwards.

Given its brief history, the literature on entrepreneurial learning contains a wide range of theoretical perspectives concentrating on a broad range of concepts. These perspectives can be classified into two main categories: (i) entrepreneurs' personal

or individual learning experiences and cognitive capacities, and (ii) entrepreneurial learning as a collaborative process (Erdélyi, 2010). In simple words, entrepreneurial learning may be thought of as either an individual or a shared activity.

The first approach regards entrepreneurship as a behaviour that can be developed with time and experience (Deakins and Freel 1998; Rae 2006). Kolb's (1984) experiential learning theory falls in the first category, along with Rae and Carswell 2001; Taylor and Thorpe 2004; Corbett 2005; Politis 2005; and Holcomb *et al.* 2009, which explain how entrepreneurs grow by learning from experience. Entrepreneurial learning is also thought to take place at a specific point in a business owner's or manager's professional life, for instance when one transition from a 'potential entrepreneur' to a 'nascent entrepreneur' (Rae 2000; Erikson 2003), or when one gathers enough expertise and funds to set up a business (Rae, 2005). Among this first category, there is a subset that characterises entrepreneurial learning as a process of opportunity identification and focuses on the entrepreneur's intellectual capabilities for finding and deciding on entrepreneurial prospects. Notwithstanding these attempts to frame the cognitive act of opportunity exploration, the emphasis is primarily on the cognition of the individual entrepreneur. Another subset closely related to this literature is 'executive education and management training' (Leitch and Harrison, 1999), and it focuses on teaching entrepreneurship (Wee 2004; Matlay 2006, 2007; Pittaway and Cope, 2007a, 2007b; Fisher, *et al.*, 2008; Rae, 2007; Gompers, *et al.* 2005; Lens, *et al.*, 2008. In short, as suggested by Erdélyi (2010) this subset is concerned with the supply side of entrepreneurial learning.

The collective approach seeks to characterise entrepreneurial learning as a social activity and is thus more concerned with the organization's setting than with the entrepreneur's personality and cognition. The different organisational entities mentioned in the literature include SMEs, inter-organizational interactions within a network of companies, and national innovation systems (Erdélyi, 2010; Man, 2007). The investigation of collective learning in the SME sector began with the implementation of the idea of organisational learning as an adjustment to the process of entrepreneurship (Levitt and March 1988). Simultaneously, attempts were made to apply the conceptions of the 'learning organisation' (Gibb, 1997) and 'learning company' (Pedler *et al.*, 1991) within the SME context (Choueke and Armstrong,

1998; Gray and Gonsalves, 2002; Devins *et al.*, 2002), in order to achieve the prescriptive ideal of an entrepreneurial learning organisation that promotes the learning of all its members and continuously evolves (Pedler, *et al.*, 1991). Although, the transition in the unit of study from the individual entrepreneur to the organisation widened the extent of the notion of entrepreneurial learning; however, similar to the preceding individualist perspectives, this part of the literature is still more focused on the internal processes of learning than the external factors of learning. The only difference in this approach is that it has substituted the individual entrepreneur's learning with the organisation or collective learning, but the attention still revolves around the dynamics of internal learning (Erdélyi, 2010).

Pfeffer and Salancik (1978, cited in Erdélyi, 2010) assert that there are good historical and rational reasons for the prevalence of an internal point of view in organisational research, however, this is a prejudice that must be controlled against the fact that organisations are innately reliant on external resources for their ongoing survival. Erdélyi (2010) agree with the observation of Pfeffer and Salancik (1978) that most of the studies have focused on resource utilisation while overlooking the significant issue of resource acquisition. The idea of networks of external stakeholders developed only when the study focus shifted from the internal factors of learning to the external elements and sources. In his research of university-facilitated learning groups of new ventures, Tell (2008) expands on the concept of the network even more clearly. He discovered that entrepreneurs utilised their learning network as a 'reflection instrument' (Argyris and Schön 1978).

To reduce disparities between the concepts of individual cognition and the shared dimension of organisation, Lee and Jones (2008) utilised Nahapiet and Ghoshal's (1998) concept of cognitive social capital. In their study, the communications inside an entrepreneurial network are defined as a conversation between players, focused on their common language, codes, and discourses, which act as information distribution mediums. In a similar attempt, De Carolis and Saporito (2006) aim to relate the cognitive components of opportunity exploration with the network properties of social capital even more clearly. According to Erdélyi (2010), these initiatives leave little scope for nonhuman resources to be considered. Building on

Crossan et al's (1999) 4I framework of organisational learning (organisational learning as a process of Intuiting, Interpreting, Integrating and Institutionalising knowledge), Jones and Macpherson's (2006) add a fifth "I" (5I model) to their concept of organizational learning, the Inter-organizational dimension, which aligns them with the network viewpoint. They make the distinction between entrepreneurial learning, which occurs on an individual basis, and organisational learning, which is conducted in a collective or social setting. Most importantly, they also take into account the issue of obtaining resources from external entities. However, the individual stays the originator and key cause of learning in the 5I model, just like the 4I model, thus Jones and Macpherson's attempt is closer to individualist perspectives than the more diverse views of networks described before (Erdélyi, 2010). Another distinct dimension of entrepreneurial learning literature is entrepreneurship assumed to be a national movement. Matlay and Mitra (2002) regarded entrepreneurship as a primary source of national competitiveness and an encompassing phenomenon characterised by learning, knowledge, and innovation, all of which emerge from the connection and interplay among industry, government, and the educational system.

From the above discussion of key developments in the entrepreneurial learning literature, two key dimensions of learning emerge: (i) individual learning, and (ii) collective learning. The individualistic approach can be regarded as an experiential or cognitive process (Erdélyi, 2010). The collectivist approach, on the other hand, views entrepreneurial learning as being spread across or generated by a variety of actors of different scales, ranging from a small business through local networks to national innovation systems (Man, 2007). Both entrepreneurial learning approaches are discussed in section 2.3.3.

2.3.2 Significance of Entrepreneurial Learning

Entrepreneurial learning is significant as is an observable phenomenon that entrepreneurs participate in or are linked with, and it is a central policy target in advanced Western countries that is accomplished through sponsored programmes aimed at entrepreneurs (Erdélyi, 2010; Man, 2007; Rae and Carswell, 2000). Sullivan (2000) stresses the need of understanding the entrepreneurial learning

process. Williams (1998), Senge (1990) and Argyris (1992) also agree that for businesses to prosper in today's dynamic, competitive, and fast-paced environment, they must have a strong learning capability. Overall, the ability to learn on a continual basis is currently seen as a critical factor in determining competitive success, therefore, it is necessary to have a better grasp of the idea in both practical and theoretical ways in order to remark on how it may best be supported in the context of SMEs (Sullivan, 2000). It might be claimed, for example, that most of what is learned within the context of entrepreneurship and venture creation is done via experience.

Deakins (1996, cited in Sullivan 2000, p.161) highlights that "We do not understand how entrepreneurs learn, yet it is accepted that there is a learning experience from merely establishing a new enterprise. The learning process that is involved in business and enterprise development is poorly understood, yet programmes have been devised and interventions are made in business development.... There is now a need for re-focusing research away from the emphasis on picking successful entrepreneurs or picking winners, to identify key issues in the learning and developmental processes of entrepreneurship".

Effective learning is widely acknowledged as critical to entrepreneurship success (Cope, 2005a; Deakins, O'Neill and Mileham, 2000; Man, 2007; Rae and Carswell, 2000). The skills, information, and competencies necessary at different phases of venture development can be obtained via effective learning and then implemented. As a result, learning is seen as crucial to the entrepreneurial growth process (Deakins, *et al.*, 2000). Most of the entrepreneurial learning takes place in the workplace, where entrepreneurs learn through their decisions, errors, experiences, and from their network of peers (Man, 2007). Entrepreneurs' capacity to learn from specific experiences along the development phase will have an impact on how prosperous their businesses become (Deakins and Freel, 1998; Olugbola, 2017). The structure of enterprise education and entrepreneurship support and training programmes requires a thorough grasp of entrepreneurial learning (Down, 1999; Man, 2007; Rae and Carswell, 2000). According to Down (1999), if support policies and training are to be more successful, more comprehensive knowledge of the 'situated learning process' is required. Therefore, understanding entrepreneurial learning in the

business incubation context will help to better surmise the process and establish more comprehensive metrics of incubator performance.

Some critics believe that further study in the subject of entrepreneurial learning is required as there is limited knowledge about the learning process (MattuPolitis, 2005; Rae and Carswell, 2001; Ravasi et al, 2004; Yousafzai *et al.*, 2021), and nascent entrepreneur's learning styles, requirements, and techniques (Honig 2001; Minniti and Bygave, 2001). In this discipline, similar issues have mostly gone unaddressed (Politis, 2005). Researchers have repeatedly shown that there is a dearth of knowledge as to why and how certain entrepreneurs are able to discover and explore more prospects compared to others (Cope 2005a; Minniti and Bygave 2001; Ozgen and Baron, 2007). Previous approaches to understanding the role of learning in entrepreneurship research have been criticised for taking a rather rigid view of the entrepreneurial learning process, where the *process* simply refers to the logic of describing the causal association between entrepreneurs' past experiences and the efficiency of the succeeding endeavour. As a result, less emphasis is paid to how entrepreneurs gain entrepreneurial knowledge via their experiences, which allows them to detect and act on entrepreneurial prospects as well as the structure and manage new enterprises. The issue of how entrepreneurs gain entrepreneurial knowledge that may have an implicit beneficial influence on venture performance remains largely unexplored in the literature (Politis, 2005).

Entrepreneurial learning, according to Donohoe and Wyer (2005), plays a critical part in the evolution of entrepreneurs from the start-up phase to late-stage venture. Entrepreneurial activities are fraught with danger and uncertainty, especially the start-up phase. Given the substantial financial risk that challenges the existence of both start-ups and their entrepreneurs, as well as the need to construct an ecosystem and a strong resource base (Brush, 2001), learning is unquestionably critical in that early and precarious period of entrepreneurial development (Rupčić, 2019).

According to Dimov (2007), instead of being the work of one individual, entrepreneurial possibilities are part of a social learning process in which new information arises on a regular basis to address the ambiguity that comes with each step of opportunity creation. Opportunities may be thought of as a steady flow of ideas that are formed and influenced by communication, innovative perspectives,

and activities at every step. Dimov's (2007) viewpoint provides a unique approach to entrepreneurship research. According to this perspective, learning is integrated with the venture creation process. A similar view is shared by Corbett (2005) that entrepreneurs must learn throughout their journey and discover new possibilities to be successful. Furthermore, according to Pittaway and Cope (2007), entrepreneurial learning emerges via experience and exploration, as well as acting and reflecting. All of these researchers examine entrepreneurship from the perspective of learning.

Effective learning is widely acknowledged by several researchers as critical to entrepreneurship success (Cope, 2005a; Corbett, 2005; Deakins, O'Neill and Mileham, 2000; Erikson, 2003; Minniti and Bygrave, 2001; Politis, 2005; Rae and Carswell, 2000). However, these studies have primarily focused on what influences entrepreneurial learning and how it happens and did not establish a clearer conceptual link between efficient learning and individual entrepreneur performance. To address this issue, Man (2007) provided an alternate conception of entrepreneurial learning through the competency approach that view entrepreneurial learning as a 'competency'. In the following sections three perspectives of entrepreneurial learning identified by Man (2007) are discussed:

According to Reuber and Fischer (1993 cited in Song and Zhang 2017, p. 779), "only if we truly understand the "mechanisms" of entrepreneurial learning can we explain the success of entrepreneurs." Therefore, it is essential to comprehend the process of entrepreneurial learning from the standpoint of different learning approaches.

2.3.3. Processes of entrepreneurial learning

2.3.3.1. Experiential Learning

Experiential learning is "the process whereby knowledge is created through the transformation of experience" (Kolb, 1984, p. 38). Knowledge is built through the comprehending or interpretation of raw experience, as well as the modification of that experience. The concept of experiential learning brings entrepreneurial learning into the context. Kolb (1984) proposed a comprehensive integrative view on learning based on experiential learning theory, which blends experience, perspective, cognition, and behaviour. Experiential learning theory as the name

suggests emphasises the significance of experience in the learning process.

Several studies highlight that most of the learning that occurs in an entrepreneurial setting is experiential (Cope, 2003; Essig and Guevara, 2016; Minniti and Bygrave, 2001; Politis, 2005; Sullivan, 2000). This indicates that in order to enhance the understanding of entrepreneurial learning, the process by which entrepreneurs learn by doing and experiencing must be addressed.

Learning, according to experiential learning conception, is a system in which ideas are drawn from and constantly transformed by the experience, and different people approach the experience using various learning approaches. Some scholars concentrate on the application of these learning strategies to the entrepreneur's experience (outside the context of business incubation) (Bosma, Meijaard and Popta, 2002; Corbett, 2005; Ulrich and Cole, 1987; Ulrich, 2001), most of the studies identify that experience is the primary factor in entrepreneurial learning (Cope, 2003; Essig and Guevara, 2016; Man, 2007; Politis, 2005). Consequently, a range of learning experiences for entrepreneurs has been recognized, including their formative years, employment, past enterprises, official and unofficial engagements, mentors or idols, and school relationships (Rae and Carswell, 2001). Furthermore, it has been recognised that learning from experience entails more than merely repeating what has worked in the past for oneself and others while avoiding what has not (Man, 2007). For instance, entrepreneurial learning should be viewed as a process of creating the meaning of experience, according to Rae and Carswell (2001). In short, according to the experiential viewpoint, an entrepreneur develops required information, capabilities, and competencies through 'learning by doing' and 'learning via experience' (Man, 2007).

2.3.3.2 Cognitive–affective Learning

This viewpoint encompasses a variety of initiatives to simplify the entrepreneurial learning process whilst concentrating on various cognitive aspects that influence learning (Man, 2007). Learning, in this view, can be viewed as mental labour in the intake and organisation of knowledge. Young and Sexton (1997) used Bandura's (1986) social cognition theory to approach entrepreneurial learning as a cognitive process of obtaining, retaining, and applying entrepreneurial knowledge in long

memory. In contrast to the experiential perspective's emphasis on the entrepreneurial experience as the major factor influencing entrepreneurial learning, the cognitive-affective perspective has identified a broader range of behavioural, motivational, and personality factors, including self-worth, self-assurance, desire to accomplish and perseverance, as playing a key part in encouraging entrepreneurial learning (Rae and Carswell, 2001). These elements can also have an impact on the learning process (Man, 2007), and it can be seen in Cope and Watts' (2000) study. Cope and Watts' (2000) research consists of a series of longitudinal case studies of six entrepreneurs and their enterprises, reflecting a wide range of age, background, previous experiences, industry, and business age. The function of crucial situations in the learning process, as well as the articulation of reflection and its influence, were given special attention, and even though the nature of the experiential learning is experiential, the cognitive component seems to play a vital part (Man, 2007).

Some researchers, on the other hand, have attempted to explore the learning process's fundamental mechanism. According to Minniti and Bygrave (2001), the association between knowledge acquisition and decision making is recursive, consequence-based, and influenced by the entrepreneur's level of confidence in past deeds. They suggest that entrepreneurs only replicate the decisions that seem to be favourable and reject the ones that turned out unsuccessful in the past. This aligns with Ravasi and Turati's (2005) conceptual framework, wherein entrepreneurial learning is viewed as a self-augmenting activity. The decision-making process is also strongly linked to entrepreneurial learning. Based on the cognitive-affective approach presented above, it can be argued that entrepreneurial learning is a complicated process including a broad mix of cognitive, personality, emotional, and behavioural components and that it is a continuous process, as suggested by Man (2007).

2.3.3.3. Situated Learning

According to situated learning theory, learning occurs in social circumstances and through communication (Sense, 2015), and perspective learning is “an integral and inseparable aspect of social practice” (Lave and Wenger's, 1991 p. 31). Learning is therefore embedded in professional communities, in which actors comprise one another and unanimously grow the practice in which they are participating (Lave and Wenger, 1991). Professional communities or communities of practice are

communities of people who have a common focus, a set of challenges, or an enthusiasm for a subject, and who socialise on a regular basis to expand their knowledge and competence in that field (Wenger *et al.*, 2002, quoted in Theodorakopoulos *et al.*, 2013, p.3). This approach suggests that learning is integrated with daily routines and actions. It affirms the idea that learning is both a collective and individual activity (Hamilton, 2011). Since social practices are constantly evolving, knowledge is regarded as contextual, hence learning is inextricably linked to social engagement in situated learning (Eslahchi and Osman, 2021). Several studies have emphasised the examination of entrepreneurial learning in a social setting (Cope, 2005a, b; Eslahchi and Osman, 2021; Jones *et al.*, 2021; Hamilton, 2011; Politis *et al.*, 2019; Taylor and Thorpe, 2004).

As part of experiential learning, situated learning theory highlights the impact of the surroundings on an entrepreneur's ways of knowing and learning. Learning, in this perspective, is grounded in the circumstances in which the experience occurs rather than in the individual (DiFrancesco, 2011). Corbett (2005) asserts that experiential learning theory entails both cognitive and situated learning, with situated learning involving group activities and the reinforcement of behaviours through interaction with others. Individuals transform their experiences into new knowledge by applying cognitive qualities. According to Eslahchi and Osman (2021), the process of experiential learning is deeply ingrained in the situated learning. This indicates that if entrepreneurs do not engage in communities of practice, they will be unable to gather experience and develop. Learning and development are regarded as an inherently social phenomenon in which implicit knowledge plays a key role, according to situated learning approach (Theodorakopoulos *et al.*, 2013). In their study, Theodorakopoulos *et al.* (2013) utilise situated learning theory as the learning theory that underpins human resource development. Human resource development initiatives, according to Kerno and Mace (2010), emerge across diverse networks of practice, in which individuals involve in various capacities and have dynamic interactions with one another. In terms of situated learning theory, what is essential here is to provide the environments that render learning meaningful and effective, rather than to generate the learning itself (Wenger, 1998). According to situated learning approach, three characteristics are crucial to develop a venture as a community and acquiring new skills relevant to that venture, namely “community

strength, healthy identities and boundary space quality”, where community strength represents the level of engagement and social activity of community members in the pursuit of a shared objective, healthy or empowering identities relate to a direct experience of having ties to community of practice that integrate members of the community, and the quality of the boundary spaces in which people of diverse communities of practice engage socially is critical for constructing knowledge and creating new views, as well as learning new skills and evolving as professionals (Theodorakopoulos et al., 2013, p.4). In a nutshell, situated learning scholars believe that learning occurs at the intersection of members of related communities of practice. A social learning system is made up of clusters of such associated communities of practice and the design components of situated learning theory as a perspective on organisational learning are broadened by examining them in a new context—that of entrepreneurship (Theodorakopoulos and Figueira, 2012).

2.3.3.4 Collaborative Learning

The third aspect of entrepreneurial learning highlighted by Man (2007) is an entrepreneur's networking activities. O'Reilly *et al.*, (1987 cited in Taylor and Thorpe, 2004) point out the limitations of research centred on isolated decision-makers, saying that a greater understanding can be reached when broader contextual factors are considered. Criticising the concept of isolated decision-makers and supporting a similar perspective, Granovetter, (1992) asserts that in a world where enterprises are immersed in networks of social, professional, and trade connections with other players, the premise that independent and isolated firms compete in an impartial market environment is becoming highly inappropriate (Granovetter, 1992).

Gibb (1997), building on Boissevain and Mitchell's (1973) network theory, suggests that firms can learn from their networks. Down (1999) supports this perspective and asserts that small and medium-sized enterprise (SME) owners learn a great deal through internal and external social networks and stakeholders. According to Boussouara and Deakins (1999), the social connections of the entrepreneur in the early phases of business development, are particularly important for success and subsequent development in the firm. Rae's (2005) notion of negotiated enterprise aligns with this networking concept with multiple entities within and around the

firm offering interactive learning opportunities. Taylor and Thorpe (2004) took a similar approach, viewing entrepreneurial learning as a collaborative process rather than a series of standalone decisions. The network centred approach of entrepreneurial learning is deemed significant by some other studies as well such as (Baron and Markman, 2000; Birley, 1985; Blundel and Smith, 2001; Collinson and Shaw, 2001; Devins *et al.*, 2002; Harding, 2004; Nohria and Eccles, 1992; Politis *et al.*, 2019; Shaw and Conway, 2000; Taylor and Thorpe, 2004).

According to the collaborative learning perspective, networking may teach an entrepreneur, not just technical and specialised information, but also dynamic, non-expert driven guidance and experience, that can bring continuing gains for the firm. This type of learning aids in the development of entrepreneurial experience (Man, 2007). In the context of business incubation, university incubators integrate the networked model that allows internal networking among the tenant entrepreneurs and as well as external networking opportunities (Bruneel *et al.*, 2012; Bøllingtoft and Ulhøi, 2005; Eveleens *et al.*, 2017; Hansen *et al.* 2000).

2.3.4. Facilitators of Entrepreneurial Learning

Entrepreneurial learning is a critical component of any firm's survival and success, and it is widely acknowledged that learning empowers firms to traverse competitive environments and overcome difficult and complicated situations (Cowdean *et al.*, 2019; Man, 2007; Olugbola, 2017). To facilitate entrepreneurial learning and promote entrepreneurship and innovation (Jayawarna *et al.*, 2011; Paolini *et al.*, 2019), universities have been playing a crucial role (McAdam and Marlow, 2008). Besides the traditional functions of development and transfer of knowledge through study and teaching, universities are more strongly involved in the marketing of knowledge (Sanz-Velasco and Saemundsson, 2008). Universities and governments have demonstrated dire interest in academic entrepreneurship and university spin-offs both in highly advanced and developing nations as a way of creating relations between academia and industry (Lerner, 2004). As a result, the term entrepreneurial university was emerged to represent institutions that are dedicated to regional and national economic growth (Etzkowitz, 2003).

Robust dedication to enterprise education and the promotion of graduate entrepreneurs by offering business incubation programmes is becoming an

increasingly vital feature of entrepreneurial universities (McAdam and Marlow, 2008). Although universities' primary goal is to provide instruction, they can also make a significant contribution to local economies by doing research that leads to economically viable innovations and developments, as well as encouraging entrepreneurship and creativity (Chiesa and Piccaluga, 2000; Lerner, 2004). Universities are increasingly being recognised as essential tools for fostering local economic growth and encouraging graduates to engage in entrepreneurial endeavours (Peckernell *et al.*, 2011). University business incubators (UBIs) have been shown in studies to be valuable support systems for promoting the growth and development of promising and innovative start-ups (McAdam and McAdam, 2008; Mascarenhas *et al.*, 2019; Wonglimpiyarat, 2016). The focus on incubation programmes corresponded with a surge in curriculums aimed at encouraging students to pursue entrepreneurship (Herrmann *et al.*, 2008).

Several universities in the UK provide business incubation programmes to promote entrepreneurship by assisting recent graduates to initiate entrepreneurial paths (Voisey *et al.*, 2013). It is not easy for recent graduates to pursue entrepreneurial paths due to their lack of enterprise and industry experience and the burden of student loans, and not to mention their lack of credibility with investors and resource providers, and limited social networks (Jones *et al.*, 2021). However, incubators can assist in overcoming such disadvantages in a variety of ways (Jones *et al.*, 2021), such as connecting them with the wider entrepreneurial ecosystem (van Weele *et al.*, 2018) and providing them access to funding opportunities (McAdam *et al.*, 2016). Fresh graduates pursuing entrepreneurial paths most likely do not have any prior enterprise or industry experience, as well as a minimal social network and no credibility with investors and other related stakeholders. The goal of university business incubation programmes is to help these individuals by offering a variety of services and resources (Bruneel *et al.*, 2012), and an opportunity to enhance their learning by doing and also learning from other like-minded individuals (Jones *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, these programmes serve as mediators, connecting entrepreneurs with experienced members and useful connections in the ecosystem (Eveleens *et al.*, 2017; McAdam *et al.*, 2016; Van Weele *et al.*, 2018), such as seasoned mentors, business advisors, industry experts, successful entrepreneurs, and investors.

As this research investigates how entrepreneurs learn whilst participating in UBI, the next section of this thesis (Part II) now reviews literature related to business incubation.

Part II: Business Incubation

This part reviews the existing literature related to business incubators and incubation, the history, evolution, and development of the business incubation, and the impact of business incubation on the success of start-ups.

2.4. Business Incubators and Business Incubation

This section discusses business incubation and explains its concept, history, developmental stages and various forms. As mentioned earlier, the literature review adopted a traditional narrative approach (Hammersley, 2001). According to Jones and Gatrell (2014 p.257), as long as authors can demonstrate a genuine "contribution to knowledge", narrative reviews will always have a place. The descriptive nature of this section of the literature review is aimed at providing the reader with an overview of the notion of business incubation since the rest of the chapter will explore key literature related to it.

2.4.1. Introduction to Business Incubators

Business Incubators are business development and support mechanisms that provide nascent entrepreneurs assistance in setting up innovative start-ups (Allen and McCluskey 1991; Bøllingtoft and Ulhøi, 2005; OECD, 2010). Policymakers all over the world use BIs as instruments to promote budding entrepreneurial endeavours and business start-ups and thereby contribute to economic growth (Mian *et al.*, 2016). The main goal of a business incubator is to establish and develop innovative ventures and improve their chances of survival (Bruneel *et. al.*, 2012; Grimaldi and Grandi, 2005; Hackett and Dilts, 2004b; Harper-Anderson and Lewis, 2018) along with that, these support structures are also meant to foster local development and the overall entrepreneurial ecosystem by drawing together many stakeholders from both private and public sectors (OECD, 2019).

It was observed in the literature that there is no generally accepted definition of a business incubator. The suggested definitions place a strong emphasis on the aspect of physical space, but not on the integrated network of services and support which is a crucial aspect of BIs (Bruneel *et al.*, 2012; Ratinho *et al.* 2020). Provision of physical space and infrastructure is the key distinguishing feature of a business

incubator; however, it is just a small part of what incubation entails as the process of incubation within an incubator offers a lot more than just providing affordable office space and shared resources (Aernoudt, 2004; Wang *et al.*, 2008). These programmes provide tenant entrepreneurs a controlled environment (Autio *et al.*, 2018) and advanced infrastructure, enterprise services and training, and access to internal and external networking (Bergek and Norrman, 2008; Dee *et al.*, 2015). In addition, these programmes also promote entrepreneurial learning (McAdam *et al.*, 2006). BIs are part of a larger set of initiatives designed to promote and foster entrepreneurship (Autio *et al.*, 2018; Spigel, 2017; Mian, 1996). Allen and McCluskey (1991) suggest that business incubator is an umbrella term for start-up support organisations that offer shared physical space and shared resources to support nascent ventures.

Hackett and Dilts (2004b, p.57) define business incubators as:

“A business incubator is a shared office space facility that seeks to provide its incubatees with a strategic, value-adding intervention system (i.e., business incubation) of monitoring and business assistance. This system controls and links resources with the objective of facilitating the successful new venture development of the incubatees while simultaneously containing the cost of their potential failure.”

It is important to keep in mind the inclusiveness of the business incubator as it is more than just a coworking place, shared facilities, and policy document. It is nexus of people and organisations including the internal and external staff of the incubator, networks of contacts, local universities and individuals and corporations providing capital funding (Hackett and Dilts, 2004b).

24.1.1. Distinguishing Business Incubators and Business Accelerators

The distinctions between business incubators, incubation and accelerators tend to be a source of significant misunderstanding. Business incubators and accelerators both have different types of business models, but these terms are often wrongly used interchangeably (Fehder and Hochberg 2014; Cohen and Hochberg, 2014). For the sake of clarity, it is beneficial to the current study to grasp the differences between these terminologies.

Business Incubator is a physical facility that offers economical office premises and shared services and enterprise support to nascent start-ups. The primary goal of BIs is to improve start-up survival rates by providing nascent entrepreneurs with a range of services varying from the provision of office facilities and resources to more specialized services and access to technological and managerial expertise, support and guidance in strategic planning (Grimaldi and Grandi, 2003).

Business Accelerator, as defined by Cohen and Hochberg (2014), is “a fixed-term, cohort- based program, including mentorship and educational components, that culminates in a public pitch event or demo day” Incubators were the forerunners of accelerators and may have originated as the incubators evolved (Pauwels *et al.*, 2015). An accelerator is a programme, whereas an incubator is a facility. As a result, an accelerator can operate inside an incubator, and not vice versa (Stone, 2018).

Incubators and accelerators both have the same objective of assisting nascent start-ups in their early and vulnerable stages of growth. Hence both are part of the wider definition of ‘business incubation’ - which is the umbrella term for a range of support services provided by incubators, accelerators, angel investors, technology innovation centres, and other start-up support organisations (Dee *et al.* 2015).

Business incubation is a structural mechanism that aims to focus on cultivating an entrepreneurial ecosystem in a region; it is the process of assisting a start-up in order to maximise its chances of surviving and becoming an established business (European Commission, 2002; UKBI, 2013). This process is meant to equip the entrepreneurs with the necessary knowledge and provides a controlled environment to ensure their venture smoothly goes through the early stages of its formation, nevertheless, it is the entrepreneur’s ultimate responsibility to keep their venture afloat (Bruneel *et al.*, 2012). It aims to find a practical way to connect technology, funding, and technical expertise in order to utilise entrepreneurial creativity, promote the growth of small ventures, and thus stimulate technology utilisation (Autio *et al.*, 2018). Incubators fulfil the purpose of business incubation by providing physical space and infrastructure, business support and guidance, networking and funding opportunities to new ventures (Ayatse *et al.*, 2017).

It appears that the incubator literature has gotten muddled by this myriad of

terminology as business incubators have been labelled under a number of more or less interchangeable terms over the years, such as research park (Danilov, 1971; Kang, 2004), science park (Hansson, 2007; Squicciarini, 2009), network-incubator (Bøllingtoft and Ulhøi, 2005; Hansen *et al.*, 2000; McAdam and McAdam, 2006), etc. Despite this variation in incubator forms and terminologies, the majority of the scholars view business incubators as an entrepreneurial development mechanism aimed at economic growth and development, assuming that successful ventures would foster community cohesion, create employment opportunities, and increase creativity (Theodorakopoulos *et al.*, 2014).

2.4.2. History and Evolution of Business Incubators

The first incubator was founded in Batavia, New York in,1959 as the Batavia Industrial Center when Charles Mancuso, a local real estate developer purchased a vacant factory building and separated it into smaller offices to rent out to several small businesses and some of the tenant businesses sought business and capital generation advice (Adkins, 2002; Bruneel *et al.*, 2010). Subsequently, in 1964, University City Science Centre, the first research park and incubator was launched in Philadelphia in association with a partnership of 28 universities in the region (Mian *et al.*, 2021). From there the idea spread first in the US than to the rest of the world and within a few decades became an industry (Moraru and Rusei, 2012; Sanyal and Hisam, 2018). At first, there was a gradual increase in the number of incubators, but within a few decades, the concept of business incubators gained popularity and spread worldwide (EC, 2002). This time span is referred to by some scholars as to the first generation of incubators or the first wave of incubator growth, and the incubators were primarily seen as a tool to boost local economic development (Bøllingtoft and Ulhøi, 2005). These early BIs provided low-cost office space and shared services such as reception, administrative support, meeting spaces, conference rooms, and parking facilities to the tenant incubatees (Barrow, 2001; McAdam and McAdam, 2008).

During the 1980s, governments in Europe and the United States were faced with rising unemployment in some sectors such as cars and the mechanical industry (Reich, 1991 cited in Bruneel, *et. al.*, 2012). Incubators became a common tool for encouraging entrepreneurship and the creation of new innovative businesses (Lewis,

2001). As the new tech-intensive firms lack the industry experience required to survive in the market, apart from affordable office space and shared resources, these companies needed additional services and specialised resources (Bruneel *et al.*, 2012). Business incubators responded by incorporating knowledge-based services in their business model during this time span. Consequently, the second generation of BIs emerged and was far more than just a physical structure for nascent businesses (Smilor and Gill, 1986).

During the 1990s, the third generation of BIs appeared, with a focus on providing access to services through external networks (Hansen *et al.*, 2000; Lalkaka and Bishop, 1996). These networks provided tenant incubates access to potential buyers, vendors, technology providers, and venture capitalists (Hansen *et al.*, 2000) and the opportunity to network with other companies which gives the nascent businesses credibility in the marketplace (Aldrich and Fiol, 1994; McAdam and McAdam, 2008). The number of e-businesses and incubators erupted between 1998 and 2000, resulting in the dotcom bubble. When the dotcom bubble exploded, the massively overvalued internet-based firms, as well as a significant number of the incubators that followed it, plummeted. The new millennium marked the beginning of a new wave of incubator development when the incubators industry renewed itself. The number of incubators rapidly grew during that period, and the industry became more diverse (Bøllingtoft and Uihøi, 2005; Hackett and Dilts, 2004a).

Figure 2-4: The Evolution of Business Incubators

Source: Theodorakopoulos et al. (2014)

The business incubator model has been constantly evolving to address the ever-changing needs and specifications of the business world (Grimaldi and Grandi, 2003). Over the years, the concept of business incubation has grown to include more than just a physical space, with policymakers and scholars identifying it as an entity that supports and enhances the growth of tenant start-ups by providing business support services (BEIS, 2019; Carvalho and Galina, 2015; Ratinho *et al.*, 2013). Thousands of business incubation programmes with a diverse set of business models have been established and modified over the last six decades and are currently in operation all over the world (Klofsten *et al.*, 2020; Mian *et al.*, 2021).

Over the years the business model of incubators has evolved and each generation of BIs has introduced a new feature to their value proposition (Grimaldi and Grandi, 2005). For this study, the third generation of business incubators i.e., the network incubators are the focus is on university-based incubators. The network-based view of incubation received substantial attention in 2000 (Hansen *et al.*, 2000). Brunel *et al.* (2010) claim that networks provide opportunities for learning and skill development. Literature suggests that networked incubators not only provide office space and basic services to the tenant start-ups, but also acts as a platform for these

nascent start-ups to effectively and regularly network with like-minded entrepreneurs and internal and external business support agencies. Hence, it has the potential to provide a plethora of opportunities for entrepreneurs to learn and gain experience collectively (Bøllingtoft and Ulhøi, 2005; Hansen *et al.* 2000).

2.4.3. Classifications of Business Incubators

Business incubators can be classified into different types and there is little consensus in the literature on the incubator taxonomy as various categories of incubators have been established. Incubators are usually classified using in the literature depending on the kinds of businesses they assist, incubator features or model, and incubator's funding. University business incubators are the focus of attention of this study; however, different categories of BIs are discussed in this section. A more discerning classification of business incubators would be to categorise them into two basic types: for-profit -also called public incubators and, and not-for-profit- also known as private incubators (Becker and Gassman, 2006; Grimaldi and Grandi, 2005; Zedtwitz, 2003).

As the name suggests, profitability is the ultimate strategic goal of for-profit incubators, while the primary focus of non-profit incubators is public good by increasing new venture development, encouraging innovation, improving regional employment, and creating job opportunities etc. In spite of the fact that the strategic goals of a non-profit incubator, in the long run, are economic, its rewards are reaped by some external party e.g., parent organisation or sponsor (Zedtwitz, 2003). Most of the business incubators are non-profit (Robles, 2017). In general, BI is categorised into the five prevalent types, namely independent commercial incubators, regional business incubators, university incubators, company-internal incubators, and virtual incubators.

2.4.3.1. Independent Commercial Incubators

Profitability is the primary objective of independent commercial incubators, however, contributing to the regional and national economic development is never out of the scope (Zedtwitz, 2003). These types of incubators are usually corporate spin-outs as entrepreneurial boot camps or sometimes initiated by a group of independent entrepreneurs with the purpose to help other like-minded entrepreneurs.

Inner competencies, particular industry or technology and target market are the basis of the business model of this type of incubator (Grimaldi and Grandi, 2005).

24.3.2 Regional Business Incubators

As reported by Zedtwitz (2003), these types of incubators are formed and sponsored by local governments to accelerate innovation and new venture creation. They are developed to provide resources to entrepreneurs in the local community from diverse backgrounds. Therefore, the first and foremost goal of regional business incubators is local economic development by supporting local industry and creating job opportunities in the region, whereas profitability is the secondary objective. Substantial investment in a certain geographical region can indeed generate additional industry and ultimately create a regional innovation hub (Zedtwitz, 2001;2003). Silicon Valley is an excellent example in this regard. The fees for the services they provide, as well as funding from regional, national, and international initiatives, are the sources of funding for these incubators (Grimaldi and Grandi, 2005).

24.3.3 University Business Incubators

Technical and research-intensive universities are usually the breeding grounds of technological innovations and scientific breakthroughs (Mian, 1996). Especially, in the past few decades, due to the rising internal demand and economic agenda, more and more universities have started to provide workspace for students with entrepreneurial interests and competencies (Zedtwitz, 2003). Such university incubators usually stem from established science that are parks designed to foster engagement across academia and industry (Nicholls-Nixon and Valliere, 2020). Tenant start-ups are provided with mentorship, venture capital market, assistance with business strategies and networking opportunities. Such operations are mostly conducted in close cooperation with the regional technology transfer centre as the intellectual property typically is held by the university and requires to be licensed by the tenant start-up before commercial viability (Zedtwitz, 2003). The goal of university incubators is to attract, create and develop innovative high-tech ventures that eventually positively impact economic growth (Mian, 1996; Nicotra *et al.*, 2018).

24.3.4. *Company-internal Incubators*

For several years, the company-internal incubation of emerging technology has been a corporate R&D function. Companies shifted to the idea of incubation in the 1990s to address some of these issues (Zedtwitz, 2003). Company-internal incubators have the ability to maintain and collect projects that don't really integrate into the organization but are nevertheless appealing from a financial perspective (Becker and Gassmann, 2006; Zedtwitz, 2003). Brightstar at BT (British Telecom) is an example of a corporate-internal incubator and was founded in 2000 after the company realized that a number of technologies developed within the company were not fully utilised (Zedtwitz, 2003).

24.3.5. *Virtual Incubators*

As the name indicates, virtual incubators provide no actual workspace or office support, unlike conventional incubators. Instead of a physical workspace, they provide a virtual platform- web access to entrepreneurial teams, investors and mentors, as well as resources to help meet other entrepreneurial requirements (Grimaldi and Grandi, 2005; Lewis *et al.*, 2011). However, the positive impacts of community collaboration between like-minded entrepreneurs experienced by face-to-face networking and problem-solution sharing are not provided by this type of incubator (Zedtwitz, 2003). Nonetheless, virtual incubators are able to provide their incubatees with a wider support network, better balancing the supply and demand of management and technical expertise.

Ever since the establishment of the first business incubator most business incubators have been developed as publicly funded tools for the provision of job opportunities, economic development, and the corporatization of university technological innovations (Mian *et al.*, 2016; Campbell and Allen, 1987), or as privately funded organisations for the incubation of high-potential new projects (Zedtwitz, 2001; 2003).

24.4. Business incubation Process and Configuration

As a strategy for fostering innovation and economic growth (Al-Mubarak and Busler, 2011), business incubators establish an incubation process that is expected

to be able to add value to incubated firms with the purpose of enhancing their survival rates (Ayatse *et al.*, 2017; Albadvi and Saremi, 2006; Moreira *et al.* 2012). This value-adding is commonly referred to as the company incubation process (Ayatse *et al.*, 2017). Due to the varying regional features, goals, and demands of the incubated firms, the business incubation process differs considerably from incubator to incubator (Albadvi and Saremi, 2006). Most incubation models, according to Bergek and Norrman (2008), are restricted in scope, focusing largely on outcomes and overlooking the complex relationships between value-added functions and other incubator operations.

Campbell, Kendrick, and Samuelson (1985) are credited as being the first to establish a business incubation process model, and their model identifies four fundamental value-added services that business incubators may help incubatee entrepreneurs with. The value-added services begin with a requirements assessment that is applied to the business idea presented by the prospective entrepreneurs. After a successful assessment, the successful start-ups chosen for incubation are supervised. Incubatees also benefit from extra value-added benefits such as financial resources and access to specialist networks, as well as the possibility of venture financing (Ayatse *et al.*, 2017). The incubatees or tenant entrepreneurs eventually move on to become promising growth enterprises after completing the incubation phase. This model has been criticised by Hackett and Dilts (2004a) for neglecting the prospect of incubatee venture failure. The Campbell model is also restricted to private incubators exclusive, as it ignores potential entrepreneurs' talents, environmental constraints, and a lack of a selection criterion in the selection of prospective entrepreneurs (Ayatse *et al.*, 2017).

Smilor (1987b) builds on this model by prioritizing the external factors and incubator's stakeholders at the detriment of the incubator's internal operations (Hackett and Dilts, 2004b), and regards the incubator as a mechanism that provides tenant entrepreneurs with structure and credibility while also regulating a collection of supportive resources. With affiliations to the corporate industry, higher education institutions, government, and non-profit organisations, the incubator administers a platform of value-added services. According to Hackett and Dilts (2004b), Smilor's work is one of the most thorough attempts to identify and describe several aspects

of the incubation system. Commenting on this model, Ayatse *et al.* (2017) assert that both the internal and external support systems are established to attain successful ventures and contribute to economic prosperity ultimately.

Hackett and Dilts (2008, p.440) created a model of company incubation founded on the notion of a “black box”. That model focuses on the incubator’s internal process and how it connects with its surroundings. According to Hackett and Dilts’ (2008) model, business incubation is defined as the careful selection of entrepreneurs from a community of potential applicants who gain entry to the black box of incubation (Ayatse *et al.*, 2017; Bergek and Norrman, 2008).

Incubatee selection efficacy, supervision and extent of business support, and resource availability are the three methods in which incubatees get value-added services, before finally leaving the incubator as a successful or unsuccessful outcome of the incubation's ‘black box’ (Ayatse *et al.*, 2017). To conclude, this model consists of three basic activities: choosing nascent start-ups with a strong potential to grow, tracking and supporting those who will succeed, and finally delivering the necessary resources to enable them to successfully exit the incubator.

Bergek and Norrman (2008) argue that the incubation process model has been deemed as a black box inside which incubator objectives and their final outcome has been concentrated on, whereas the internal procedure has been widely overlooked. In an endeavour to identify the best practice incubator model, Bergek and Norrman (2008) established a framework that contains three distinct model components: selection, business support, and mediation. Building on these earlier models and frameworks, Pauwels *et al.* (2016) propose that access to business infrastructure including physical space, funding resources and networking opportunities should be the essential features of an incubator design.

It is evident that regardless of the several efforts to investigate the incubation process setups, only a few researchers have adopted a comprehensive perspective that includes social as well as structural aspects of the process. Additionally, a considerably limited amount of literature has given consideration to the human contexts that populate these systems, with those that have done so typically limiting themselves to the applicant screening process. These studies have once again concentrated on a structural rather than a social or human perspective of the process.

Incubators have widely been envisioned as a collection of structures bounded together by operational reasoning, instead of the dynamics of social interplay that govern incubation as a practical activity and as perceived by the tenant entrepreneur. In this context, the prevalent perspective of the incubation process and incubator structure is one devoid of the social dimension, in which individuals' conduct is viewed as complying with prearranged responsibilities and regulations. This orientation results in failure to effectively describe how incubatees learn and what exactly happens inside the business incubator in terms of human interaction, and as a result, assigns intangible operational objectives a non-viable and impractical role. Incubator's practices and services are the most pivotal determinant of its incubator's effectiveness (Ayatse *et al.*, 2017; Lewis *et al.*, 2011). Considering this, the obvious scarcity of such a crucial dimension of the incubation process tends to provide a partial grasp of how incubation occurs.

245. Impacts of Business Incubation on Start-ups

The impact of business incubators on incubatee firms has been the focus of researchers for several years and a substantial amount of research has been done to examine the effectiveness of these start-up support mechanisms (Aernoudt, 2004; Bone *et al.*, 2019; Chan and Lau, 2005; Chen and Wang 2008; Hansen *et al.*, 2000; Hughes *et al.*, 2007; Oakey, 2007; Patton, 2014; Rothaermel and Thursby, 2005; Scillitoe and Chakrabarti, 2010; Schwartz, 2012; Sehitoglu and Ozdesmir, 2013; Soetanto and Jack, 2013; Voisey *et al.* 2013). Researchers have primarily focused on assessing the success of business incubators in terms of tangible metrics such as firm's performance, profitability, survival, etc., and success of business incubators is often described in tangible or quantifiable measures; however, the softer intangible metrics of success, such as learning and experience of tenant entrepreneur, are potentially just as essential in the development of entrepreneurship.

Although there is a plethora of research on business incubation, there is no widely acknowledged set of metrics to evaluate the effectiveness of incubator programs (Albort- Morant and Ribeiro-Soriano, 2016; Dee *et al.*, 2011; Phan *et al.*, 2005). In order to evaluate the success of business incubation, researchers examined a variety of metrics that pertain to a specific aspect of the business incubator (Dee *et al.*,

2011), such as occupancy, jobs created, firms graduated (Allen and McCluskey, 1991), start-up revenue, number of patent applications per firm, number of discontinued businesses (Phillips, 2002), advantages from pooling resources, sharing resources, consulting services, positive effects from a higher public image, networking advantages, clustering effects, geographic proximity, cost subsidies, funding support (Chan and Lau, 2005). Such variables have been widely used as success measures in most of the studies. Although these metrics give helpful statistics for specific studies, they are of limited relevance in assessing the effectiveness of an incubator (Theodorakopoulos *et al.*, 2014). There is substantial debate over which indicators are well appropriate (Hausberg and Korreck, 2018; Theodorakopoulos *et al.*, 2014). Furthermore, some scholars (such as Dee *et al.*, 2011; Voisey *et al.*, 2006) have highlighted that incubator success is skewed due to the overstated of triumphs and unreported setbacks. This adds up to the challenges of measuring incubator success.

When evaluating business incubation effectiveness, Grimaldi and Grandi (2005) recommend using context-specific quantitative metrics instead of establishing a homogeneous pattern of indicators. For instance, mitigating the costs of setting up a venture and contributing to the regional economic development is the reason behind the development of a non-profit business incubator, so its effectiveness should be assessed accordingly, whereas corporate incubators should be evaluated on their capacity to expedite the start-up period of extremely innovative businesses. Finally, the rationale for university business incubators is their ability to minimise start-up costs for inspiring entrepreneurial projects. These incubators should be evaluated on their ability to curtail start-up costs, boosting the economy, and most importantly successful transfer of knowledge (Grimaldi and Grandi, 2005) i.e., learning of the tenant entrepreneurs.

Vanderstraeten and Matthyssens (2010) argue that the literature on business incubation assessment is contradictory, and according to them confining the success evaluation of incubators to simply limited success metrics is a miscalculation as this can restrict the comprehension of the BIs phenomenon. To achieve a better understanding of BIs and their effectiveness, they favour six parameters introduced by Schwartz and Göthner (2009) to assess the success of various business incubators

statistically. These are “average incubation time, (2) share of start-ups, (3) share of high-tech firms, (4) client satisfaction, (5) overall survival, and (6) employment growth after graduation”.

Contrary to Grimaldi and Grandi’s (2005) recommendation of classifying incubators as public, corporate and university backed for effectiveness assessment, Al-Mubarak and Wong (2011) suggest that the specialisation of incubator e.g., tech incubator or a non-tech incubator should be acknowledged when employing hard metrics for incubator effectiveness. While reviewing the income statement is frequently the conventional approach for determining performance in any business organisation (Voisey *et al.*, 2013), but analysing the performance of not-for-profit business incubators, such as UBIs, necessitates a more complex approach (Sawhill and Williamson, 2001).

The literature on the use of hard measures to understand business incubation’s role is clearly disputed. The extant research on business incubation argues for an approach that takes a comprehensive perspective and employ soft metrics (such as incubatee learning and development) to assess the effectiveness of non-profit incubators such as public and university business incubators as most incubators are non-profit organisations (Hackett and Dilts, 2004b). As a result, it might be argued that the achievements of the tenant entrepreneurs are a stronger metric of incubator effectiveness. Successful graduation of a tenant entrepreneur reflects the success of the incubator programme and all the facilities it offers. However, very few studies have taken this into account such as Bergek and Norrman, 2008; Robinson and Stubberud, 2014; Stokan, Thompson and Mahu, 2015. In a more recent study, Alpenidze *et al.* (2019) highlight a significant issue in assessing the success of incubation that it is challenging to evaluate the effectiveness of incubation as the outcomes might take a long time to manifest. A venture can take on average two to three years to incubate, and the outcomes might take a long time to manifest. Most studies that evaluate the impact of incubation neglect the ‘follow-on actions’ and ‘entrepreneurial learning’ that are likely to occur as a result of the company's demise (Alpenidze *et al.*, 2019). According to Alpenidze *et al.* (2019), some business incubators do not keep track of their results beyond the number of ventures that graduate and the data is unreliable for those that track the results. Consequently,

success is overstated whereas setbacks are understated (Dee *et al.*, 2011; Voisey *et al.*, 2006).

It is evident from the above discussion that it is crucial to consider the soft metrics such as incubatee learning and development while assessing the effectiveness of incubator programs and disregarding such metrics may result in presenting a non-viable image of the incubation.

24.6. Roles of Business Incubators on the Development of Incubatees

Upon reviewing the incubation literature, Hackett and Dilts (2004b) identified that little attention has been paid to how tenant entrepreneurs evolve during the incubation process. As a result of the systematic review, they spotted that merely three attempts were made to study incubatee development. These investigations focused on the growth of tenant entrepreneurs with the help of incubator involvement. Fry (1987) undertook a census of NBIA members to investigate the differences in the degree of planning activities among tenant entrepreneurs. The study contends that tenant entrepreneurs are more active planners compared to non-participating entrepreneurs. Stuart and Abetti (1987) concentrate on the factors that influence the early success of nascent ventures. The authors find a positive correlation between entrepreneurial attributes and success whereas a negative correlation between success and market dynamism, R&D intensity and start-up provenance. Scherer and McDonald (1988) study five tenants of the St. Louis Technology Center and the study highlighted the new venture's proclivity for overly ambitious growth assumptions and a lack of understanding of the requirement for operational capital. According to Hackett and Dilts (2004b), these findings are hardly ground-breaking; however, they are valuable in emphasising the fact that incubatees have the same shortcomings as non-incubatees. These three investigations focused on the development of tenant entrepreneurs through incubator assistance, and Hackett and Dilts' (2004b, p.13) review concluded, "incubatee development studies are underdeveloped and will likely remain so...".

In a later study, Bøllingtoft and Ulhøi (2005), highlight that the importance of social connections within a business incubator has received little attention as researchers and scholars have examined the business incubator phenomenon using a traditional

top-down planning approach that views business incubator as a structure supervised by a qualified incubator management team. The study also suggests that it is critical to conduct research on entrepreneurial activities and facilities, as well as BIs, talents, and social networks.

Theodorakopoulos *et al.* (2014) highlight that over the recent years, intangible indicators and social aspects of business incubation have received researchers' attention while identifying incubation success factors, however, despite this shift in focus to more intangible aspects of business incubation, it is undeniable that there are still major inadequacies in understanding the role of incubator managers in helping the incubatees build their entrepreneurial skills. They further point out that a vast majority of business incubation studies ignores the perspective of the tenant entrepreneurs.

2.4.7. Entrepreneurial Learning of Incubatees

Understanding how incubatee entrepreneurs learn and exploit opportunities throughout their stay at the incubator is critical not only for the advancement of business incubation research but also for entrepreneurship research in general. This postulates an important issue that how incubatees learn to exploit opportunities in the incubator setting, and to cope with the liabilities of newness associated with new venture creation.

Entrepreneurial learning is characterized by Minniti and Bygrave (2001) as a process of learning by doing. According to them, entrepreneurs learn from their positive and negative experiences and take decisions in the light of those experiences. This approach is individual centred and does not consider the surroundings of the entrepreneurs. This perspective is criticised by Larty (2005) who claim that experiential research concentrates solely on the individual and ignores the social aspect of learning.

According to Thorpe *et al.* (2006), learning research is placing emphasis on learning networks or communities. Supporting this view, Seidel (2002) argues that a business incubator is a social network that provides a collective learning environment for the tenant entrepreneurs' development. McAdam and McAdam's (2006) study highlights that business incubators play a crucial part in the provision of external networks. These researchers revealed a relationship between the development of

entrepreneurs and the social setting of a business incubator (Meckel, 2014); however, they are mainly concerned with the incubation's networking impact.

Entrepreneurs learn from irregular experiences and introspective constructive self-contemplation, according to Cope (2003). He also suggests that additional study is required to examine the social aspects of the phenomenon of learning from irregular events. Rae (2005) takes both individualistic and collective learning into account and claims that entrepreneurial learning necessitates not just an individual's capacity to see and respond to possibilities, but also the ability to engage socially in order to launch develop and manage projects.

Wenger (1998) regards learning as social engagement, based on the notion of situated learning, and classifies learning into four components: learning as becoming, learning as experiencing, learning as doing, and learning as belonging. These aspects imply that entrepreneurs learn not only from self-contemplation but also by engaging with their surroundings and through community interactions (Meckel, 2014). Several studies argue that entrepreneurial learning does not occur in solitude but rather as part of a social process and is socially created (Cope 2003; Cope and Watts 2000; Rae 2005; Rae and Carswell 2001). Pittaway and Cope (2007b) outline reflecting, reasoning, encountering, and implementing as key aspects of entrepreneurial learning. Entrepreneurial learning entails devising innovative methods of resource management while seeking opportunities (Hassan, 2020). This notion recognises the proactive part entrepreneurs play in the process of recognising and exploiting opportunities through self- contemplation and interpersonal relationships.

As this research precisely focuses on UBIs, the next section describes UBI and review the relevant existing literature.

2.5. University Business Incubation

2.5.1. Introduction to University Business Incubators

The notion of 'Entrepreneurial University' has grown in popularity over the previous few decades (Guerrero and Urbano, 2012). An entrepreneurial university's mission involves not just teaching for students' intellectual growth and research for the advancement of science, but also contributing to the ecosystem's economic,

sociological, technological, and policy development (Nicotra *et al.*, 2021). This rising trend is referred to as the *third mission* (Cunningham *et al.*, 2018; Lehmann and Menter, 2016), and it is widely regarded as an important aspect of university operations (Nicotra *et al.*, 2018). The *third mission*, which urged universities to become central to regional economic growth, established a procedure that was widely implemented in the USA (Etzkowitz, 1998) and the UK (Woollard *et al.*, 2007).

To improve economic performance, the UK, like many other advanced and developing economies, has fostered the establishment of business incubators to promote technology transfer and enhance economic performance (Cooper and Park, 2008). To help entrepreneurs overcome the difficulties and challenges of new venture formation, UK universities have been significantly involved in the development of business incubators (Jayawarna *et al.*, 2011). Policy makers in the UK have focused on knowledge as the core competitive differentiator and as a result, several business incubators have been established in collaboration with universities aiming to promote entrepreneurship and innovation (Hannon and Chaplin, 2003; Jones *et al.* 2014; Reid and Garnsey, 1998).

Todorovic and Moenter's (2010, p.28) define university business incubation programme as:

“a university incubator is a programme sponsored by a university to nurture new and small businesses by providing support throughout the early stages of development. Most university incubators provide specialized resources, such as technical or other research capabilities that are not otherwise available to the firm.”

University Business Incubators (UBIs) are a form of Business Incubators (Hassan, 2020; Nicholls-Nixon and Valliere, 2020), and are seen by policy makers as a tool to foster entrepreneurship and enhance regional economic growth. UBIs are primarily designed to encourage and support graduate entrepreneurs in setting up their own ventures (Battisti and McAdam, 2012; Jones *et al.*, 2021). Several universities in the UK provide business incubation programmes to promote entrepreneurship by assisting recent graduates to initiate entrepreneurial paths (Bone *et al.*, 2019; Voisey *et al.*, 2013). It is not easy for recent graduates to pursue entrepreneurial paths due to their lack of enterprise and industry experience and the

burden of student loans, and not to mention their lack of credibility with investors and resource providers, and limited social networks (Jones *et al.*, 2021b). Incubators are designed to assist these nascent entrepreneurs in overcoming such disadvantages in a variety of ways (Jones *et al.*, 2021b), such as connecting them with the wider entrepreneurial ecosystem (Van Weele *et al.* 2018) and providing them access to funding opportunities (McAdam *et al.*, 2016). In addition to the standard incubation services, UBIs provide tenant entrepreneurs with university services and resources (Redondo and Camarero, 2019). Despite the fact that universities have the same goal and share similar socioeconomic circumstances, they are distinguished by their rules, procedures, resources, and features (Guerrero and Urban, 2012). Equivalently, based on differences in their resources, regional and organisational factors, limitations, and stakeholder constituencies (McAdam *et al.*, 2016), UBIs exist in a variety of designs and dimensions (Wonglimpiyarat, 2016).

2.5.2. Key Activities of University Business Incubators

Incubation activities involve the services and resources received by tenant entrepreneurs during their tenancy at the UBI. UBIs provide tenant entrepreneurs with university services and resources in addition to usual incubation services (Redondo and Camarero, 2019). Stokan *et al.* (2015) suggest that incubation offers a variety of services, and regardless of the fact that tenant firms get access to more services compared to non-incubated start-ups, it is still unclear which services have the greatest effect. Allen *et al.* (1990) observed that in the incubator sector, services are referred to as value-added, which refers to the particular techniques that an incubator uses to help its tenant entrepreneurs thrive and expand their businesses. A university business incubation programme generally consists of the following components:

Shared office space and facilities: The provision of affordable office space allows the entrepreneurs to save cost and avoid potential problems such as restrictive tenancy agreements, resource constraints and unappealing sites during the early stages of venture development (Todorovic and Moenter, 2010; Zhang and Sonobe, 2011).

Business Support Training and Development: Throughout the initiative, the start-up team collaborates closely with mentors, consultants and experts in order to

obtain the experience needed to effectively communicate their business concepts to prospective investors. Meanwhile, the incubator's team assists the nascent ventures in establishing the business operational procedures (Bergek and Norrman, 2008). Business consulting services, which include guidance on legal and intellectual property rights, advice on business insurance, etc., have been reported to have a positive impact on start-ups' performance (Cumming and Fischer, 2012). In addition, incubator advisors, according to research, operate as intermediaries between venture capitalists and entrepreneurs (McAdam and Marlow, 2012). Similarly, enterprise training and development is regarded as a significant aspect of the incubation programme, as nascent entrepreneurs often lack prior business or industry experience (Bergek and Norrman, 2008).

Mentorship and Coaching: In the early stages of an entrepreneur's career, mentorship is seen to be beneficial because it provides a sense of foresight and can expedite the start-up development process because mentors can detect difficulties and hazards beforehand, leading to avoidance of mistakes (Haines, 2016). Mentorship has been demonstrated to boost an entrepreneur's confidence and risk-taking ability; however, the role of a mentor is to listen to the mentee's struggles and encourage a dialogue to help the mentee develop new ideas and perspectives regarding an issue, instead of forcing the mentee to adopt a specific course of action (Burke, 1984; Bury and Lonsdale, 2010).

Access to Funding: Financing constraints harm small firms more than large ones, according to the literature (Cantamessa *et al.*, 2018). The lack of access to capital is also a major obstacle to start-up survival and expansion (Akter and Iqbal, 2020). Furthermore, difficulty in obtaining funding because of a lack of credibility in the eyes of investors is linked to this factor (Yang and Aldrich, 2017). Therefore, the need to access capital to establish their ventures is a primary motivation for most entrepreneurs who join incubation programmes (Muriithi *et al.*, 2018). As incubators frequently have strong ties to a variety of funding sources and investors, they can offer substantial support and guidance to the entrepreneurs seeking funding to initiate and grow their venture (Muriithi *et al.*, 2018; Shih and Aabo, 2019).

Network Mediation: The incubation process extends beyond the confines of the incubator (Hackett and Dilts, 2004 b). As a result, one crucial aspect of an incubator

is to act as a 'bridge' (Bergek and Norrman, 2008) between entrepreneurs and pertinent innovation systems (Peters, Rice and Sundararajan, 2004). Incubators engage in network facilitation, which entails pairing tenant entrepreneurs with key stakeholders, in order to offset the lack of established entrepreneurial networks among incubatees (Peters *et al.*, 2004; von Zedwitz, 2003). Bergek and Norrman (2008) use the term 'network mediation' instead of the more widely used 'networking' in order to distinguish the incubator's intermediate position from its operations to developing a network from which it can acquire knowledge for its business support activities.

University Resources: Access to university resources such as academics, students and lab or other specialised equipment is a distinguishing feature of UBIs. Studies suggest that faculty involvement in the start-up process is of utmost importance for the entrepreneurs as they can provide specialised scientific knowledge in the areas of product creation and enterprise innovation (Breznitz and Zhang, 2019; Mosey and Wright, 2007; Wright *et al.*, 2017).

Innovation: One of the most important functions of UBIs is to stimulate innovation and creativity among the start-ups they sponsor, which they achieve by providing long-term and robust entrepreneurial support (Muriithi *et al.*, 2018), and by offering support from academics and researchers (Mosey and Wright, 2007; Wright *et al.*, 2017). Incubators help firms to pursue innovative ideas by providing them with a supportive infrastructure and the latest facilities (Muriithi *et al.*, 2018).

Graduation: Graduation or exit is linked to evacuation strategies, or decisions about when and how tenant entrepreneurs should exit the incubator programme (Bergek and Norrman, 2008). Pitch Day or Demo Day, which is the final step of the incubation programme in most incubators, is normally the culmination of the incubator's programme. Start-up companies from a cohort showcase their start-up venture to an audience of investors and corporate strategists chosen by the incubator on the Demo Day. It is very similar to BBC's Dragon's Den where young entrepreneurs pitch their ideas in front of a panel of prospective investors hoping to secure funding from them.

2.6. Knowledge Gap and Conceptual Framework

Although entrepreneurs are the primary players incubated and they have a particularly critical effect on the capacity of ventures to spin-off from the incubation process, existing incubation process research has mostly overlooked them (Gertner, 2013; Phan *et al.*, 2005). It is evident that not only is the incubatees' perspective overlooked, but the manner in which learning occurs in business incubators is also neglected. Over the years the business incubation literature has progressed from describing business incubation to establishing tangible metrics of performance (Grimaldi and Grandi 2005; Vanderstraeten and Matthyssens 2010), with a subsequent yet limited attention on soft metrics (Hannon, 2005). On one hand, quantitative or hard metrics are important to assess the efficient use of financing in the business incubators, but on the other hand, these measures are inadequate to offer a comprehensive insight into the business incubator process. In simple words, assessing the effectiveness of business incubators using quantitative metrics such as firm's performance, profitability, survival, funding rounds, etc. cannot provide a picture of what happens in these start-up support mechanisms, or how the incubation process and interactions shape the experience of tenant entrepreneurs and impact their learning.

It is evident that the research on the role of incubators is scattered, and that many studies in business incubation literature are descriptive and output-focused (Hackett and Dilts, 2008; Meckel, 2014; Todorovic and Moenter, 2010). Extant research on business incubation in the domain of entrepreneurship has focused on essential entrepreneurial traits (Hackett and Dilts, 2008; Bhabra, 2014) and human resources (Bandera and Thomas, 2018), extraneous impacts and knowledge transfer inside the BI (Hackett and Dilts, 2008; Bhabra, 2014). A crucial aspect of how learning takes place in the BIs has been widely overlooked by these studies (Mattushek, 2020).

From the discussions presented in this chapter, it is evident that the extant research on the role and impact of business incubators is scattered, and a gap in understanding the process of business incubation from the perspective of incubatee entrepreneurs was identified. Understanding how entrepreneurial learning takes place inside the incubator as a result of the incubation process is critical to identify the role and

effectiveness of BIs. This research, therefore, seeks to bridge the existing knowledge gap by investigating the UK university business incubation sector. The findings of this research are expected to make a valuable addition to the literature by exploring the perceptions of entrepreneurs towards UK university business incubators and revealing the challenges they face whilst participating in incubation programmes.

2.6.1. Conceptual framework

The review of literature on incubation and entrepreneurial learning guided the researcher to the development of a conceptual framework for this study. According to Imenda (2014), a conceptual framework is the outcome of combining a number of linked concepts to explain or predict a specific event, or to provide a comprehensive understanding of the given phenomenon— or simply, to answer a research problem. The following principles, as guided by Imenda (2014), were followed whilst constructing the conceptual framework:

- Incorporating several relevant concepts about business incubation and entrepreneurial learning that were discovered during the literature research,
- Combining or dividing these concepts, if required, to form obvious distinct groups, and
- Using appropriate terminology either by embracing existing terms where they are widely used or by generating new ones.

The following conceptual framework has been derived from the concepts that emerged in the literature review of business incubation and entrepreneurial learning.

Figure 2-5: Conceptual Framework

Source: Researcher

Participation in start-up incubation programmes could help overcome challenges in new venture formation (Politis *et al.*, 2019). These programmes can also be thought of as a collective learning process. These support mechanisms are aimed at improving entrepreneurial abilities and managerial skills, as well as improving market position and offering advice and support on accessing financial resources (Rupčić, 2019). Entrepreneurs have a business idea before starting the incubation program, and during their stay at the incubator, they might expand that business idea and form the venture. BI programme might also result in recognition and exploitation of new opportunities. Therefore, business incubation can be seen as an embodiment of entrepreneurship wherein entrepreneurs seek, explore, and utilise opportunities (Meckel, 2014). Admittedly, the incubation process incorporates the concepts of entrepreneurship, opportunity recognition, and utilisation. The present research explores the perceptions and experiences of incubatee entrepreneurs of the incubator program, investigating the incubation programme from the perspectives of entrepreneurs will provide a thorough understanding of how entrepreneurs learn during the incubation process. Entrepreneurs are the primary players incubated

and have a significant impact on the potential of ventures successfully leave the incubation phase, therefore closing this gap is critical (Phan, Siegel and Wright, 2005).

Effective learning is widely acknowledged as critical to entrepreneurship success (Cope, 2005a; Corbett, 2005; Deakins et al, 2000; Erikson, 2003; Man, 2007; Minniti and Bygrave, 2001; Politis, 2005; Rae and Carswell, 2000). The process of entrepreneurship development is regarded to be centred on learning (Deakins et al, 2000). The skills, information, and competencies required at different phases of venture development can be obtained through successful learning and then implemented. Most of the entrepreneurial learning takes place in the workplace environment, where nascent entrepreneurs learn from their decisions, failures, experience, and connections. Many prior studies have been devoted to the topic of entrepreneurial learning with the implementation of various learning theories, such as experiential learning, cognitive-affective learning, situated learning and learning from the network. Studies suggest that entrepreneurs commit to formal and informal learning activities on an individual level (Davidsson and Honig, 2003; Man, 2007), or collectively such as organising peer-learning communities (Tell, 2008). However, learning through experience is thought to have a big role in the development of the entrepreneur as a person (Rae 2006).

Knowledge is built through the comprehending or interpretation of raw experience, as well as the modification of that experience. This concept blends experience, perspective, cognition, and behaviour. In short, according to the experiential viewpoint, an entrepreneur develops required information, capabilities, and competencies through ‘learning by doing’ or via experience” (Man, 2007). The cognitive-affective approach views entrepreneurial learning as a cognitive process of obtaining, retaining, and applying entrepreneurial knowledge in long memory. Learning, in this view, can be viewed as mental labour in the acquisition and organisation of knowledge. The decision-making process is also strongly linked to entrepreneurial learning as the entrepreneurs learn from their own past experiences and of others. The situated learning approach implies that learning is incorporated into daily activities and routines. It reaffirms the notion that learning is both a group and an individual endeavour (Hamilton, 2011). The networking approach to learning

suggests that firms and entrepreneurs learn from their networks. Networking can teach an entrepreneur, not just technical and specialized information, but also dynamic, non-expert driven advice and experience, which can result in long-term profits for the entrepreneurial venture. This sort of education promotes the development of entrepreneurial skills (Man, 2007). In the context of business incubation, university incubators integrate the networked model that allows internal networking among the tenant entrepreneurs and as well as external networking opportunities (Bruneel *et al.*, 2012; Bøllingtoft and Ulhøi, 2005; Eveleens *et al.*, 2017; Hansen *et al.* 2000). In short, the literature suggests that effective entrepreneurial learning can contribute to entrepreneurial expertise and knowledge which includes recognising opportunities and dealing with the liabilities of newness.

2.7. Summary of the Chapter

Business incubation has rapidly evolved over the years (Bruneel *et al.* 2012; Grimaldi and Grandi, 2005; Lalkaka, 2002; Hausberg and Korreck, 2018). While the first generation of incubators concentrated mainly on infrastructure provision, the second generation complemented their way of working by offering one-on-one business advice to the tenant entrepreneurs. Lately, by concentrating on facilitating networks, incubators have expanded their approach. This network-based approach lets incubatees navigate intangible resources like information and credibility (Bruneel *et al.*, 2012), and these intangible resources are deemed valuable to nascent entrepreneurs (Chen, 2009). As the number of incubators has grown to more than 7000 globally in the recent decades (NBIA, 2014), business incubation for its potential to contribute towards technology transfer and entrepreneurship, has gained significant attention from scholars, policy makers and business leaders (Aernoudt 2004; Hausberg and Korreck, 2018; Phan *et al.*, 2005).

There is variation in the definition and business model of incubators. Moreover, scholars have labelled BIs under a variety of more or less interchangeable terms over the years (Theodorakopoulos *et al.*, 2014). To complicate things further, much of the extant literature does not describe the incubation process clearly. All these issues make the business incubation phenomenon challenging to study. Additionally, such difficulties obstruct the generalisation of discoveries and conceptualisation in the

field of business incubation (Theodorakopoulos *et al.*, 2014). It is critical to comprehend the function of business incubators, as they have grown in importance as a tool for institutions and governments to promote entrepreneurship, innovation and economic development. Existing research does not account for the diversity of incubation settings, which complicates incubation process theorising.

During the past few decades, the business incubation literature has progressed beyond identifying the BIs phenomenon to creating concrete metrics of performance. It is challenging to measure the efficacy of business incubators and the literature on business incubation assessment is contradictory (Bergek and Norrman, 2008; Hackett and Dilts, 2004a; Hausberg and Korreck, 2018; Theodorakopoulos *et al.*, 2014). Confining the success evaluation of BIs to simply limited success metrics is a miscalculation as this restricts the comprehension of the BIs phenomenon (Vanderstraeten and Matthyssens, 2010). Intangible metrics such as incubatee learning have been widely overlooked and not viewed as success indicators. According to Dewson *et al.* (2000), soft measures give a crucial context for clients (incubatee start-ups in the context of business incubation) demands and development, resulting in a more accurate, comprehensive image of accomplishments.

While there has been significant research into incubator structures and the impact of incubation (such as Bone *et al.*, 2019; Patton, 2014; Rothaermel and Thursby, 2005; Schwartz, 2012; Sehitoglu and Ozdesmir, 2013; Voisey *et al.* 2013), the aspect of entrepreneurial learning and experience has been widely overlooked by the researchers (Mattushek, 2021; Voisey *et al.*, 2006). Researchers have primarily focused on assessing the success of business incubators in terms of tangible metrics such as firm's performance, profitability, survival, etc., and success of business incubators is often described in quantifiable measures such as profitability, number of employees, etc., however, the softer or intangible metrics of success, such as learning and experience of tenant entrepreneur, are potentially just as essential in the development of entrepreneurship (Politis and Gabrielsson, 2015). Soft metrics can provide a greater understanding of the incubation process while also providing an alternative technique to determining incubation effectiveness. Therefore, this research seeks to investigate the perceptions of incubatees regarding UK university

incubation programmes in order to identify ways for enhancing the effectiveness of current business incubation programmes.

This chapter extensively reviewed the existing literature related to business incubation and how entrepreneurs learn whilst participating in such programmes. Different types of incubation programmes were discussed and the processes in which they assist entrepreneurs were evaluated. The next chapter now deals with the methodological aspect of the research.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Introduction

This chapter elaborates on this study's methodological approach. Various research philosophies are discussed and analysed in order to choose an appropriate philosophical approach. Following the selection of appropriate research philosophy, suitable data collection and analysis techniques are reviewed. This chapter also discusses the sampling methods, research reliability, validity, quality, and ethical considerations made. Section 3.1 contains a brief introduction of the chapter, in section 3.2 research framework is presented, in section 3.3 distinctions between philosophical assumptions are drawn, in section 3.4 research philosophy and different paradigms are discussed, section 3.5 discusses different approaches and choosing the appropriate approach, section 3.6 discusses research strategies and identifies case study as the suitable strategy for this thesis, the study design is presented in section 3.7, methods of data collection and analysis are discussed in section 3.8, in section 3.9 research reliability, validity, and quality issues are discussed, section 3.10 elaborates ethical considerations and finally section 3.11 concludes this chapter by providing a brief summary.

3.2. Research Framework

The procedural framework within which the research is undertaken is referred to as research methodology; it outlines a problem-solving strategy that could be implemented in a research project or process (Remenyi et. al., 1998). After identifying a research problem or question, a researcher has to choose a suitable research strategy and methodology for gathering data that will elucidate the research issue (Baker, 2000). Choosing the right approach and methodology for a research project can be a challenging and time-consuming task. The researcher investigates theoretical foundations, collects and analyses data, and ultimately develops conclusions about the subject under investigation (Walker, 1997). According to Collis and Hussey (2009, cited in Keith, 2014), methodology is the holistic approach to the overall process of the research study. Research technique fundamentally

focuses on determining the nature of the research problem (Remenyi *et al.*, 2003). Hence, selecting the most optimal and relevant methodology is essential to effectively meet the research objectives and for establishing the reliability of the research study. It is crucial to have consistency and logical alignment between research questions and approaches, both theoretically and methodologically, given the research philosophy, approach, strategy and procedures are all fundamental components of methodology (Churchill and Sanders, 2007). Following a review of the literature identified the various research models for undertaking a study in social science, and after careful considerations of all key models, a decision was made to adopt the research onion model of Saunders *et al.* (2019) in this research. The figure below presents the adopted research model:

Figure 3-1: The Research Onion Model

Source: Saunders et al. (2009)

This chapter is structured on the basis of Saunders *et al.* (2019)'s research onion model, in which the thoughts about the research problem are at the centre point and numerous layers must be reviewed and explained before reaching this central location, which is to conduct data collection and analysis. The subsequent section

now discusses the key research philosophies used in social science and offers justifications on the selected research philosophy of this research.

3.3. Philosophical Assumptions

Identifying the appropriate philosophy is of utmost importance in planning and executing a research study (Saunders *et al.*, 2019). Reliable research philosophy is built on carefully planned and coherent assumptions that will guide the methodological choices, research plan, data collection strategies, and data analysis process (Creswell, 2014). Since research philosophy is located at the outer layer of the research onion model, it is the first element to be addressed in the research methodology. Research philosophies are referred to as paradigms and the beliefs and assumptions that drive the researcher (Lincoln *et al.*, 2011; Saunders *et al.*, 2019). This section outlines the underlying theories of research philosophies of the research onion and the paradigms and provides a justification of the chosen philosophy for this thesis. According to Saunders *et al.* (2019), it is vital to consider the philosophical assumptions prior to determining the appropriate philosophical stance for a research study. Below, a brief description of philosophical assumptions is presented:

Ontology refers to a set of beliefs about the nature of reality. It is defined by Blaikie (2007) as the study of being, that describes the nature and form of reality. Saunders *et al.* (2019) take the example of Brexit where voters and non-voters made varied assumptions about the reality of the country's presence in the European Union, and their beliefs and assumptions shaped their decision of leaving or staying in the EU. To put it more simply, ontology clarifies the distinction between reality and how it is perceived. Hatch and Cunliffe (2006) requested study participants to express their perspectives of reality in order to investigate the idea of ontology, suggesting that people perceive reality differently as 'subjective' or 'objective' based on personal experiences. The researcher should define the actuality and truth of the researched phenomena, at the ontological level (Polit and Beck, 2004). The primary purpose of the present study is to learn about the perceptions of participants of university business incubators and understand their perspective of learning within university

incubators. Since this research involves exploring the experiences of individuals, a decision was made to investigate the phenomenon subjectively.

Epistemology refers to assumptions about knowledge, as well as what comprises acceptable, accurate, and valid knowledge and how that knowledge can be communicated to others (Burrell and Morgan, 1979; Walliman, 2011). According to Marsh and Furlong (2002), epistemology is ‘the theory of knowledge’. It aids in defining what knowledge is, as well as its sources and boundaries (Eriksson and Kovalainen, 2008). In simple words, it seeks accepted information and addresses facts in accordance with that. Referring back to Saunders *et al.*’s (2019) example of Brexit, voters made assumptions about the admissibility and credibility of data offered by both the pro-remain and anti-remain campaigns. Philosophical viewpoints related to epistemology include positivism, critical realism, and interpretivism. This research takes an interpretivist viewpoint; the rationale for selecting interpretivist philosophy is provided in chapter 3.4.

Axiology refers to the role of morals and values in research (Creswell 2009; Lincoln *et al.* 2011). Saunders *et al.* (2019) highlighted that one of the most crucial decisions researchers have to make is whether or not they desire to see the influence of their own views and values on the research as a positive move. Therefore, researchers must decide how they will deal with their own beliefs and values as well as the values of the people they are researching in order to ensure the results of the study are reliable and valid, the role of researcher's own beliefs and values during different stages of the research process are of utmost importance.

Methodology is the “strategy or plan of action” that guides the selection and application of certain procedures (Crotty, 1998, p. 3). Consequently, methodology addresses why, what, where, when, and how data is collected and processed (Scotland, 2012). According to Guba and Lincon (1994, p. 108) methodology asks: how can the observer go about finding out whatever they feel should be known?

3.3.1. Subjectivism vs Objectivism

In business and management studies, subjectivism and objectivism are two opposite approaches (Nigals, 2010 cited in Saunders *et al.*, 2016). Objectivism adheres to

scientific principles, which are commonly used in natural sciences, and contends that social reality is an external factor, while on the contrary, subjectivism contends investigators as part of their research, and assert that the social phenomenon being studied is directly influenced by the researcher's comprehension (Saunders *et al.*, 2016).

On an ontological level, objectivism supports realism, wherein all social constructs are viewed as physical substances; however, subjectivism encompasses nominalism, stating that reality is founded on social actors' conceptions, and hence reality generation involves social interactions (Bryman, 2012). Subjectivists stress on individual situations, views, and characterisations from an epistemological standpoint, whereas objectivists strive to discover the truth by obvious and quantifiable facts, which amounts to forming generalisations (Hiller, 2016). Subjectivists believe in profound reflexivity, in which they continually reflect on issues using open exchanges, while objectivists contend that isolating themselves from personal ideas and values during the research process serves to decrease bias in conclusions (Saunders *et al.*, 2016).

Ratner (2002) argues that there is an objectivist strand in qualitative methodology as well. As per objectivism, the researchers' subjectivity can allow them to accurately perceive the world as it is, but subjectivity can influence the researcher and prevent objective knowledge of a subject's psychological reality; however, this is not unavoidable as one of the benefits of understanding subjectivity is that it allows the researcher to consider whether it aids or hinders objective comprehension (Ratner, 2002). Values that impede objectivity can then be substituted with values that improve objectivity (Ratner, 2002). Researchers must be conscious of how their own and the participants' perceptions may have been normalised, else they risk implicitly accepting the patterns and visions enforced by the prevailing discourse (Mills, 2010).

After analysing the nature of the topic under examination, the researcher chose subjectivism since it corresponds to the purpose of the study, which is to explore tenant entrepreneurs' perceptions of university incubation programmes. As

subjectivism stress on individual situations, views, and characterisations from an epistemological standpoint (Hiller, 2016), it is considered suitable to gain an in-depth insight into the incubatees' perspective of support and resources provided by UBIs. Furthermore, some sciences, such as the Human Sciences, are now questioning the ideas of objectivity (Fuza, 2017), attempting to involve the subjects who conduct science, barring them from behaving as simple replicators of the "scientific status quo" (Rodrigues, 2009, p. 5).

Positivism and interpretivism are the two most popular research philosophies, and each advocates a different approach to inquiry, with the positivist researchers relying on objectivism while the interpretivism embracing subjectivism (Saunders *et al.*, 2016). Pragmatism, which tries to bridge the gap between the two approaches, is also often mentioned in the literature (Creswell and Clark, 2011). In order to identify an appropriate research philosophy for this study, the next section discusses these research philosophies in detail.

3.4. Research Philosophy

The process of obtaining knowledge has generally been divided into three paradigms: positivist, interpretivist (Guba and Lincoln, 1994), and pragmatist (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004). Every paradigm has its own set of ontological and epistemological premises. The philosophical assumptions of any paradigm can never be empirically proven or disproven because all assumptions are speculation (Scotland, 2012). Tsoukas and Knudsen (2003) assert that there is disagreement among researchers and scholars in the business discipline about one best philosophy. The ideal philosophy to choose is decided by the problem statement and aims of the research study (Saunders *et al.*, 2019) and there are three different philosophies to choose from positivism, interpretivism and pragmatism.

3.4.1. Positivism

According to Polit and Beck (2004), the positivist paradigm takes a typical scientific approach to inquiry, stressing the logic and science involved. Cohen *et al.* (2013) argue that positivism seeks to understand social reality through observation and experimentation at the ontological level. The notion of falsification, established by Karl Popper, is one of the key doctrines of positivism. Popper (1963) argued that an

idea could not be considered scientific until it could be falsified. Falsification, in its most basic or naive form, states that once a statement has been shown false, all related theories should be rejected (Remenyi *et al.*, 1998).

Positivism aims to study social reality via quantitative observation and investigation at the ontological level (Cohen *et al.*, 2013; Saunders *et al.*, 2009) and from an epistemological standpoint, in order to prevent bias, positivists try to keep their own ideas and thoughts apart from the case being studied and seek to use a combination of deductive reasoning and detailed empirical observations to find and validate a set of probable causal elements that may be used to predict broad patterns of human behaviour (Antwi and Hamza, 2015).

Positivists devise objective ways for attaining the most accurate representation of reality in terms of how factors interact, influence events, and result in consequences (Creswell, 2014). The positivist paradigm's objectivist ontology and empiricist epistemology necessitate a detached or neutral quantitative research technique, with the emphasis on measuring variables and evaluating hypotheses that are related to broad causal explanations (Antwi and Hamza, 2015; Marczyk *et al.*, 2005). Quantitative methodology is built on a positivist research paradigm (Antwi and Hamza, 2015); thus, approaches that offer quantifiable data are frequently preferred by positivists (Creswell, 2014). Remenyi *et al.* (1998) argues that positivism is not viewed as a method that will lead to fascinating or meaningful insights into complicated issues, notably in the field of business and management studies, especially in the social sciences.

3.4.2. Interpretivism

Positivists' beliefs, on the other hand, have been dismissed by interpretive paradigms. From an ontological standpoint, this paradigm reinforces the importance of contextualising analysis (Cohen, 2013). According to interpretative investigators, realities are made up of an individual's personal experiences of the outside world (Antwi and Hamza, 2015; Thomas, 2017). From an epistemological standpoint, interpretivist scholars think it is difficult to entirely separate cause and effect or to separate the researcher's thoughts and views from the investigation because they

regard it to be the primary source of reality (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004). Interpretivism prioritizes gaining a deeper insight into the world by hands-on and interactive experience, fair documentation, and quotes from participants' conversations. To do so, they use an inductive strategy to develop theory using qualitative data collection techniques, for instance, interview, focus group discussion, or naturalistic observation, which motivates respondents to openly express opinions and fully comprehend the researcher's pursuit for knowledge and understanding into a phenomenon that the participant has encountered (Merriam *et al.*, 2016). This paradigm employs small sample sizes since the focus is not on generalisation to a bigger population, unlike the positivists' numerical instrument (Green *et al.*, 2013). According to Sanders, Lewis and Thornhill(2007), some would suggest that an interpretivist approach is particularly well suited to business and management research, particularly in domains like organisational behaviour, marketing, and human resource management.

3.4.3. Pragmatism

Pragmatism is a paradigm that attempts to act as an intermediary between the two above aforementioned approaches (Creswell and Clark, 2011). The primary objective of this paradigm is to bridge the gap between positivism and interpretivism by taking use of their virtues while limiting their weaknesses (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004). Nonetheless, this paradigm demonstrates a significant gap that may arise when combining the two preceding paradigms, necessitating the researcher's vigilance in addressing them. For instance, the priority given to each paradigm in mixed research studies and the phase at which both methodologies should be merged (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2007). The researcher's ability and the complications of the phenomenon under investigation determine the effectiveness of a pragmatic study.

3.4.4. Selected Research Philosophy and Justifications

According to Guba and Lincoln (1994), paradigms reflect the researcher's core beliefs and ideas and should be accepted on faith. Cohen *et al.* (2002) argue that every researcher should identify which paradigm best represents his or her individual views and follow. It is claimed that neither research approach is superior nor inferior to the other, since both have been shown to be beneficial in research projects (Antwi and

Hamza, 2015). Both positivist and interpretivist paradigms have positives and negatives. Neuman and Robson (2012) argue that the positivist viewpoint is effective in enabling researchers to condense issues based on discernible and measurable measures, and it makes meticulous statistical testing easier to integrate, however, this condensation simplifies some notions, and the quantitative method may not capture the entire intricacy of some experiences. Interpretivism provides a thorough and comprehensive explanation of the phenomenon under investigation (Merriam *et al.*, 2016). The strength of interpretivism (qualitative measures) is that it acknowledges that observation may not necessarily lead to a single conclusion as individuals can interpret events or occurrences differently, however, it limits the element of generalisability (Punch, 2014).

Given the nature of the research topic, the researcher has determined that interpretivism is the most appropriate research philosophy for this research study. Rather than seeking to generalise the foundation of understanding for the entire population, interpretivism encourages researchers to get a deeper grasp of the issue and its intricacies in its specific context (Creswell, 2007). The primary goal of this study is to explore the perceptions of tenant entrepreneurs towards university business incubators and investigate their experience of setting up their venture, as well as to provide the UBIs with a rich insight into how incubation processes and procedures, as well as different forms of social interaction, influence the incubation experience of tenant entrepreneurs. The review of the business incubation literature suggests that the incubatee perspective of BIs is an under-studied phenomenon and requires exploring, this highlights the need to investigate and bring into attention the perspectives and detailed first-hand experiences of tenant entrepreneurs by utilising an interpretivist approach to the investigation, which can be best done by conducting an exploratory qualitative study.

Moreover, understanding the perceptions of the respondents requires incorporating their views and experiences, which can be best investigated under the interpretivist philosophy. Adopting an interpretivist approach enables the researcher to gather the experiences of participants of the study as well as gain a rich insight into their perspectives which can ultimately provide a better understanding of the business

incubation process in the UBI context. In addition, the incipient nature of research on the incubate-perspective renders itself to an interpretive qualitative approach, which can generate a rich understanding of the underexplored phenomenon by minimising the difference between incubatees and the investigator that can ultimately assist in developing theoretical as well as practical understanding of the topic, and thereby addressing the knowledge gap (Ponelis, 2015). It may be unviable to examine phenomena relating to individuals' perceptions, attitudes, and views using a positivist approach (Hammersley, 2013). Adopting a positivist approach could limit the researcher's ability to gain in-depth insight into tenant entrepreneurs business incubation experience.

3.5. Research Approach

This part of the chapter examines two major logical thinking methods that are most appropriate as a firm foundation for this study. According to Cresswell (2007), it is essential to demonstrate the research approach as a useful tool to improve the credibility of research in social sciences. Hence, both approaches have been discussed in this section.

3.5.1. Deductive Approach

The deductive approach involves establishing a hypothesis based on extant theory and then constructing a research plan to test the hypothesis (Wilson, 2010). According to Trochim, (2000), the deductive approach is regarded as involving more scientific reasoning; it progresses from general to specific, drawing inferences from specific results and evidence. As cited by Keith (2014), Newton's discovery of gravity from the sight of an apple falling to the ground, which he inferred must have been caused by gravity, is a well-known example of the deductive approach, therefore, a particular conclusion can be reached focusing on a particular result. The figure below shows the process of theory testing in a deductive study.

Figure 3-2: Deductive Approach

Source: Burney (2008)

The deductive, also referred to as the ‘top-down’ approach (Creswell and Clark, 2007), starts with a basic theory that is being investigated, related to the subject of research. The theory is subsequently developed into a hypothesis, which is put to the test to see if it is true or not (Gill and Johnson, 2002). The inquiry is guided by the hypothesis and theories are notional and suppositious answers to the issues that are put to the test through observation and experimentation (Walliman, 2011). The hypothesis must be stated as verifiable, allowing the required variables to be assessed in order to verify or disprove the hypothesis, and hence the theory's validity. The test's findings should demonstrate the link between the variables. The hypothesis may need to be revised as a result of this finding to allow for more precise results.

The Ancient Greeks were the first to consider deduction as a method of reasoning (Walliman, 2011). Despite being a classic method, the deductive approach is not without flaws. Williman, (2011) argues that the validity of the conclusions is highly dependent on the accuracy of the assumptions and premises. Blaikie (1993) claims that deductive reasoning is inductive due to its subjectivity. Although hypothesis testing is regarded as scientific, the theory that serves as the foundation for the reasoning might be challenged as being biased and subjective. Subjective

interpretation may have a strong influence on how a hypothesis is generated and how it turns out.

3.5.2. Inductive Approach

Inductive reasoning builds a broad conclusion or a general theory from particular observations or sensory occurrences (Trochim, 2000; Walliman, 2011). According to Williman (2011), induction was the first and is still the most prevalent method of scientific endeavour today as we incorporate it on a daily basis in our everyday lives to learn from our surrounding environments and experiences. The inductive approach, also referred to as the ‘bottom-up’ approach (Creswell and Clark, 2007), begins with a certain observation and progresses to a broader theory or conclusion, implying some ambiguity when dealing with increasingly complicated variables; initial results may be contradicted (Walliman, 2011).

Revisiting Newton’s discovery of gravity example, if Newton had used inductive reasoning to analyse the same scenario, he would have noticed an apple falling during the harvest season and a multitude of complicated elements would have been identified as the possible causes. According to Blaikie (2007), the method is based on the assumption that all science is derived from observations, which lay the groundwork for knowledge development. The figure below shows the process of theory creation in an inductive study.

Figure 3-3: Inductive Approach

Source: Burney (2008)

The fundamental difficulty with the inductive technique is the potential of forming wrong conclusions based on erroneous connections between observations. The likelihood of inaccurate conclusions can be lowered, but not completely eliminated, by increasing the number of observations.

3.5.3. Selected Research Approach and Justifications

After careful considerations of both inductive and deductive approaches, an inductive approach is utilised in this study. The inductive approach's proponents assert that it is the ideal approach for social science research as it allows researchers to make diverse interpretations in varying circumstances (Saunders *et al.*, 2016). In addition, when investigating a phenomenon, an inductive technique is considered effective in discovering emerging themes because it adopts a comprehensive view (Wilson, 2014).

Carson *et al.* (2001) advocate that inductive and deductive reasoning be harmonised, especially in interpretive research, because a solely inductive research approach ignores current theory, while a deductive research technique may not create new or relevant theories. The current researcher, on the other hand, disagrees with these standpoints. Existing theories are not ignored when using an inductive method as inductive researchers do not investigate a subject matter until they have a thorough

understanding of it (Saunders *et al.*, 2007). This research takes an inductive approach and builds a conceptual framework based on a thorough literature review, which serves as the foundation for this research. However, this conceptual framework is not to be viewed as a restrictive set of assumptions, in accordance with the interpretive research philosophy of this study (Miles and Huberman, 1994). As a result, this study takes an inductive approach, which is well suited to drawing broad conclusions in uncharted topics like tenant entrepreneurs' perspectives of UBIs while depending on existing literature on business incubation and entrepreneurial learning for direction (Edmondson and McManus, 2007).

3.6. Research Strategy

A research strategy is a comprehensive plan for carrying out a research study as it helps a researcher to design, carry out, and monitor the research study (Johannesson and Perjons, 2014; Remenyi *et al.*, 2003). It is one of the aspects of the research methodology. In any research study, identifying a suitable research strategy is a critical component (Remenyi, *et. al.*, 1998).

Case study, survey, action research, experiment, grounded theory and archival research are some of the key methodologies used in business and management studies (Creswell 2013; Robson, 2002; Saunders *et al.* 2009; Yin, 2003). Although numerous research techniques exist, Yin (2003) and Saunders *et al.* (2009) noted that there are significant overlaps among them, therefore the most essential consideration would be to choose the most favourable strategy for a specific research topic. Below, the fundamental conceptual issues, and the justification behind using the case study as the chosen strategy are discussed.

Saunders *et al.* (2019) assert that the selection of a suitable research strategy should be based on the research questions and objectives, the philosophical foundations, the degree of existing knowledge on the research topic and the availability of time and resources. Taking a different perspective, Yin (2003) suggests that a suitable research strategy be chosen based on: the kind of research question, the degree of influence an investigator has over particular behavioural occurrences, and the degree of attention on current or historical occurrences.

3.6.1. Case Study Research

Case study research strategy is considered appropriate for this study for investigating the UK UBIs. Over the years, the case study strategy has become a popular technique for obtaining information in social science (Denzin and Lincoln, 2008; Trochim, 2000; Gustafsson, 2017). Since there is no simple explanation for what a case study is, defining it is difficult (Gustafsson, 2017). Table 3.1 presents some key definitions of case study:

Table 3-1: Definitions of Case Study Research

Authors	Definitions
Jacobsen and Sandin (2002)	A case study is an in-depth investigation of an individual, a group of people, or a unit with the goal of generalising across multiple units; the focus of a case study is on a particular unit.
Yin (2003, p.13)	A case study is empirical research of a “contemporary phenomenon in its real- life context”, particularly when the boundaries separating the phenomenon and context are not readily visible.
Collis and Hussey (2009, p.74)	A case study is an approach for investigating “a single phenomenon” in a natural context “using a variety of methods” to get in-depth understanding.
Thomas (2011)	A case study is a comprehensive examination of systems that uses one or more methods to examine them.
Cousin (2005)	The case study approach is not intended to analyse cases, but it is a useful tool for defining cases and exploring settings in order to gain a better understanding of the research phenomenon.

The scholars' varying approaches to developing case study research are reflected in the various definitions, which typically reflect the characteristics they emphasise as fundamental to their designs. One of the most commonly recognised advantages of case study is its flexibility, as researchers choose the research topic's limitations (Miles and Huberman, 1994). Case study research can accommodate a variety of research methods and is generally applied when in-depth understanding regarding a phenomenon is required (Gerring, 2007; Yin, 1994). Furthermore, case study research can include both quantitative and qualitative data, enabling the researcher to obtain a diverse set of data for the study (Gerring, 2007; Yin 2003, Yin, 1994).

The current study concurs with Stenhouse (1985, p. 49) that the interview is the primary means of accessing "multiple realities" and adopts Yin's (2003; 2006) approach that a suitable research strategy should be chosen based on: (1) the kind of research question, (2) the degree of influence an investigator has over particular behavioural occurrences, and (3) the degree of attention on current or historical occurrences. Therefore, the case study strategy has been chosen as a suitable strategy as:

- (1) The research questions for the current study are in form of "what" and "how" (i.e., What do incubatees perceive about the services and resources provided by UBIs, how does the shared work environment impact their experience, what challenges they come across during the incubation phase and how can those issues be addressed).
- (2) For this study, the researcher remained an investigator outside the 'case' (university business incubation programmes) and had no control over the events and did not influence the behaviour of research participants (current and former tenant entrepreneurs). Also, the topic under investigation is current and explores views and experiences of tenant entrepreneurs regarding the current university business incubation programmes, and
- (3) the context of the present research is UBI, and the tenant entrepreneurs registered for the incubation programmes, and according to Perren and Ram (2004), case study research is gaining popularity in the small business research community. Furthermore, Chetty (1996) indicated that adopting case study research in an SME or entrepreneurial context results in the discovery of novel

insights that would not have been obtained using a technique like a survey. This was notably relevant and significant for the current study because the extant literature on tenant entrepreneurs' perspective of university business incubation is limited.

This research uses a holistic or single case study design and examines the cases as a whole. According to Yin (2003), a holistic case study is an ideal approach if the study primarily seeks to examine one object (for instance, one individual from a specified group) or a single group (for instance, a group of individuals). Holistic case studies can elaborately describe the existence of research phenomena (Siggelkow, 2007). Using a holistic case study enables the researcher to examine previous theoretical linkages and investigate new ones, resulting in a more thorough investigation (Gustafsson, 2017), and a better grasp of the issue for the researcher (Dyer and Wilkins, 1991). Moreover, implementing multiple case studies can be highly time-consuming and costly (Baxter and Jack, 2008). Therefore, considering the time and budget constraints, the researcher opted for a holistic case study, although multiple case studies and case comparisons may have provided a rich insight into the research phenomenon (Dyer and Wilkins, 1991).

Although case study research is a distinguishing research strategy, like any other research strategy, it is not without criticism and limitations. The academic community has criticised certain characteristics of a case study, such as its flexibility, claiming that it might lead to a lack of rigour in sampling and collection and analysis of data. According to Yin (2003), subjectivity, challenges in making generalisations, lack of rigour, and spending too long and generating a vast amount of data are some of the main criticisms of case study research. In addition, Denscombe (2008) raises concern about its predominantly descriptive nature. The researcher stresses that the importance of the case study strategy should not be disregarded as a consequence of this criticism, having studied its key benefits and limitations in this section.

Due to the nature of the research question under investigation, the grounded theory approach could be the next best option for this study. The grounded theory approach aims to provide an integrated set of ideas that may be used to give a comprehensive

theoretical explanation of the phenomena under investigation, and theory is developed from evidence in grounded theory, which is methodically acquired and examined throughout the research process in an iterative manner (Corbin and Strauss, 1990). Nevertheless, the goal of this study is to explore the perceptions of entrepreneurs towards university incubation programmes, and it is not primarily seeking to develop theory from data but aiming to inductively inquire the research topic and draw conclusions. Consequently, as compared to the case study technique, grounded theory was regarded as less appropriate. The flexibility that the case study strategy provides in terms of data collection and analysis methods, allowing rich qualitative data and comprehensive knowledge of the subject under investigation, (Gerring, 2007; Yin, 2003) was one of the significant factors that overwhelmingly backed its selection for this study.

3.7. Research Design

Yin (2009) defines research design as a ‘road map’ that links empirical data to research questions and, subsequently, to the results and conclusions. According to Myers (2013), with the purpose of connecting empirical evidence with research questions, the researcher chooses on all aspects of the research: philosophical foundations, research method, data collection tools and data analysis techniques.

There are three types of research designs: quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods. Quantitative and qualitative designs can be employed separately or collectively (Saunders *et al.*, 2019). The contrast between qualitative and quantitative research is frequently defined in terms of the use of “words (qualitative) rather than figures (quantitative), or the use of closed- ended questions (quantitative hypotheses) instead of open-ended questions (qualitative interview questions)” (Creswell, 2014, p.32). Quantitative research is a method for studying the association between variables in order to test objective theories; these variables can then be measured using instruments, resulting in numerical data that can be examined using statistical processes, on the other hand qualitative research is a method of exploring and comprehending an individual's or a group's perspective on a social or human phenomenon (Creswell, 2014).

Similarly, mixed methods research involves gathering both quantitative and

qualitative data, combining the two types of data, and employing different designs that may include philosophical assumptions and theoretical frameworks. The primary premise of this method of investigation is that combining qualitative and quantitative methodologies yields a more comprehensive understanding of a research topic than either strategy alone (Creswell, 2014). Nevertheless, given the exploratory nature of the present research topic, the researcher employed a qualitative research design in this research. Figure 3.4 depicts the research plan for the study.

Figure 3-4: Research Design

Source: Researcher

3.7.1. Justifications for using Qualitative Design

A qualitative study, according to Creswell (1998), is a process of understanding based on diverse methodological traditions of inquiry that investigates a social or human problem. The researcher constructs a sophisticated, comprehensive picture, analyses terms, delivers extensive participant's perspectives, and performs the research in a natural setting. Strauss and Corbin (1990, p.11) characterise it as “any type of research that produces findings not arrived at by statistical procedures or other means of quantification. It can refer to research about persons’ lives, lived experiences, behaviours, emotions, and feelings as well as about organisational functioning, social movements, cultural phenomena, and interactions between nations.” According to Rahman (2017), this definition focused on how individuals interpret and experiences events in the world, and, thus, qualitative research is fundamentally linked to a variety of factors. Qualitative research, according to Denzin (2008), creates a deep and comprehensive account of respondents' thoughts, ideas, and perceptions, as well as analyses the interpretations of their actions.

The qualitative technique is primarily concerned with comprehending the meaning of social phenomena and emphasises connections between a broader set of variables in a smaller number of cases, whereas quantitative methodology is involved with seeking to quantify social phenomena as well as gathering and analysing numerical data, with an emphasis on the relationships between a limited number of characteristics over a large number of cases (Antwi and Hamza, 2015). In general, qualitative research methods are particularly valuable for determining the significance and meaning that individuals attach to events (Lincoln and Denzin, 2000). The aim of this study is to explore tenant entrepreneurs’ views and experiences of university incubation programmes.

The researcher agrees with Stake (2000) that when the nature of research questions need exploration, a qualitative technique is recommended. Open-ended questions, such as ‘how’ or ‘what’, can elicit significant and unanticipated replies that can provide a new dimension to the study findings (Bryman and Bell, 2003; Yin, 2003). As understanding incubatees’ perceptions of university business incubation programmes are the aim of this study, the research questions were designed to generate extensive insight into their experiences. Using close-ended questions in a

quantitative survey could undermine the purpose of this study.

Furthermore, the qualitative approach enables the researchers to probe study topics that include participants' feelings, experiences or thinking processes (Sandelowski, 2004), which cannot be effectively captured using quantitative methods (Strauss and Corbin, 1990). The researcher decided to adopt a qualitative approach to explore the perspectives of tenant incubatees (Gerring, 2007; Yin, 2003). In addition, the researcher's involvement as an active participant in the study is highlighted in qualitative approaches (Creswell and Crewell, 2005; Stake, 2000). For this research, the researcher is the primary tool in gathering data as well as interpreting and analysing the data.

In the social sciences, qualitative research has a long history (Myers, 2013) of being utilised to gain a deeper understanding of the phenomenon under investigation by focusing on the experiences and perspectives of individuals (Rynes and Gephart, 2004). There is widespread agreement that qualitative research adds to the richness of academic research in entrepreneurship by providing deep and fresh insights into entrepreneurial occurrences (Javadian, 2020). In contrary to quantitative approaches, qualitative research has the advantage of allowing entrepreneurship researchers to create theories inductively, in direct engagement with contexts, meanings, and processes, in comparison to quantitative methods (Van Burg *et al.*, 2020). Consequently, qualitative research has become increasingly popular in the field of entrepreneurship (Suddaby *et al.*, 2015). Thus, a qualitative research design was considered most appropriate for exploring tenant entrepreneurs' perceptions and experiences of services and resources received during their stay at the university business incubation programmes.

3.8. Data Collection

3.8.1. Sample Composition

In contrast to quantitative research, which frequently involves a broad, randomly chosen sample, qualitative research frequently employs smaller, purposeful samples (Small, 2009). According to Malterud *et al.* (2016), qualitative sample size should be assessed on the basis of the depth and quality of information instead of statistical generalisability. The objective of qualitative research is to seek carefully chosen

participants in order to better comprehend the research subject (Creswell, 2012). The theoretical requirements of the present research led the decision to conduct a deep qualitative research study, which enabled the researcher to delve into significant subjects in great depth (Silverman, 2013).

The purposive sampling technique was chosen to guarantee that participants represented a diverse group of incubatees. This technique allowed the researcher to focus on specific participants for more detailed interviews (Patton, 1990). Purposive sampling includes study participants who have comprehensive and immediate knowledge of the research issue and may discuss and express their opinions on it (Etikan *et al.*, 2016; Patton, 1990). For sample selection, the researcher has devised a precise justification and criterion. The core intent is not to make broad generalisations, but to generate in-depth understanding of the phenomenon under investigation through individuals who have first-hand experience with it (Etikan *et al.*, 2016).

The population of interest for this doctoral thesis are current and recently graduated tenant entrepreneurs from university business incubators in the UK. UBIs are distributed fairly equally across the United Kingdom, and most of the incubators focus primarily on tech start-ups or have no preference in any particular sector (Bone *et al.*, 2017). According to the latest BEIS report by Bone *et al.* (2017), there are around 130 incubators and accelerators organised by UK universities. For this study, the focus is on public funded university incubators in the UK. A review of the archival data of UBIs revealed that the provision of services and resources by UBIs varies from institution to institution. The focus of this study is public funded UBIs that support start-ups during the early stages of their entrepreneurial journey and provide physical space, shared facilities, cohort-based programme, networking opportunities, mentorship, access to funding, access to university resources, business support and training. The researcher acquired a list of operating UBIs in the UK from the Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy's (2017) report⁶, which is

⁶ [Research and analysis overview: Business incubators and accelerators: the national picture - GOV.UK \(www.gov.uk\)](https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/614242/research-and-analysis-overview-business-incubators-and-accelerators-the-national-picture-gov.uk)

most recent and up to date. The next step was to narrow down the list of all UK-based incubators and accelerators to university business incubators. Following the identification of the UBIs, the researcher proceeded to each one's website and analysed the features of their incubation programmes to ensure they matched the selection criteria, as well as archival data to identify tenant entrepreneur profiles. As the primary focus of this study is to explore incubatees' experiences and perspectives of UBIs in the UK, it was essential to purposively recruit the sample of entrepreneurs who could provide in-depth information. Hence, the target population was determined using the following criteria:

- The incubatees had to be part of a public funded UBI that provide physical space, shared facilities, cohort-based programme, networking opportunities, mentorship, access to funding, access to university resources, business support and training.
- The incubatees had to be currently enrolled at a UBI or had recently graduated (within the last two years).
- The incubatees had to be part of the university incubation programme for at least a year at the time of the interview.

Sample sizes in qualitative research are generally small to allow for the extensiveness of case-oriented analysis that is required to this method of inquiry (Field et al., 2006). In addition, due to the time constraints of full-time doctoral studies and the dire circumstances and restrictions imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic, it was deemed practicable that a small number of UBIs should be the focus of effort. The sampling frame consisted of incubatees from eight university business incubators across different regions in the UK that met the study's requirement. Two of the UBIs were based in the southwest of England, two were in the northwest of England, two were in Scotland, one was in the southeast of England and one in Northern Ireland. A total of twenty-four incubatees were invited to participate in the study, with three incubatees chosen from each selected institution. The sample was drawn from a population of incubatees that were tenant entrepreneurs or graduated within last two years from a UK university business incubator that provided physical space, shared facilities, cohort-based programme, networking opportunities, mentorship, access to

funding, access to university resources, business support and training. There were no age or gender restrictions, and they could be from different sectors and working on varied kind of start-ups, namely lifestyle start-ups, small business start-ups, scalable start-ups, buyable start-ups or social start-ups. Entrepreneurs from UBIs from different regions in the UK, as well as diverse start-up types and sectors, were included in the sample to guarantee a fair representation of the total population. The use of a sample frame drawn from different regions of the country and diverse sectors also enabled that tenant entrepreneurs' experiences of establishing a venture in a UBI could be explored in a wider context.

3.8.2 Sample Size and Data Saturation

Appropriate sample sizes in a research study differ depending on whether qualitative or quantitative research design is used (Small, 2009). In qualitative research, the researcher chooses individuals who have first-hand knowledge of the core phenomenon, or the subject matter being investigated (Morse et al., 2002). Choosing an appropriate sample size for qualitative research to attain acceptable research quality is a philosophical and practical conundrum (Sandelowski, 1995; Vasileiou, 2018). Some scholars believe that a minimum sample size of at least twelve be used to achieve data saturation in qualitative research (Braun and Clarke, 2013; Fugard and Potts, 2015; Vasileiou, 2018), while others, such as Baker and Edwards (2012) recommend a sample size of fifty. Hence, it is evident that determining the number of interview participants required to attain adequate study quality is one of the complications of the qualitative research design.

In qualitative research, samples are often small to allow for the intensity and richness of case-oriented analysis that is essential to this method of inquiry (Field *et al.* 2006; Sandelowski, 1996). In this research, considerations were given for data saturation in order to achieve an adequate level of research validity (Guest *et al.*, 2006), and data saturation, not the statistical power analysis, influences the sample size in purposive sampling (Etikan et al., 2016). This absence of inferential statistical analysis, according to Ishak and Bakar (2014), enables the researchers to be more flexible in their approaches to sampling concerns. The efficiency of the qualitative data analysis, as well as the efforts and time spent analysing the interviews, were valued more than the number of interviews by the researcher. Moreover, given the

unfortunate situation caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, the constraints in data collection were unavoidable as the prospective participants were working from home and voluntary participation in a research study was not their top priority. Nevertheless, the researcher managed to conduct fourteen in-depth semi-structured interviews with incubatee entrepreneurs and obtained a rich insight of their experience that was considered sufficient to achieve the research aim and questions.

In order to recruit the participants of the research, a purposive sampling technique within the non-probability sampling method was utilised for this study as it best suits the study requirement. Purposive sampling has the benefit of revealing key themes and concepts in a relatively small number of interviews (Guest et al., 2006).

In their study, Guest *et al.* (2006) conducted 60 interviews, however they reported that was reached after 12 interviews, and key themes appeared only after the first 6 interviews. For the present study, participants were chosen after carefully considering the research objectives, with the hope that each participant will offer distinctive and valuable information to the study (Etikan et al., 2016). To guarantee diversity and richness in the qualitative data acquired, the researcher selected the interview participants from different backgrounds, industries and venture setting experience levels. Purposive sampling allowed the researcher to focus on specific participants for more detailed interviews. As a result, a sample size of fourteen interviews was deemed to be adequate for reliable population inferences and satisfactorily answering the study questions. At the twelfth interview, data saturation was achieved as the same themes were repeating, however, two more interviews were conducted to ensure data saturation.

Moreover, using the case study strategy supports a small sample size as a case study offers a unique way of examining a phenomenon (Yin, 1984). The term 'unique' refers to the fact that only a small geographical area or number of subjects of interest are thoroughly investigated, as case studies look at data at the micro-level, as opposed to quantitative analysis (Zainal, 2007).

3.8.3 Data Collection

According to Smith (2012), data collection tools for a study are determined in accordance with the philosophy that informs the study. Interpretive philosophy, for example, prefers interviews, focus group, observational techniques, and documentary analysis in qualitative studies to examine a range of attitudes rather than their intensity (Bhattacharjee, 2012; Merriam *et al.*, 2016). On the other hand, positivist philosophy commonly applies approaches that offer quantifiable (Creswell, 2014), for instance, survey questionnaires, experimentation (Schiffman and Kanuk, 1997). As this is an interpretive research study, interviews were used for the purpose of data collection.

3.8.3.1 Interviews

According to Ryan *et al.* (2009), “interview is a valuable method of gaining insight into people’s perceptions, understandings and experiences of a given phenomenon and can contribute to in-depth data collection”. In qualitative research, the interview is the most frequent data collecting technique (Jamshed, 2014). The three main categories of research interviews are structured, semi-structured, and unstructured (Gill *et al.*, 2008).

Structured interviews are basically vocally delivered questionnaires in which a set of pre- decided questions are asked with almost no flexibility and no incentive for follow-up questions to replies that require more detail (Saunders *et al.*, 2019). They are quite straightforward and simple to use, thus the convenience of repetition is a major benefit of the structured interview (Robson, 2002). However, it is impossible to include the emergent issues suggested by interviewees due to the pre-determined questions, as this type of interview only allow for restricted participant replies and are thus ineffective when 'depth' is needed (Gill *et al.*, 2008; Robson, 2002).

Unstructured interviews are conducted with little or no organisation and do not reflect any pre-determined beliefs or notions (Brinkmann, 2014). This category is usually employed for addressing a wide topic of interest (Robson, 2004). A significant drawback of this interview type is the length of time required to conduct it as it might take hours which makes it difficult to implement and to engage in. The absence of pre-determined questions can make it challenging for the investigator to

manage it and perplexing for the respondent (Gill *et al.*, 2008).

Semi-structured interviews include a series of main questions that help outline the topics to be examined, but also enable the interviewer or interviewee to deviate in order to delve deeper into a concept or response (Brinkmann, 2014). Unlike structured interviews, these allow flexibility and identification of useful information that may not have been considered relevant by the investigator beforehand (Gill *et al.*, 2008). Enhanced standardisation that adds validity to the data, and also the flexibility to capture evolving opinions on the topic under discussion, are some of the strengths of this interview approach (Brinkmann, 2014; Britten, 1999).

For this research, semi-structured online interviews were identified as the most appropriate option as interview data could provide valuable insight into the research topic. The use of online mediums has become increasingly common over the years (Leinhos, 2019). Phone (or online) interviews provides the researcher more flexibility and accessibility compared to the traditional techniques that require more time and resources to travel and conduct a face-to-face interview (Block and Erskine, 2012). In order to collect the main research data, interviews were conducted virtually. Chapter 4.3.1.3 provides a detailed description of the interview process followed in this research as well as the challenges faced.

However, interviews have few drawbacks as well, for instance, there's the possibility of bias to occur in the interview process, selection of respondents and researcher's influence to impact the interview process (Ryan *et al.*, 2009). Ryan *et al.* (2009) highlight that an interview is more than a 'conversational interaction' between two individuals; it requires good knowledge and expertise on the part of the interviewer. The researcher was aware of these issues and in order to mitigate these limitations, the researcher maintained professional yet reassuring conduct, structured and conducted the interview in a way to establish a rapport with the respondents (Gill *et al.*, 2008), and adhered to the ethical principles (Bryman and Bell, 2007).

3.8.4 Pilot Study

A pilot study is considered an important component in a research study as it not only assists in developing effective questions before executing the main study but also allows the researchers to discover possible issues and flaws in the interview process before interviewing a large number of respondents during the actual study (Kim, 2010; Majid *et al.*, 2017; Yin, 2009). The use of pilot study is becoming more common in qualitative studies (Kim, 2011), as it can help a qualitative researcher gain a better understanding of the research phenomenon and analyse the study's procedures (Jessiman, 2013), before commencing the actual study. In this research, a pilot study was conducted to ensure the data collection instrument designed for the study is fit for its purpose.

In qualitative studies, data is gathered mainly through interviews, which requires researchers to comprehend the phenomenon under investigation from the interviewees' perspective (Merriam, 2015). However, inexperienced researchers may find it challenging to do qualitative research effectively. It is argued that a pilot study can inform and prepare researchers, particularly inexperienced researchers, to address the obstacles that are likely to occur in the actual study (Majid *et al.*, 2017). Accordingly, before carrying out the final interviews with the incubatee entrepreneurs, the researcher conducted a pilot study. The purpose of the pilot study was to evaluate if the questions were appropriate and to gain some preliminary feedback on the effectiveness of the study.

3.8.4.1 Participants for the Pilot Study

For the pilot study, the participants were chosen purposively and depending on their inclination and availability to participate. The researcher requested two UBIs to circulate invitations to current incubatees who had been in the incubation programme for more than one year to participate in the pilot study. The initial request was made in July 2019, and the recruitment process took longer than the researcher had anticipated. The participants were recruited and interviewed over the course of three months (July 2019-October 2019). After several follow up requests, one of the UBIs referred two tenant entrepreneurs who were interested in taking part in the pilot interviews. The following table represents the profile of the participants for the pilot study.

Table 3-2: Profile of the Respondents for Pilot Study

Age	Gender	Education	Ethnicity	Industry Domain	Years of Experience as Entrepreneur	Incubator Joining Stage
27	Male	Bachelor's Degree	White British	Entertainment (Renting & selling innovative products)	4 years	Pre-start-up
25	Female	Bachelor's Degree	White British	Health & beauty	3 years	Pre-start-up

Source: Researcher

3.8.4.2 Pilot Interviews and Changes Made

Both participants were sent a participant information sheet and consent form through email before the commencement of the pilot study. The pilot interviews were scheduled to last for forty minutes each considering the availability and busy schedule of the respondents. A total of two pilot interviews were conducted; one of the interviews was conducted via telephone whilst the other was conducted face-to-face. At the start of each interview, the researcher provided a detailed explanation of the study's goals, and confidentiality of the responses and the rights of the respondents, which took longer than the researcher had anticipated. The pilot interviews lasted between fifty-five minutes and one hour which exceeded the pre-determined schedule due to the additional social conversation and a detailed explanation of the study.

Conducting pilot interviews not only enabled the researcher to make necessary amendments in the interview protocol and modify the research questions but also informed the selection of the most appropriate participants for the actual study. Furthermore, it aided the researcher in gaining experience in conducting in-depth, semi-structured interviews and establishing rapport with the respondents. As both pilot interview sessions had exceeded the specified time, the researcher decided to

send a copy of the interview protocol to the participants for the actual study and include a rather brief explanation of the study's goals, the confidentiality of their responses and the rights of the respondents participating in the main interviews. This introduction was practised and improvised numerous times by the researcher in order to commence the initial interview protocol in a timely and friendly manner. The researcher also decided to increase the interview time frame for the actual study to one hour and thirty minutes. Conducting a pilot study as a part of this research provided a valuable insight into research questions and the following additional topics were added to the final interview guide:

- Previous incubation experience before joining the current UBI programme
- UBI's help in gaining practical work experience during the incubation phase

Apart from adding the above questions, no major changes were required, and the final interview questions were unambiguous and matched with the research objectives. Furthermore, the pilot study did not result in any changes in the data collection instrument. This small-scale pilot study was primarily conducted to determine the effectiveness of the interview questions in achieving the research objectives and to provide the researcher with an insight into the interview process. The pilot study allowed the researcher to gain valuable expertise conducting semi-structured, in-depth interviews as well as to establish rapport with the interviewees. Additionally, the pilot study aided the researcher in learning interviewing techniques and conversation flow. In the light of the findings from the pilot study, the researcher was able to make modifications to the interview questions and effectively plan the interview process before the actual study. The findings of the pilot interviews matched those of the actual study.

3.9 Main Data Collection and Analysis

While the processes of data collection and data analysis were closely intertwined during this stage of the research (Morse *et al.*, 2002; Thorne, 2000), both will be presented in separate sections for clarity. The aim of this study was to explore the perceptions and experiences of entrepreneurs who were part of a university business

incubation programme in the UK. Fourteen online semi-structured interviews were conducted with current and former tenant entrepreneurs at the UK business incubation programmes. A six-step thematic analysis of Braun and Clarke (2006) was used to analyse the interview data. The following sub-sections describe the data collection process, recruitment of the participants, interview process and the stages of thematic analysis.

3.9.1 Main Data Collection Process

This section outlines the process of data collection starting from recruitment of the suitable interviewees to the process of conducting the interviews. Semi-structured online interviews were utilised with each interview lasting between forty-five minutes and one hour and fifteen minutes.

3.9.1.1 Recruitment of Participants

The data collection process initiated the recruitment of the interviewees who met the study's eligibility requirements. The participants were required to be recent graduates or current incubatees at business incubation programmes in the UK that provide office space, coaching and mentoring, access to capital, business support and advice, university support, and a shared work environment. The researcher selected eight university business incubators across different regions in the UK that met the study's requirement and obtained a list of incubatee start-ups from the UBIs websites. Participants required to be either a former incubatee who graduated within the last two years or a current tenant who has been in the incubation programme for at least a year. The researcher then contacted three founding entrepreneurs from each UBI through LinkedIn to invite them to take part in the study. The participants were contacted directly and not through the respective incubators or universities to ensure unbiased and reliable responses. In addition, potential participants were also identified and recruited by attending online pitching and networking events arranged by selected UBIs during the national lockdown caused by the COVID-19 pandemic.

COVID-19 had a dire impact on research plans and activities of doctoral researchers (Alvarez *et al.*, 2021). The recruitment of participants for the study was hampered by the national lockdown, inaccessibility of study sites, low productivity and anxiety

among prospective participants, a shift in working from home and shifted priorities. In addition, the researcher's lack of experience working in the incubation industry made it difficult to recruit participants. Nevertheless, the researcher managed to recruit participants that were able to share a wealth of information about the research subject. Most UBIs transitioned to the online form of operation within a few weeks of the lockdown, and incubator organisers subsequently arranged virtual networking and pitching events. These online gatherings provided an opportunity for the researcher to network with the incubatees and invite them to participate in the study. The researcher attended the virtual events arranged by UBIs and managed to recruit some of the participants for the study. However, not all UBIs hosted virtual networking events, so most of the participants were also invited via LinkedIn.

The prospective participants were initially invited to take part in the study using LinkedIn, as the researcher did not have direct (phone/email) access to them at that stage. Afterwards, an introductory email with the participant information sheet outlining the motivation and purpose of the research and participation consent form was sent to the candidates who consented to participate in the study. Participants were requested to provide a preferred interview date and time according to their availability. Two of the potential participants, one from a UBI in the southeast of England and the other from Northern Ireland, initially expressed willingness in participating in the study but were unable to follow through owing to hectic schedules or personal situations. A total of 14 participants were interviewed for the purpose of this research; interviews were conducted online via Zoom, and prior to interviews, participants were sent a Zoom meeting invite and interview protocol (Appendix) to their email addresses.

3.9.1.2 Interview Guide

The researcher used an interview guide (also known as a topic guide) to formulate and structure the interview. An interview guide is a list of important topics a researcher aims to cover in an interview, along with the subsequent questions under each topic (Newcomer et al., 2015). In semi-structured interviews, the interviewer creates a list of interview topics or basic questions, then adds to it as needs arise throughout the

interview (Newcomer *et al.*, 2015). Producing this guide can assist a researcher to concentrate and organise their thoughts and consequently their questions (Menzies *et al.*, 2016). The interview guide was designed to elicit information about interviewees' experiences and thoughts on their overall incubation experience. The interview structure provided interviewees greater control over the conversation and enabled detailed descriptions by the respondents (Lindlof and Taylor, 2002).

The interview guide for this research was created on the basis of the literature review findings. In addition, pilot interviews also informed the interview guide and resulted in the addition of two new topics mentioned in section 3.8.4.2. Structuring the interviews around the topic guide helped to steer the conversation in a consistent manner while still allowing for important subjects to emerge.

Table 3-3: Interview Guide

Pre-incubator
Any previous industry or entrepreneurial experience
Start-up journey stage (pre-start-up, start-up, early venture)
Reasons for joining the UBI programme
Duration of stay at the incubator
Expectations before joining the UBI
Previous business incubation experience
Experience of Accessing Incubator Services
Infrastructure and shared facilities
Help and advice from incubator manager, mentors, and business advisers
Business support and training provided by the UBI
Technical support provided by the UBI
Funding and grants opportunities and pitch training provided by the UBI
University's involvement and support
Experience in Internal and External Networking Opportunities
Cohort involvement (shared work environment)
Peer networking opportunities
External networking opportunities
Reflection
Personal and professional development
UBI's role in idea and venture development
UBI's role in providing practical work experience
Any problems experienced during the incubation stage
Areas of improvement
Concluding Questions
Anything interviewee would like to add

Source: Researcher

As can be seen in the table above, the interview guide consisted of five key topics i.e., pre-incubator, the experience of accessing incubator services, the experience of internal and external networking opportunities, reflection and concluding questions. Each topic was devised to gain insight into entrepreneurs' perceptions of different aspects of the UBI programme. Moreover, semi-structured interviews allowed the flexibility to add further questions to achieve clarity.

3.9.13 Interview Process

After arranging the interview dates and times, participants were requested to sign and return the consent form prior to the interviews. The interview protocol had contained a detailed explanation of the study's goals, the confidentiality of the responses, and the rights of the respondents. As the participants had already received a copy of the interview protocol, the researcher summarised its contents in order to stay on schedule. The researcher briefly summarised the research purpose, goals and objectives, and ensured the participants that the research was conducted for purely academic purposes to make them feel comfortable (Kvale, 1996). Participants were informed that their participation in the study was completely voluntary and that they could opt-out at any stage, including before, during, or after the interview. This was followed by establishing the ground rules and interview standards, such as the participant's right to terminate the interview at any moment or to decline to answer any question. The respondents were informed that they might be asked additional questions to clarify their responses. The researcher reassured the participants that their responses will be kept confidential and anonymous. The researcher asked the respondents if they had any questions regarding the study or their participation before commencing the interviews.

At the start of every interview, the researcher introduced herself as a research doctorate student at the University of the West of Scotland and requested the respondents to introduce themselves, this was done to establish a good rapport with interviewees (Creswell, 1994). The researcher then requested the participants to allow recording the interview so that the researcher could save time typing the responses manually. Participants were informed that the recording was solely for the purpose of data analysis and to guarantee that the responses were accurately captured and transcribed in order to minimise the interviewer bias (Merriam, 1998; Saunders *et al.*, 2016). The participants were reassured that no one other than the researcher would have access to the interview recordings, and they would be sent a final copy of the transcript for their approval. All interviewees provided their consent to record the interview. As the interview was

conducted through Zoom video call, all interviewees were willing to have their cameras on, except for one interviewee who preferred to keep his camera off due to personal reasons.

Although the majority of the interview questions were asked exactly as stated, the researcher frequently accompanied these questions with open-ended queries to clarify the concepts. The semi-structured nature of the interview allowed the researcher the flexibility to add more questions during the interview and in the interview guide (Adams, 2015). While respondents were answering the open-ended questions, the researcher was taking notes to jot down any questions that arose and asked for clarification after the interviewee's answer to the main question. For instance, one of the participants mentioned his prior experience of a commercial incubator programme which led to an open-ended question "Could you please tell me more about your experience of incubation in a commercial incubator and how was it different from to university incubator?" Similarly, during another interview, the participant mentioned acquiring clients among the tenant entrepreneurs in the cohort. The researcher took note of it and added this question to the interview guide. Before the end of the interview sessions, the participants were asked if they would like to add anything else that was not included in the interview.

Interviews were conducted over a period of six months as finding the participants proved to be more challenging than the researcher had initially anticipated. All of the interviews took place online via Zoom as it was most suitable and convenient for the respondents and also for the researcher given the travel restrictions imposed during the COVID-19 lockdown and budget constraints. Each interview lasted between forty-five minutes and one hour and fifteen minutes. Interview recordings were saved in Microsoft OneDrive immediately after every interview. When needed, an explanation of answers was obtained from the interviewees within two weeks from the interview date. Interview recordings were transcribed soon after every interview and a copy of the transcript was sent to the respondents for their approval, as the respondents were informed during the interview that they would be provided with a copy of the transcript for their approval. The transcripts were sent to the respective participants for verification; however, only two of them responded verifying the transcripts whilst others did not respond despite repeated reminders. Nonetheless, the researcher revisited the recordings to ensure all of the recordings were accurately transcribed.

3.10 Data Analysis

According to Thorne (2000), the tools of data collection, the settings of the research and the targeted findings influence the determination of data analysis methods. In terms of research processes, qualitative content and thematic analysis are commonly acknowledged as transparent and methodical. Data Analysis is arguably the most challenging and critical component of qualitative research (Bogdan and Biklen, 2007). Qualitative research methods produce a large amount of text that must be summarized, explained, and interpreted. Data analysis began with the first interview and continued throughout the study (Marshall and Rossman, 1998). In this research, thematic analysis was conducted to find patterns of meaning in the dataset (interviews). According to Harper and Thompson (2011), this method is best used to investigate how a group perceives a given phenomenon or situation. The thematic analysis was guided by Braun and Clark's (2006) six-stage thematic analysis approach. The researcher followed the steps and progressed from one to the next; however, because the stages are not always sequential (Maguire and Delahunt, 2017), the researcher had to go back and forth between them several times.

3.10.1 Thematic Analysis

There are a number of ways to analyse qualitative data, and the researcher decided to follow the thematic analysis approach proposed by Braun and Clarke (2006) for this research. The thematic analysis approach of Braun and Clarke (2006) was chosen because not only it is one of the highly used approaches in social science but also it provides clear step-by-step guidance for analysing large-scale qualitative data. The six-stage thematic analysis approach of Braun and Clarke's (2006) includes recognising, analysing, and presenting patterns or themes in the qualitative data. Using thematic analysis has a number of benefits (Nowell *et al.*, 2017); for instance, it is a more accessible method of analysis, especially for novice researchers, since it does not necessitate the same level of theoretical and technological expertise as other qualitative approaches (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Also, it is a valuable tool for assessing the viewpoints of respondents of the study, identifying parallels and variations, and discovering unexpected findings (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

Data collection and data analysis occur simultaneously since thematic analysis is an iterative and reflective process that evolves over time and requires a continuous going back and forth

between stages (Nowell *et al.*, 2017). More comprehensive detail of data the six-stage thematic analysis is provided in chapter 4.4 as a clear description of analysis methods is essential to establish the trustworthiness of the qualitative research process (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Nowell *et al.*, 2017).

For the analysis of the data, manual thematic analysis was used. For conducting qualitative analysis, NVivo, a statistical software, is widely used; however, the researcher opted not to utilise NVivo for the analysis process. The goal of adopting NVivo is to make qualitative data analysis more straightforward and thereby to save time (Bezeley, 2007); however, fully learning to operate the software can be time-consuming, this goal, thus, is mostly defeated (Zamawe, 2015). In addition, despite the claim that NVivo does not take over the analysis process from the researcher (McLafferty and Farley, 2006), the NVivo structure may nonetheless define guidelines for certain processes (Zamawe, 2015), such as the software already has *nodes*, signalling to the researcher that the data should be segregated into those nodes. Also, while functions such as queries have been praised for their merits during coding (Walsh, 2003), it might be claimed that such features tend to isolate the researcher from the context of the data (McLafferty and Farley, 2006).

Table 3-4: Stages of Thematic Analysis

Phase	Description of the Process
Step 1: Become acquainted with your data:	Data transcription (if necessary), reading and re-reading the data, and jotting down initial thoughts
Step 2: Initial code generation:	Coding interesting data aspects in a systematic manner across the full data set, and compiling data pertinent to each code
Step 3: Identifying ideas:	Organizing codes into potential themes and collecting all required data for each theme
Step 4: Reviewing themes:	Creating a thematic 'map' of the analysis by checking if the themes operate in relation to the coded extracts (Level 1) and the complete data set (Level 2)
Step 5: Defining and naming themes:	Ongoing analysis to refine the specifics of each theme, and the overall story the analysis tells, generating clear definitions and names for each theme.
Step 6: Producing the report:	The final opportunity for analysis. Selection of vivid, compelling extract examples, the final analysis of selected extracts, relating back of the analysis to the research question and literature, producing a scholarly report of the analysis.

Source: Braun and Clark (2006, p.87)

Getting familiar with the Data: All interview recordings were transcribed immediately after each interview. Since the purpose was to convey the data in a natural, impartial, and accurate manner (Nascimento and Steinbruch, 2019), a naturalised transcription technique was utilised, and the speech was conveyed as it is, without being unduly filtered (Oliver et al, 2005). After listening to the full recording, the researcher played the recording again, paused it after every sentence, and typed the responses in a Microsoft Word document. At

this stage, the researcher did not correct the typing mistakes. Once a rough draft was produced, the researcher listened to the recording again while making amendments to the draft. Any long pauses and non-verbal communication such as respondents' laughter was also noted at this stage. It took several hours to transcribe each interview and the researcher took regular breaks to ensure increased productivity. Participants were assigned a number according to the sequence of the interview (For example, Interviewee 1, Interviewee 2, etc.) to ensure anonymity. The researcher watched the interview recording once and read the transcript a couple of times. While doing so, the researcher jotted down important points that would help in the coding process afterwards (Braun and Clark, 2006).

Initial Code Generation: The next step was to generate the codes. Coding is the process of discovering relevant phenomenon, collecting their instances, and examining them in order to discover similarities, distinctions, and trends (Merriam, 2009). Codes are typically associated with text fragments of various sizes, such as words, phrases, sentences, or even entire paragraphs (Basit, 2003). The researcher attentively reviewed the transcript line by line, manually assigning a code to each chunk of the text. This process was repeated several times (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Some codes were as simple as a few words, whereas other codes were as elaborative as an entire phrase. Appendix (4A) has an example of codes generation from interview number one. In the following are some of the initial codes:

- Inexperienced founder
- Lack of knowledge of business creation process
- The venture creation process made easier
- Idea to brand
- Learning from others

Identifying Ideas: The researcher evaluated and classified the codes in this phase to discover themes (Braun and Clark, 2006). The researcher went back to the transcript multiple times, and some of the codes were renamed. Similar codes were grouped together, and themes started to emerge in the light of the research objectives.

Reviewing Themes: Using a two-level analysis of the codes, this step concentrated on refining the draft themes discovered in step three. The first level was reading over each

theme's codes to see if a consistent pattern had emerged. The researcher proceeded on to the second level of analysis if a consistent pattern was found, however, if codes did not match, the researcher had to decide whether the theme was the culprit or the codes and information for that particular topic. To finish the second-level analysis, the researcher reviewed all of the data to check that the themes were consistent with the data. This also allowed the researcher to see if there was any additional data that required coding (Braun and Clark, 2006).

Defining and Naming Themes: At this stage, the researcher defined the themes according to their main idea and named or renamed some themes. In order to do that, the researcher concentrated on defining each theme, determining its core, and deciding which part of the data and research objectives the theme corresponds to (Braun and Clarke, 2006). For instance, the themes related to entrepreneurs' perceptions towards cohort involvement were peer support and learning, emotional support, acquisition of clients and services within the cohort, and peer rivalry.

Producing the Report: During the final stage of the thematic analysis, the researcher selected quotes or extracts from the interview transcripts to support the themes (Braun and Clarke, 2006). The subsequent section of this chapter presents the findings of the analysis.

3.11 Reliability, Validity, and Research Quality

3.11.1 Reliability and Validity

Although the concepts of reliability and validity are widely associated with positivist paradigm and quantitative research, these are equally relevant in qualitative research and should be retained (Morse et al., 2002). Morse et al. (2002) suggested verification strategies to maintain the reliability and validity of qualitative research. These are outlined in Table 3.5.

Table 3-5: Verification Strategies

Verification Strategies	Utilisation in this study
Methodological coherence	<p>The review of the literature suggested that the business incubation process can be explored better from the perspective of tenant entrepreneurs, hence an interpretive-inductive approach was employed. An inductive approach is well suited to drawing broad conclusions in uncharted topics. Finally, a qualitative research method was employed to gain rich insight into the incubation experience of tenant entrepreneurs. The research questions for this qualitative study start with “what” i.e., what do tenant entrepreneurs perceive about the services, support, and resources provided by the university's business incubation programmes, what do tenant entrepreneurs perceive about the shared work environment provided by the university incubation programmes, what are the challenges or obstacles experienced by tenant entrepreneurs during the incubation phase, what measures can be taken to mitigate the challenges faced by tenant entrepreneurs during the incubation stage, and what steps can be taken by the UK university business incubation industry to enhance the current business incubation programmes? There is congruence b/w RQs and methodological elements. The goal of methodological coherence is to establish that RQs and components of the research method are consistent (Morse <i>et al.</i>, 2002). At each and every stage of this study, steps were taken to ensure methodological coherence.</p>
Adequate sample	<p>Before selecting the sample for this study, the researcher evaluated BI literature and archival data of UBIs in the UK to gain sufficient subject knowledge and to ascertain that the sample was adequate. As a result, it was determined that the sample would include both current and former tenant entrepreneurs from different UBIs in the UK in order to obtain sufficient data on different aspects of the university business incubation programmes. The purposive sampling technique was chosen to guarantee that participants represented a diverse group of incubatees. This technique allowed the researcher to focus on specific participants for more detailed interviews (Patton, 1990), as the core intent is not to make broad generalisations, but to generate in-depth understanding of the phenomenon under investigation through individuals who have first-hand experience with it (Etikan <i>et al.</i>, 2016). In addition, data collection and analysis were closely intertwined, and data saturation was achieved in thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2021), i.e., after the twelfth interview, no new themes or codes surfaced, therefore the researcher performed two more interviews to guarantee no new themes or codes</p>

	emerged.
Collecting and analysing data simultaneously	The researcher used Braun and Clarke's (2006) six step thematic analysis to analyse the qualitative data acquired from semi-structured in-depth interviews with tenant entrepreneurs. The six step data analysis method is practically a repetitive and reflective procedure which changes constantly and requires frequent transitioning across stages. Therefore, the processes of data collection and data analysis were closely intertwined during this stage of the study (Thorne, 2000), and were carried out simultaneously, allowing for mutual interaction between what was known and what was needed to be known (Morse <i>et al.</i> , 2002).
Thinking theoretically	As the data collection and analysis took place concurrently, ideas and concepts arising from data analysis were reconfirmed in new data, and so forth; this resulted in the emergence of new ideas (Morse <i>et al.</i> , 2002), which were then checked in previously acquired data. In short, the researcher ensured that information acquired from the interviews was verified with the next interviews and with the literature as well.
Theory development	In this study, the aspect of theory development that requires contemplation is moving from a "micro perspective of data" to a "macro conceptual understanding" (Morse <i>et al.</i> , 2002, p.18), was fulfilled as the researcher used the conceptual framework (in Chapter 2) as a guide to constructing interview guide which was used to collect data, as well as to guide the discussion of data analysis. The conceptual framework established a relation between university business incubation programme and how it facilitates different approaches to entrepreneurial learning. It guided the inquiry and the data analysis discussion as well.

Source: Modified from Morse et al. (2002)

3.11.2 Research Quality

Given this study aims to explore tenant entrepreneurs' experiences and perspectives of university business incubation programmes, the researcher opted to use an interpretive-inductive approach and qualitative research. This interpretive paradigm aims to explain experiences and phenomena with regards to how the individuals involved see and comprehend their own experiences (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004). Data accuracy, however, is a concern for qualitative researchers (Morse *et al.*, 2002). A research study's quality can be assessed using various standards proposed in the literature.

3.11.21 Establishing Trustworthiness

In fundamental, Guba and Lincoln (1980) replaced reliability and validity in qualitative research with the related idea of trustworthiness, which has four aspects: credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability (Morse *et al.*, 2002). As qualitative research requires the researcher to actively participate in the collection and interpretation of participants' views and responses, it is important to establish trustworthiness in qualitative research (Nowell *et al.*, 2017). By demonstrating trustworthiness investigators can convince themselves and others that their research findings are worthy of consideration (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). In this research, the researcher used Lincoln and Guba's (1985) criteria of credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability to strengthen the trustworthiness of the findings of this study.

3.11.22 Credibility

According to Guba and Lincoln (1989), a study's credibility is assessed when other researchers or readers are exposed to the phenomenon and can identify it. Credibility ensures that there is congruence between participants' viewpoints and the researcher's portrayal of them is referred to as credibility (Tobin and Begley, 2004). To ensure credibility, Lincoln and Guba (1985) offered a number of strategies, including prolonged researcher engagement, consistent observation, data collection triangulation, and researcher triangulation, peer debriefing, and member checking to verify the findings. The researcher reduced challenges to credibility by triangulating the findings and using the procedure of member verification to validate the interview outcomes and interpretations (Birt *et al.*, 2016; Yin, 2003). Participants were provided data (interview transcript) to check for accuracy and relevance to their own experiences. In addition, as the study progressed, and specific chunks of information were available, procedures were taken to cross-check each piece of information with other sources, such as a follow-up interview or further questions for clarification (Lincoln and Guba, 1985).

3.11.23 Transferability

The generalisability of an investigation is referred to as transferability (Nowell *et al.*, 2017). The researcher must provide detailed evidence so that others wishing to apply the findings to their own setting can evaluate their applicability and transferability (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). The researcher provided detailed, extensive descriptions, allowing other researchers to make

transferability determinations.

3.11.24 Dependability

Dependability can be attained by providing a systematic, verifiable, and well-documented research process (Tobin and Begley, 2004), as readers are better equipped to determine the study's dependability when they can analyse the research process (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). To promote dependability, the researcher maintained an audit trail that detailed how data was obtained, categories were developed, and choices were made throughout the investigation.

3.11.25 Confirmability

Confirmability is concerned with ensuring that the researcher's interpretations and findings are clearly drawn from the data, and it requires the researcher to explain how inferences and interpretations were achieved (Tobin and Begley, 2004). Confirmability is attained when credibility, transferability, and dependability are all fulfilled (Guba and Lincoln, 1989). The researcher strived to regulate biasness by continually evaluating data, looking for examples of the occurrence in the literature, acquiring different perspectives, looking for negative examples of the phenomenon, and reviewing and revising data to improve conformability (Strauss and Corbin, 1998).

3.12 Ethical Consideration

This study fully complied with the University of the West of Scotland's (UWS) ethical regulations and guidelines. Before initiating the data collection, the researcher gained approval from UWS's Ethics Committee (Appendix 3). Participants were provided with a participant information sheet (Appendix 1) that contained an overview of the research purpose, the rights of the participants to withdraw or opt-out any time and contact details of the researcher. They were also provided with a participant consent form (Appendix 2) seeking their approval to participate in the study.

During the data collection stage, the attention on ethics is crucial, since it allows participants to openly express their views without concern of being judged (Saunders *et al.*, 2016). The researcher was able to obtain high-quality data in accordance with the research procedure as a result of these ethical considerations. The study complied with the ethical considerations specified by Bryman and Bell (2007):

Voluntary participation and right of withdrawal: Taking part in the study was entirely voluntary, and all interviewees had the option to withdraw at any point during the study. Participants were free to avoid any questions that they did not feel comfortable replying to.

Informed consent: Participants were provided sufficient information on the implications of their participation prior to the interviews. They had complete autonomy to refuse to take part in this study or to leave at any time without offering an explanation. Before taking part in the interview, the participants granted their permission.

Respect and dignity: The dignity of the interviewees was greatly honoured. In the formulation of interview questions discriminatory, or other inappropriate terminology was avoided, and social skills were employed to prevent inducing discomfort to respondents throughout the interview.

Anonymity and confidentiality: Participants' privacy was protected at all times, and their identities were anonymised while reporting the findings, as were the names of their institutions and start-ups. Furthermore, no one other than the researcher had access to interview recordings.

Avoiding harm: Every measure was taken to ensure that participants were not affected during the research process. No participant was physically or psychologically harmed.

Misrepresentation: The researcher ensured that participants views were not misrepresented in the findings. A naturalised transcription technique (Oliver et al, 2005) was used to convey the facts in a natural, impartial, and accurate manner, and the speech was conveyed as is, without being unduly filtered.

Honesty and transparency: The participant information sheet provided participants with a clear understanding of the purpose of the study and their rights as well. They were given additional information upon request, as well as the contact information for the researcher and supervisor. The study was not funded, and there was no financial benefit or deceit involved.

3.13 Summary of the Chapter

This chapter discussed the research design and methodological approach utilised in this study to explore the perceptions of entrepreneurs towards university business incubation programmes in the UK. This chapter was guided by Saunders *et al.* (2009) Research Onion Model. Due to the subjective nature of the phenomenon being investigated, the interpretivist paradigm was considered the most suitable research philosophy. This study utilised an inductive approach as it allows researchers to make diverse interpretations in varying circumstances.

The case study strategy was selected, and the researcher opted for a single or holistic case study design, as a holistic case study is considered an appropriate approach if the study is exploring a single group of individuals. Considering the nature of the study and chosen paradigm, the researcher chose a qualitative method for this study and used semi-structured interviews to collect data. After careful consideration, the researcher decided to utilise Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-stage thematic analysis approach to analyse interview data. The chapter ended with a discussion on research quality and establishing trustworthiness in qualitative research and ethical considerations. The next chapter presents the findings of the data analysis.

4. FINDINGS

4.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the findings of the qualitative data analysis in accordance with the research objectives. The overall purpose of this study was to investigate the perspectives and experiences of entrepreneurs who had taken part in a university business incubation programme in the UK. In order to explore the feelings and perceptions of the entrepreneurs towards the current university business incubation programmes, the interpretivist research philosophy was considered appropriate as it would enable the researcher to explore the phenomenon in a comprehensive manner. The study employed a qualitative method and conducted fourteen semi-structured online interviews with current and former incubatees from six different university business incubators across the UK. Research data was collected using an interview guide comprising of open-ended questions, the interview sample was selected purposively after carefully considering factors such as time, accessibility, and resources, and data was acquired and analysed concurrently. Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-step thematic analysis were used to analyse the interview data.

The findings of the thematic analysis are presented in this chapter, along with corroborating quotes from the participants, to convey a comprehensive picture of incubatees' experiences of UBIs.

4.2 Participants for the Study

In terms of age, gender, education, start-up sector, and experience, the sample featured a diverse range of entrepreneurs from six different university business incubators. Two of the UBIs were based in the southwest of England, two were in the northwest of England and two were in Scotland. Some of the participants are currently undergoing the business incubation process, while others have already graduated. None of the participants had prior enterprise experience, and their primary goal for attending the UBI programme was to obtain the necessary help and advice, as well as to gain access to internal and external funding opportunities. Before joining the UBI, they all had start-up ideas which they had to pitch in front of the interview

panel in order to be accepted into the incubation programme. The table (table 4.1) presents the profile of the respondents interviewed.

Table 4-1: Profile of the Respondents

Participant No.	Age	Gender	Education	Ethnicity	Industry Domain	Years of Experience as Entrepreneur	Incubator Joining Stage	Prior BI Experience
						Current Status		
1	24	Female	Bachelor's Degree	White European	Creative industry-Web design & development	2 years	Pre-start-up	n/a
						Graduated from UBI		
2	27	Male	Bachelor's Degree	White European	Creative industry-Video production service	1.5 year	Pre-start-up	n/a
						Still at UBI		
3	40	Male	Bachelor's Degree	British Asian	Software-AR Games & data analytics	2 years	Pre-start-up	University incubator
						Still at UBI		
4	22	Male	Bachelor's Degree	British Asian	EdTech-Disability Awareness and Team Cohesion Program	2 years	Pre-start-up	n/a
						Still at UBI		
5	32	Male	Bachelor's Degree	British Asian	Food Tech	3 years	Pre-start-up	n/a
						Graduated from UBI		
6	31	Male	Bachelor's Degree	White British	Software development	4 years	Start-up	n/a
						Still at UBI		
7	27	Male	Bachelor's Degree	White Scottish	Sports & fitness	2 years	Start-up	Commercial incubator
						Graduated from UBI		

8	26	Male	Bachelor's Degree	English	PropTech-Property management software	3 years	Pre-start-up	Commercial incubator
						Graduated from UBI		
9	24	Female	Bachelor's Degree	White British	Product Design	1.5 years	Start-up	n/a
						Still at UBI		
10	27	Female	Bachelor's Degree	White European	FinTech	2 years	Start-up	n/a
						Still at UBI		
11	27	Male	Bachelor's Degree	White Scottish	Product design	3 years	Start-up	n/a
						Still at UBI		
12	25	Female	Bachelor's Degree	British African Caribbean	Website development	3 years	Pre-start-up	n/a
						Graduated from UBI		
13	28	Male	Bachelor's Degree	White English	Sales and marketing	4 years	Start-up	Commercial incubator
						Graduated from UBI		
14	27	Female	Master's Degree	British Afro Caribbean	EdTech- Training, education & leadership development	3.5 years	Pre-start-up	n/a
						Graduated from UBI		

4.3 Findings

Whilst keeping the objectives of the study in mind, the themes were classified into five categories, namely advice, guidance and managerial support, access to resources, cohort involvement, challenges, and suggestions. A total of twenty-four themes were identified from the analysis of the data. The categories and identified themes are organised according to the research objectives in Table 4.2.

Table 4-2: Findings of the Research

Objective 1	To explore the views and experiences of tenant entrepreneurs regarding the support and resources provided by UBIs
Category	Advice, guidance and managerial support
Relevant Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simplification and acceleration of new venture creation process • Learning from the experience of managers and advisors enabled entrepreneurs to move forward in the right direction • An efficient incubator manager ensures a productive incubation experience • Entrepreneur's responsibility • UBI is a source of encouragement and motivation • UBI is a source of gaining practical experience
Category	Access to resources
Relevant Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to free or affordable office space provide cost- saving opportunities • Access to investors and external funding opportunities helped in progressing forward in entrepreneurial journey. • Access to university resources provided cost-saving opportunities
Objective 2	To explore the views and experiences of tenant entrepreneurs regarding the shared work environment provided by the UBIs
Category	Cohort involvement
Relevant Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peer learning and support • Learning through social interactions • Acquiring clients and services from within the cohort • Peer rivalry
Objective 3	To identify any challenges that tenant entrepreneurs experience during the incubation process
Category	Challenges
Relevant Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incubator bias • Hidden motives of incubators and external stakeholders • The lack of inclusion • Investors' reluctance to take risks • The lack of industry-specific information • Entrepreneurs' financial struggles during the incubation stage
Objective 4	To explore the suggestions of entrepreneurs on making the current business incubation programmes more effective
Category	Suggestions
Relevant Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industry-specific smaller cohorts • Personalised support for start-ups • Assessment of needs • Financial incentives for entrepreneurs during the research phase • Collaborations between current and former cohorts

Source: Researcher

The section below now details upon each finding identified during the analysis. The findings are organised according to the study objectives, with each sub-section beginning with a brief discussion of the finding in response to the research objective in question, followed by an explanation of the category and themes within each category.

4.3.1 Objective 1: To explore the views and experiences of tenant entrepreneurs regarding the support and resources provided by University Business Incubation programmes

A thematic analysis of the data revealed various entrepreneurs' perceptions towards the university incubation programmes. After carefully reviewing the list of perceptions identified during the analysis, they were categorised into two categories, namely perceptions towards advice, guidance, and mentorships from the incubation programmes, perceptions towards access to resources. Below, perceptions related to each category is described:

4.3.1.1 Advice, guidance, and managerial support

Entrepreneurs in the sample shared their views about advice, guidance, and managerial support they receive whilst participating in university incubation programmes and highlighted that they found it useful as it not only simplified and expedited the new venture creation process but also allowed them to learn from the experience of the incubator managers and advisors.

- **Joining the UBI programme simplified and accelerated the new venture creation process**

All of the interviewees in the sample mentioned that being a part of the incubator programme not only simplified but also accelerated the process of new venture creation. According to the participating entrepreneurs, they were provided with the necessary information required to initiate the venture creation process, and this provision of seemingly complex information in a simplified way helped them significantly.

It saved my time. I would have made lot of mistakes if I was doing this alone. I can definitely say, going to the incubator opened my horizons. I could see far more possibilities. It simplified this myth of doing business as something so complicated and scary and the view that a businessperson should be mature and like 40 years old wearing a suit etc.... (Interviewee 4)

Interviewees mentioned that by joining the incubation programme they were able to receive

practical knowledge about various aspects of doing a business, such as attending a board meeting, writing a press release, pitching a business idea, cash flow sessions, business design sessions, etc. According to them, there are various aspects of creating a new venture that requires practical insight and training to equip inexperienced entrepreneurs with the abilities they need to succeed in the business world. As mentioned by one of the respondents:

I got into the incubator straight after uni. (university), and I studied creative field and had absolutely no idea about taxes or legal requirements of doing a business. Incubator offered a lot of training. There was quite a lot of sessions in different fields and aspects. Telling us about everything from how to pitch a business idea, how to write a press release, how to decide legal structure of the business, quite diverse. They try to touch on everything that would be relevant, and I feel quite confident that I know the things that I didn't know before; things that need to be considered. (Interviewee 12)

Respondents also mentioned receiving practical training related to different aspects of the business during their incubation journey. The incubator provided such training to prepare the nascent entrepreneurs for real-world business situations.

We had this board meeting to kind of train me for board meetings. And we just pretend like they're on my board and you have to run it and its good training. (Interviewee 7)

Young graduates with no prior industry or business experience may find the idea of setting up their own ventures daunting, if not unattainable. However, the essential support and guidance offered by the incubation programmes provided these nascent entrepreneurs with the courage to initiate their entrepreneurial endeavours. They mentioned that getting guidance from the incubator in setting small, easily attainable goals and prioritising tasks helped them move forward in the right direction.

Our business advisor was very structured, and he would help me set milestones not by telling me "You should do this and that", but by discussing it with me. We used to meet our business advisor every 3 weeks or so. With every meeting we'd give her updates on what's happening with the business progress and stuff. We almost had a work plan at the end of every meeting. We'd have like a checklist and list of tasks to do. So, we were always given direction moving forward. We also got help with prioritising that what we should be focusing on like setting milestones. (Interviewee 1)

Interviewees revealed that the business support, advice and guidance they received during the incubation period made them better entrepreneurs and it was a significant aspect of joining the incubation programme. They indicated that coping with the complicated process of starting a new business and the essential procedures it involves could be exhausting and overwhelming especially if entrepreneurs are new to this as must absorb more and more intricate information while processing new information in less time. Being part of the incubator programme and receiving all the support and guidance from business advisers and mentors simplified the whole process for the participating entrepreneurs.

- **Learning from the experience of the managers and advisors enabled entrepreneurs to move forward in the right direction**

Participating entrepreneurs revealed that the support and guidance they received from their respective incubator managers during the incubation process extensively helped them. According to them, they needed the right mentorship, support and advice to move forward in their entrepreneurial journey as they did not have any prior enterprise experience. One of the interviewees in the sample highlighted that the experience manager had was helpful in understanding how to raise a large amount of funding, for example:

He had years of experience in tech start-ups and in terms of raising huge amounts of money with early-stage companies selling them and the whole shebang. So, it's a good person to learn from. (Interviewee 8)

Interviewees indicated that incubator manager's own industry and entrepreneurial experience benefitted them greatly, as they were able to acquire crucial knowledge through them which gave them the confidence to pursue their entrepreneurial dream.

In school (university) there's not quite a lot said about what is it that need to be done to start a business, so you don't necessarily learn this by doing a business degree. By joining incubator, you have people who know what they are talking about and you learn so much from them, and there I was able to see that doing my own business isn't that complicated and it's doable even if I was 22, but I could do my own business. It's not rocket science and of course, the people we had, the experts who gave talks, made it easy. (Interviewee 1)

Some of the interviewees shared contrasting views about receiving advice and mentorships. According to them, mentors have valuable experience and knowledge to share with nascent incubatees, but they are not paid employees of the incubator programmes, and their involvement is voluntary, thus they have their own priorities.

Some mentors and managers are good, and some are not so good. I've had both. So, mentors are

difficult, because often they're volunteers, and they've got other commitments. (Interviewee 3)

Participating entrepreneurs found the advice, support and mentorship provided by the incubator managers and business advisors extremely valuable as they were able to learn from them, and that knowledge helped them in their entrepreneurial endeavours. However, some did not receive much benefit from their mentors because they believed their assigned mentors had other priorities and were not fully committed to their role. Nonetheless, as seen in the sample, participants in general did benefit in one way or another from the available advice support and mentorship whilst participating in the programme.

- **An efficient incubator manager ensures a productive incubation experience**

Many of the interviewees in the sample expressed their views related to incubator managers' roles and their impacts on their incubation journey. Based on the responses of the participants, it appears that the incubator manager had a significant impact on the entrepreneurs' overall experience of the incubation program. As mentioned by one interviewee:

The incubator was okay, it's been a bit topsy turvy, but man, the guy running it, he is a really great guy. And I would say the best thing of that incubator is that specific individual. (Interviewee 11)

According to the respondent, the incubator itself was not ideal in terms of its procedures and resources, however, having an efficient and supportive manager made a significant impact on the respondent's incubation journey. The positive experience of the entrepreneur's incubation journey appears to be strongly influenced by incubator managers, and the absence of such a supportive figure appeared to have caused the opposite effect on the entrepreneur, making the entire incubation process seem meaningless.

So, in all honesty, at first, I thought it was absolutely pointless. I joined the programme, in a time where incubator was sort of in turmoil, and they were changing the manager. (Interviewee 7)

The respondent joined the incubator and due to unstable managerial arrangements, the respondent had a negative impression of the incubation programme and of the incubator itself. This demonstrates that supportive and effective management not only ensured a productive incubation experience for the tenant entrepreneur but also shaped the image of the incubator itself. Besides, ineffective management led to participants forming negative perceptions about the programme entirely.

Some of the interviewees, during their stay at the incubator, developed a strong connection with

the incubator manager which continued even after they exited the incubation program. They mentioned that having a manager as a mentor made a significant impact on their entrepreneurial journey not only during the incubation process but also beyond. Thus, incubator managers who became mentors to the tenant entrepreneurs, and provided their unwavering support and assistance, had a lasting impression on the entrepreneurs.

He (incubator manager) was my mentor? He still is one of my mentors. I could literally call him now. And he would answer. I'd call him at 1am. And he'd pick up the phone. Like I said, I call him every single week, three, four years later, because of how much I value his input on my personal development and the company's progress... (Interviewee 8)

Another respondent shared a similar experience of receiving the remarkable and unwavering support from the incubator manager, which resulted in his personal development and his start-up's development as well.

I still now two years later have a weekly call with him. because of how much I value his input on my personal development and the company's progress. (Interviewee 7)

The impact of incubator managers on the entrepreneurs' incubation journey was tremendous. Interviewees revealed that having a sincere and compassionate manager made a meaningful impact on their incubator experience. Although incubator managers are required to follow the incubator's structure and policies, some influential managers had the inclination and ability to change the incubator's policies and structure to solely serve the interests of the entrepreneurs.

There's a lot of incubators a lot of accelerators out there that are interested in monetising the opportunity, taking equity from start-ups, charging fees, or just progressing their own agenda, whether or not that is a university agenda, or a private company or a corporate company that is getting involved with VC. However, Incubator ABC was different because of the manager, he would fight back against the university and still does with what their agenda is versus what's best for start-ups. (Interviewee 14)

According to interviewee 14, some of the incubators are more focused on “monetising the opportunity” and putting their own interests before the entrepreneurs' interests, but in the above example, the incubator manager would take a stand against such policies and do what is best for the start-ups and the entrepreneurs.

Although most of the respondents in the sample reported a positive experience of the managerial support and mentorship provided by the incubation programmes, not all of them had an ideal experience with mentorship. One of the respondents in the sample stated that he was left without a mentor once his assigned mentor left the programme.

I got a mentor, a business adviser, who, after about a month left. And then there was no more mentors.... and so yeah, that mean, that wasn't ideal. (Interviewee 13)

Interviewees revealed that having a supportive and sincere manager has a strong influence on entrepreneur's journey and personal growth which stays with them even after they graduate from the incubation programme. This demonstrates the importance of an incubator manager in ensuring a positive and effective incubation experience for tenant entrepreneurs, as well as the need of providing such necessary assistance and direction.

- **Entrepreneurs are responsible to fully utilise the support and resources provided by the incubation programmes**

The discussion with participants indicated that although the incubator provides all essential advice, support, guidance and mentorship, it is ultimately the responsibility of the tenant entrepreneurs to fully utilise those resources and opportunities and make the most of their incubation journey. According to interviewees, tenant entrepreneurs can gain valuable experience of the incubation process if they fully engage with others in the incubator and actively take part in the activities and events organised by the incubator.

If you engage with it fully, you get a lot more out of it. Whereas there are a lot of people who weren't engaged weren't coming in weren't going along stuff. And then they'll turn around and be like, (to the incubator manager) you're (incubator manager) not helping me. (Interviewee 12)

Another respondent echoed similar views about the role of the tenant entrepreneurs in efficiently utilising the opportunities and resources provided by the incubator.

You get external speakers and industry experts come and give talks, and you're not going to learn everything you need to know from that talk, it's up to you to then follow up with again. So, it's you know incubators, like provide everything you could need. But then it's up to you to what you, what you're going to do that resource that has been in front of you. So yeah, they give you the range, but I think it's more suited to what you do after and what you're doing in your spare time to follow up. (Interviewee 7)

Interviewees also mentioned that the role of incubator manager was more akin to that of a mentor, and the role of a mentor, in general, requires listening to the mentees' struggles and promote dialogue to help the mentees develop new ideas and views about an issue instead of compelling the mentee to choose a specific course of action. It is the entrepreneur's responsibility to take full advantage of the support provided to them, especially if the mentor or

manager is committed to providing his or her full assistance. As mentioned by an interviewee:

Manager is not gonna run a business for him, or her. He's there to be the right mentor and support, but if that person isn't needing him, then manager's not going to actively be saying, well, use me. The mentorship you receive, it's not about the incubator. It's about the individual. And that mentor you have and how close you are to them, and how much you know how willing they are to give you their time, energy and effort of getting involved in your project. (Interviewee 8)

Both the incubator and the incubatees, according to interviewees, are equally responsible for the incubatees' useful and productive incubation experience. If an incubator provides the essential support and direction, it is the incubatees' responsibility to fully utilise that support and resources in order to have a successful incubation experience.

- **Joining the university incubation programme was a source of encouragement and motivation for entrepreneurs**

Interviewees mentioned that joining the incubation programme proved to be a source of 'encouragement and motivation' for them which gave them the confidence to pursue their entrepreneurial dream.

People believe in my idea and are willing to give me their time to help me with my idea, so I must be onto something. It gives me that boost to go forward. (Interviewee 11)

Interviewees revealed that by providing them with a place at the incubator programme and offering support and resources, the incubator showed confidence in them. They did not have any prior enterprise experience before they joined the programme and, they were not ascertained about the fate of their future venture at that stage. The incubator exhibited trust in their idea, and this gave them the confidence to continue. Respondents also revealed that being in the incubator with all the other entrepreneurs made them feel part of a community and provided them with a sense of belonging. They felt connected to the wider entrepreneurial ecosystem, which instilled optimism in them.

Yeah, I mean, it's more sort of, kind of it gives you that kind of mental boost that, okay, you're part of a hub, you are a part of something bigger. (Interviewee 13)

Another interviewee corroborated similar views:

You feel a buzz a sense of buzz, it pumps you up a bit makes you more energetic it gives you drive.
(Interviewee 1)

Participating interviewees stated that being part of the incubator not only provided them with essential support and resources but also gave them inspiration and motivation to pursue their business idea.

- **Joining the university incubation programme was a source of gaining practical experience**

By joining the program, entrepreneurs gained an opportunity to obtain practical experience by helping their peers, or by gaining access to volunteer projects. This was particularly the case with small business start-ups as those entrepreneurs were readily available to offer their services to other start-ups in the cohort and to external organisations. UBI connected such entrepreneurs with organisations that could benefit from their free services, allowing them to improve their talents and network with potential clients.

We did quite a lot of work for charities and for the businesses inside the incubator (cohort) and this helped us learn a lot. Because we were fresh out of university and we had no studio experience, getting some volunteer work done helped us gain confidence. (Interviewee 1)

Many of the entrepreneurs joined the incubator immediately after completing their graduation and had no prior industry experience. They were able to improve their practical abilities and gain access to potential clients through UBI.

4.3.1.2 Access to resources

During the interviews, the participating entrepreneurs also shared their views regarding access to various resources provided by the incubator such as office space, funding, university resources and access to internal and external networks. Entrepreneurs expressed that provision of different incubator resources such as office space, funding, university resources, mentors and speakers and networking opportunities helped them to save costs and provided numerous opportunities as presented below:

- **Access to office space provided cost-saving opportunities for entrepreneurs**

The provision of free office space was acknowledged by participants as a significant factor in keeping costs down during the early phases of venture creation. As mentioned by some of the respondents:

We had the access to space during our stay and it was very helpful, so we used it for client meeting, for working. It was very good. (Interviewee 1)

It was great free office space for my whole team and saves me like four grand a month for a year, for eighteen months, save me fifty plus grand as a business.... big help when you're trying to set up a start-up from scratch. (Interviewee 8)

Entrepreneurs in the sample highlighted the need for affordable office spaces to work on their start-up ideas, conduct initial research with their team members, and meet potential clients and other stakeholders. UBIs provided them with affordable office space that greatly helped them during the initial years of venture creation.

- **Access to investors and external funding opportunities helped in progressing forward in the entrepreneurial journey**

One of the key reasons why participating entrepreneurs joined the incubation programmes was to gain access to financing options, and they indicated that the incubator's assistance in obtaining funds and grants was highly valuable. As stated by one of the respondents:

So, we actually raised about eighty thousand pounds in grants during the time when we were there, so good significant amount for an early-stage company. And that was with their (incubator's) support. (Interviewee 8)

Incubator programmes, according to the interviewees, not only supplied them with information about grants and funding opportunities but also helped them prepare a pitch to present to investors, for example:

They encouraged us to apply for different grants and also helped us with preparing for pitch and for bid writing. They gave our contacts to the university who were involved in bid writing, to be able to review our bids with us. And that, I would say, certainly helped us to secure those funds. Huge difference at that stage. (Interviewee 10)

Interviewees also mentioned that they found the pitch training provided by the incubator programmes highly valuable. Since the incubators have a thorough understanding and detailed knowledge of the funding criteria, they were able to effectively prepare the entrepreneurs for regional funding and grants competitions. As mentioned by an interviewee:

The thing with all these competitions and the grants is that it's more like a box ticking exercise for the people that are reading them. So, they want to hear certain things because all these companies have their own agendas, so like Scottish Edge, there's a very specific way you need to write a Scottish edge application, you can't just go and say I 've got a great business plan and blah, blah, blah.... You've got to say: 'I've signed up to be fair pay employer, and we'll make sure the sustainability policies are in place'... They want to see all that stuff getting ticked, so the main way that incubators help us is they know the ecosystem, they know what investors want to hear... (Interviewee 7)

Interviewees explained that their primary sources of funding in the early stages – while developing their product or service, are secured through funding competitions and government grants, and incubators prove to be of great help as they have a good understanding of the selection criteria for the funding and grants. They acknowledged that without the support of incubation programmes, they would not be able to generate the funding in such a timely and effective manner.

- **Access to university resources provided cost-saving opportunities**

Interviewees reported that being able to access university resources such as specialised equipment, labs, access to academics and human resources helped them during the incubation process. Some interviewees, due to the nature of their business, needed special equipment, and incubator helped them gain access to university lab or equipment. One interviewee explained how getting access to specialised equipment helped her business during the early stages:

Our business is related to multi-disciplinary design and web development, we required equipment for 3D printing and laser cutting stuff. Through the incubator we could access and use all the university equipment even though we were not university students at the time. We also managed to get access to the university's equipment store. We could rent out camera lenses, photography and video equipment and even sound equipment. So, that helped us. In fact, saved us coz if we had started without any of that, we would not be able to do it. All the equipment we have been using. So much money maybe thousands of pounds. But with the incubator we had the free access. (Interviewee 1)

According to the interviewees, access to special equipment was immensely helpful during the

early stages, as they had to keep the start-up costs to a minimum. Few of the participating interviewees also reported receiving help from the partner universities during the incubation process. They mentioned receiving assistance from the university professors as well as students in a variety of ways.

We even had access to academics and students....in a sense that certain students wanted work experience, and they facilitated that through academics, so we could even get research projects done by students, research in different areas related to our start-up. (Interviewee 4)

Another respondent from a different incubator who was able to access human resources through the partner university shared a similar experience. He explained that, during the incubation process, the incubator's affiliated university was able to support them with specific research initiatives that were not relevant to the entrepreneur's areas of competence.

Law students wanted to do a project so we were like, okay, sweet, can you just review our employment contracts and come back with stuff, stuff like that, you know. I had access to students through the staff and academics that would bring them together, and doing the group work, so definitely got a lot of that. (Interviewee 8)

The support provided by the affiliated university, according to interviewees, aided the success of their new start-ups. However, not all interviewees had the same experience regarding university involvement. As a matter of fact, most of them did not receive any direct help from the university's academic staff. Some interviewees even had a disappointing experience seeking support from academics. One interviewee expressed frustration while answering the question about university involvement in the incubation process:

There's zero involvement. I mean I've got a psychology department, literally a mile away, and literally two hundred yards away, I've got a nursing place where I've contacted the professors to say, 'can you review our work? Can you look at this?' We are not asking you for, you know, two or three days of your time, we are asking for just half an hour or so. But they don't even come back, don't even reply. There is 'that' culture of helping in those institutions and its horrible. (Interviewee 3)

As can be seen above, the interviewees' experiences regarding university involvement and support were inconsistent. While some of them mentioned getting help and assistance from the university, the majority reported the contrary. Most of the associated universities do not appear to be actively involved in directly aiding the tenant entrepreneurs which appears to have negatively influenced the progress of the tenant entrepreneurs.

4.3.2 Objective 2: To explore views and experiences of tenant entrepreneurs regarding the shared work environment

Another important finding that emerged from the qualitative data analysis was ‘cohort involvement’, which reveals views of the participating entrepreneurs about the impact of being a part of a network of entrepreneurs. All of the respondents mentioned several benefits of being part of a network of like-minded entrepreneurs. As a matter of fact, cohort involvement was considered by most of the participating entrepreneurs as the most valuable aspect of being part of a business incubation program. Within the cohort, tenant entrepreneurs were able to learn from one another, provide support and assistance, find clients, and acquire services. Interviewees revealed some disadvantages of cohort involvement as well. Below, findings related to the perceptions of the incubatees towards peer-networking opportunities are presented:

4.3.2.1. Cohort Involvement

Participants shared their views on working in a cohort of entrepreneurs. Being a part of a cohort-based incubation programme is referred to as cohort involvement. As part of the cohort, entrepreneurs worked in a shared environment and utilised shared facilities with other like-minded entrepreneurs who shared the same passion.

- **Peer learning and support**

Peer support and learning in the cohort were frequently cited by interviewees. Tenant entrepreneurs helped and supported one another during their incubation journey in several ways such as learning from each other’s experience, sharing their knowledge and expertise, offering emotional support or simply through social interactions. As mentioned by one entrepreneur:

The main help that you get is just by being in a room with other entrepreneurs. Some that are similar stage. So, some are calling the same stages mean, an idea on a piece of paper, but some have actually, they've got a prototype, or they're actually selling stuff. So, you do learn a lot from other people. And it's just getting all these people together, and to share ideas and to talk to each other. (Interviewee 13)

According to the respondents, being part of a network of entrepreneurs with various backgrounds and abilities substantially helped them during the incubation period because they were able to share ideas and expertise with one another.

The biggest help was networking and learning from other people in there. And I had that in spades because you learn from other people and that journey goes on, the more you can surround yourself with those people that have been there and done all this and learn from them, the better results you're going to get. (Interviewee 9)

Entrepreneurs in the sample frequently stated that they were assisting and supporting their cohort fellows, and vice-versa. Although all the tenant entrepreneurs were at the same stage in their start-up journey, they all had diverse backgrounds, experiences, and expertise, and they were able to help and support one another in different ways. One of the participants shared how he was able to learn 'technical things' from his fellow cohort member:

Some other people had more business experience so they could always advise us on the legal side of the things etc. and some people were creative like us, doing creative stuff or creative background and they were giving us advice on the processes and how they were getting clients. So, I can definitely say that there was peer support happening. We did learn quite a bit from others. Especially from three of them because they were spending lots of time in the space and someone was doing digital things like algorithms, influencer marketing stuff and they were very knowledgeable in stuff like SEO (Search Engine Optimisation) and the technical things that go behind the target advertising, so I learnt a lot from them. (Interviewee 1)

Tenant entrepreneurs not only got technical help and support from their cohort fellows, but they also got plenty of emotional support from one another. The entrepreneurial journey and its challenges are often misunderstood by non-entrepreneurs. Being part of the cohort provided entrepreneurs with the opportunity to share the struggles of their journey with one another when their friends outside the entrepreneurial circle and even family members could not understand them.

When it's really tough, and when other people don't really understand what you're going through, because my parents have no idea what I'm doing. And my friends look at me like you work too hard. Whereas they (other tenant entrepreneurs) actually understand what you're going for in a different way. (Interviewee 6)

Interviewees mentioned that tenant entrepreneurs in the cohort had different abilities and were able to assist their peers accordingly. While some entrepreneurs were able to offer technical help and support, others who had more business knowledge or useful contacts, were able to provide advice and guidance to others. Being part of the cohort also provided them emotional

support during difficult times.

- **Learning through social interactions**

Being a part of the cohort, according to entrepreneurs in the sample, created a social environment that tremendously aided them in feeling like a part of a team and obtaining solutions to their problems through casual chats. For example:

Especially, when we have little chat “how are you, how’s business doing, how did you get to this point? How’re you making progress? What should we look out for when doing things? It helps your start-up a lot. (Interviewee 1)

A big thing is just to socialize and go out and have a drink with the bunch of entrepreneurs, and that's when you actually like learn more. Because people are willing to talk to you, if you're in the hub for the incubator, and everyone's working away. You don't want to ask the person because they are busy doing their stuff. If you go out for a drink in the like, the conversation just flows a lot easier. So, like it's totally just about learning off others is the main benefit of incubator XYZ, it definitely helped. (Interviewee 7)

Due to this social aspect, entrepreneurs’ learning was not limited to the physical boundaries of the incubator, as socialising with the cohort members outside of working hours proved to be immensely helpful to the incubatees. One of the entrepreneurs in the sample explained that they were able to achieve great success through social interactions.

I've created websites, I've even got apps developed, and they've been done with people that I've met through the incubator. But not through the official incubation channel, but just, you know, meeting for a cup of tea or a coffee or something like that. (Interviewee 3)

Thus, the social aspect of the shared working environment provided by the UBI helped entrepreneurs gain new knowledge and skills and seek solutions to their business problems which helped them during the incubation phase.

- **Acquiring clients and services from within the cohort**

Respondents with technical or creative backgrounds (i.e., web development or product development) were able to find their initial clients within the cohort.

For us it was particularly good because we were learning how to create branding those new businesses use, for example, logo etc. So, we actually learned a lot and got our first few clients

from it (cohort). So, it was pretty good. (Interviewee 1)

Similarly, another interviewee from a different incubator mentioned getting company logo and branding services from one of the start-ups in the cohort. Interviewees revealed that start-ups offering services for new ventures such as product designing could frequently find clients within the cohort. Also, non-innovative ventures such as web development, branding and logo design services were likely to easily find clients or customers within the cohort, whereas entrepreneurs with innovative tech start-ups found it difficult to find clients among the cohort.

- **Peer rivalry**

Despite all this support and positivity among the cohort of tenant entrepreneurs, there was a sense of competition and rivalry when it comes to achieving funding and grants, as entrepreneurs compete with one another for the “same pot of funding”. One of the respondents stated as follows:

It all starts off at lovey dovey, you're new to it, you're meant to be pals, you're with each other. But then when it comes to, okay who is going to get the money, nobody wants to help each other, everyone's to go their own way. We help each other, but there's always you know, there is competition. Because at the end of the day, every single person, and that start-up is competing for the same pots of funding. (Interviewee 6)

There are external grants and funding opportunities from various different sources, and not every entrepreneur might be aware of every single opportunity. While entrepreneurs in the cohort had a friendly relationship with one another, when it came to sharing information about funding opportunities, they usually prioritise their own personal ambitions.

There're always people in the incubators, who will keep the cards very close to the chest and once you're in them for a while, you start to see the kind of politics of it going on. So, for example, there was a guy in my cohort who applied for funding from the military because they were giving a lot of money for new designs. He knew my product could be used by the military. He told me the day before the military funding closes and by that time it was too late to apply because you need to have signed up with an advisor like two weeks prior. So, I was like, okay, so you knew that two weeks ago and you didn't tell me. (Interviewee 7)

The respondent further explained the reasons for such rivalry:

Few months back, there were these competitions that Coronavirus challenge and stuff like that. And if everyone's at the same stage, and that's the only funding goal, then the guy to my right,

and the guy to my left, they're both wanting the same pot of money as me. So why am I going to tell them how to do something. (Interviewee 7)

Interviewees revealed complications of being part of the cohort of entrepreneurs in the incubators, and it appears that peer support and involvement comes with a price of conflicts and disputes among the peers, for example:

There are always a lot of product designers in the incubators, and they would often offer their services. It would kind of start off as free advice and if you wanted to continue, they'd say "okay! Pay me coz I need the 3D printing and stuff, which is absolutely fine. This also caused a few issues; I mean there was a girl with us and for her product, a guy from the cohort made a specific part for this girl's product, and she has now made the product and selling it. And he's now saying that I demand to be named on the patent because I helped design that and he's wanting royalties. And she's like No, we are not co-owners just coz you gave me advice. There was no contract in place, so he has no right to ask for royalties. (Interviewee 12)

Despite all of the peer support and help, the intense competition for funding among the tenant entrepreneurs in the same cohort could be clearly seen in the responses of all of the participants, generating a sense of rivalry among the entrepreneurs.

4.3.3 Objective 3: To identify any challenges that entrepreneurs experience whilst participating in university business incubation programmes

A thematic analysis of the interview transcripts revealed numerous challenges entrepreneurs faced whilst participating in the university incubation programmes. The identified key challenges include incubator bias, hidden agendas of the incubator organisers and the stakeholders, investors' lack of willingness to take risks, racial and social discrimination, the lack of access to industry-specific information, and the absence of financial support for entrepreneurs' personal expenses during the incubation period.

4.3.3.1 Challenges

This category refers to difficulties faced by tenant entrepreneurs during their incubation journey. A thematic analysis of the data revealed interesting themes under this category. Below each of the findings is presented in detail:

- **Incubator bias**

During the interviews, some of the participating entrepreneurs mentioned their concerns about incubator's support being biased as some start-ups tend to receive more support than others. One of the participants in the sample highlighted that universities treat start-ups that are started by their home students more favourably and often treat them as 'pet projects'. For example:

They've got their pet projects, unfortunately, and this is not just me, this is actually other people saying to me that, do you notice, so and so was lunching with so and so, and then say, those companies are getting plugged a lot more, because the role of the incubator is to plug (link) the companies, because a lot of it is about opening doors. And actually, they've got a role in signposting people to you and your customers. I think they do that more so for some than others. (Participant 5)

Another entrepreneur corroborated a similar view:

If there are things (start-ups) that have been out of the (affiliated) university, they will already have legs. They've got full support of lectures, you know, they've already got people that are vocal about what those start-ups are doing. However, if you build a start-up, and you've got potential to succeed, you've still got to then establish that potential and get going on that because you're your own mouthpiece. Participant 9)

Participants also highlighted that some incubator programmes are biased towards start-ups that are able to raise funding prior to joining incubator programmes. One of the entrepreneurs in the sample highlighted those start-ups that receive a large amount of funding from private angel investors tend to receive more support from the university incubation programmes. He shared his experience of being able to receive more support from the incubation programme as he was able to secure substantial funding from an angel investor prior to attending the programme.

I think we're probably had quite high calibre coming into it (incubator) in a sense of.., I mean, I don't think anyone else had raised money, let alone sort of 150 grand coming out of uni. (university), I think it's sort of situation, they were like, wrapping their arms around us and saying, YES. I think we probably ended up being one of the ones that got quite a lot more support than others because we were able to raise a large amount of money from a generous private investor. (Participant 8)

During the interviews, nearly all of the participants suggested that if an entrepreneur is a graduate of the home university, they are more likely to be treated favourably. Besides, entrepreneurs that are able to raise higher funding from private investors are also treated more favourably. This indicates that incubation programmes are biased against entrepreneurs that are not known to the university or are unable to raise large private funding, disproportionately affecting them despite having great business ideas. Therefore, incubator bias was identified as one of the key challenges faced by entrepreneurs whilst participating in university business

incubation programmes.

- **Hidden motives of incubators and external stakeholders**

According to interviewees, incubators and their external stakeholders may have their own hidden objectives, such as prioritising their own interests over what is best for the tenant start-ups. A few interviewees indicated that UBIs selection of start-ups is driven by ‘university’s own agenda’ which is to give preference to the student entrepreneurs of the home university over other entrepreneurs, as the incubator was based at and funded by the university.

Launch space Incubator is funded by university XYZ, and university has quotas and targets that need to be filled. (Interviewee 8)

According to the respondents, this made getting a spot at the incubator considerably easier for students from linked universities. All they were required to do was to express their interest in initiating an entrepreneurial activity and they would get priority of the UBI.

It's, it's relatively easy for you if you are alumni. You can come up with an idea and go to your university’s department head and say, hey! I've been researching how to grow flowers quicker using ultraviolet light. And the guy goes, well go to the incubator I’ll have a word with them (incubator). (Interviewee 3)

According to some of the interviewees, this is unfair to non-university start-ups or entrepreneurs because they may lose their fair opportunity of getting a place in the incubator, as UBIs are supposed to promote and foster entrepreneurship by supporting entrepreneurs regardless of their affiliation to the university.

Interviewees on the sample also mentioned ulterior motives of some of the external speakers that were supposed to deliver a talk to the tenant entrepreneurs to help, guide or motivate them during their journey. A respondent shared his own experience of having such an external speaker during his stay at the incubator. A regular external speaker was invited to deliver a talk about securing funding and grants, but she was advertising her company’s own services and trying to convince the entrepreneurs to utilise them.

Well, I mean, you know, some of the cases with speakers, it was also evident that, you know, ABC from XYZ, is going to come in and give you a talk about how you can do this, when half of the talk is just them plugging, using their services if you want to do crowd raising crowdfunding... (Interviewee 3)

According to the interviewees, this demotivated the tenant entrepreneurs, and they could understand the difference between an external speaker who genuinely wanted to help them and those who merely wanted to promote their own services, such as crowd fundraising in the case mentioned above. A similar experience was shared by another respondent from a different incubator where the incubator arranged an external speaker whose hidden motives were to promote his company's own services to the start-ups, for example:

Well, there's a big difference between bringing in external support to really help start-ups versus bring in third party professional services that want to sell into your start-ups. (Interviewee 7)

Interviewees revealed that sometimes incubators and some external stakeholders may have their own concealed objectives and agendas that are not necessarily in the best interests of tenant start-ups. Such conflicts of interest are not beneficial to entrepreneurs, as these institutions are designed to make their journeys easier and more productive. Therefore, hidden motives of incubators and external stakeholders were identified as one of the challenges faced by the entrepreneurs.

- **The lack of inclusion**

Interviewees stated that tenant entrepreneurs endure social and racial discrimination from investors which makes it challenging for them to secure funding. According to the interviewees, there is 'unfairness in the incubation business industry' and that investors are biased against entrepreneurs from less fortunate backgrounds and ethnic minorities.

I've sat in a room with two other founders, and where we've got a product, it works, people are using it, and we're being given: '*how you're going to do this, how you're going to do that*'. And these others that haven't even ticked the box of actually building something, they're still talking about something hypothetical, and they're talking about how they may solve the problem. We've actually built it, we're solving the problem, and we're on that journey. And we'll be dealing with scrutiny, whereas (for) them they (investors) are just sort of like, Yeah! Fine! We like your idea! (Interviewee 5)

An interviewee from the BAME community revealed his personal experience of being subjected to "unfair scrutiny" by investors who exhibited little faith in his product, despite the fact that his product was actually selling while putting their full confidence in another white British tenant entrepreneur's idea, which was merely a concept. He indicated the issue of investors' prejudice against tenant entrepreneurs from less fortunate backgrounds.

Somebody that is white British, and with English Heritage but have grown up on a council estate. They won't necessarily be taken as seriously as somebody who is, who knows how to converse with the higher, with those parts of society. So, when you can't speak their language, or you can't converse with them in their sort of, in the same sort of way that they're speaking, then people may, you know, then they may not take the person as seriously. If you are going in front of a group of investors, and they're going to completely disregard you because of your colour, or social status, there's nothing that those incubation managers or incubators can necessarily do about correcting that. (Interviewee 5)

According to the respondent, UBIs provide extensive training to tenant entrepreneurs before they pitch their ideas to investors, however, UBIs have no control or regulation over whether investors disregard their ideas due to unconscious racial or social bias against them.

One of the respondents from ethnic minorities, who is a solo founder from European background, also highlighted his struggle to fit into the incubation industry due to language or cultural barriers. He did not feel welcomed, and the white British entrepreneurs in the cohort did not seem approachable. He mentioned his struggle to interact and form relationships with white local British cohort members.

The problem is that white British people are not easy to interact with, they are introverts and don't mix with foreigners. And to be successful in this field, you've got formrelationships. And the thing is, if people don't let you in, if people will prejudge you as part of that, then how are you going to move forward? Because the thing is, is that in any field, you've doors have got to be opened for you, or you've got to try and open those doors. But, if people are reluctant to let you in, then then you know, what are you supposed to do, there's very little you can do. (Interviewee 2)

According to the respondents, founders from the BAME community and less privileged backgrounds face unfair scrutiny from investors who have preconceived ideas and unconscious bias against them. Due to this unconscious bias, their ideas are not taken much seriously which makes it difficult for them to secure funding. Therefore, the lack of inclusion was identified as one of the challenges faced by the entrepreneurs during their UBI journey.

- **Investors' reluctance to take risks**

Some of the interviewees in the sample mentioned that both incubators and external investors tend to avoid taking risks by selecting 'safe options', or start-ups that pose minimal risks to investment. According to the participating entrepreneurs, this approach of avoid taking risks is

not ideal for promoting innovation as innovation and entrepreneurship is all about taking risks.

They want to pick safe options. This sector has a very risk averse culture, and that culture, stifles innovation... (Interviewee 10)

According to the interviewees, this “risk-averse” approach of the incubation industry is especially challenging for entrepreneurs who have previously failed, as they get this stigma associated with them which makes it difficult for them to get a second chance. A participating entrepreneur who had failed a start-up previously shared his own experience of having difficulty securing funding afterwards.

... because people (incubator management and investors) think, you know, he's failed, so don't associate stuff with him... (Interviewee 3)

Many interviewees mentioned that the incubation industry tends to avoid taking risks in terms of investing in risky start-up ideas or investing in entrepreneurs who have been unsuccessful in their entrepreneurial endeavours in the past. This has not only discouraged many entrepreneurs but also potentially prevented innovations; therefore, investors reluctance to take risks was identified as one of the key challenges faced by entrepreneurs whilst participating in a UBI.

- **The lack of industry-specific information**

Several interviewees in the sample said that their UBI provided them with very general information that they considered to be of minimal use. According to interviewees, incubators often provide generalised support for all incubatees which includes sessions from external speakers, mentors, and industry experts. When entrepreneurs within a cohort have different needs and different types of start-ups, they do not find this general information useful. This is especially challenging if the incubator supports both small business start-up and a tech start-up, as both ventures have different needs.

I didn't understand how you could put someone that's, you know, designing some more glitter or, you know, trying to start a hairdressing company or something, and that sort of spans with a high growth tech company, and then put into the same programme and think that we're going to have the same needs. (Interviewee 8)

Another interviewee echoed these thoughts and shared a similar experience of attending a session led by an external speaker. The respective UBI was supporting tech only start-ups, but the guest speaker had no experience in the tech sector, which caused frustration and confusion among the entrepreneurs.

I remember this one (speaker) was someone who's selling sandbags for garden, and I was like, that's absolutely fine. You've got a successful business; you sell out a lot of sand. But none of what you're seeing applies to me or to pretty much anyone and here. We were like bored to death and I just did not take anything from it. (Interviewee 7)

According to the participating entrepreneurs, the incubators' generalised information and support for all tenant start-ups, regardless of industry or business type, is of little help to them because they need industry and sector-specific information. Thus, the lack of industry-specific information and guidance was identified as one of the challenges faced by the entrepreneurs.

- **Entrepreneurs' financial struggles during the incubation stage**

Interviewees revealed that the lack of financial support for entrepreneurs' personal expenses during the early years of their journey is one of the main reasons entrepreneurs give up on their entrepreneurial ambition. This is especially the case with start-ups that require extensive research and development (R&D) before they could reach the stage of launching their product or service and monetise it.

It's just very hard to persevere with not getting paid and being in that constant cycle of R&D, to try and get your product to a presentable stage (in order) to get the money. So, the incubators don't give you financial support. So, all they really do is give you the space, give you the time and expertise. But if you're not making money, and you've got rent to pay, then you're not going to continue with your business idea for fairly long. (Interviewee 7)

It's quite tricky and a complicated sort of scenario in terms of just managing budgets while getting things developed, and just progressing with the platform. (Interviewee 11)

The interview data revealed that less innovative ventures that do not require significant research before product development, do not experience such financial struggles during the incubation process, as they are able to sell their product or service during the incubation process.

We were doing product designing and we started doing freelancing and provided services to other businesses in the incubator. (Interviewee 9)

Respondents highlighted the financial struggles entrepreneurs go through during the period of developing their idea or service. As they are not provided financial assistance to cover their personal expenses, it can be challenging to continue their entrepreneurial endeavour. However, entrepreneurs that do not require extensive R&D before launching their product or service,

manage to work as freelancers during the incubation process. Nonetheless, as little financial support is provided to the entrepreneurs whilst participating in UBIs and most entrepreneurs faced financial difficulties, the lack of sufficient financial support was identified as one of the challenges entrepreneurs face whilst participating in UBI programmes.

4.3.4 Objective 4: To explore suggestions of tenant entrepreneurs on making the current business incubation programmes more effective

Participating entrepreneurs identified several areas of improvement in the current business incubation industry and offered a variety of suggestions for enhancing the effectiveness of UBI and BI programmes. They suggested that business incubators should be industry-specific and have small cohorts, UBI should regularly assess the needs of tenant start-ups, they should provide some financial incentive to entrepreneurs to cover their financial expenses during the incubation period, and that they encourage current and former cohorts to collaborate. These suggestions are presented below in detail.

4.3.4.1 Suggestions

This category contains themes related to the key areas of improvement in the current business incubation programmes, as recommended by the participating entrepreneurs. Each of the findings is presented in detail below.

- **Industry-specific incubators and smaller cohorts**

Respondents suggested that business incubators should accommodate small and industry-specific cohorts of entrepreneurs to ensure efficient and industry-specific support for all incubatees.

It's not a one size that fits all... different companies have different needs and demands.
(Interviewee 14)

Some of the respondents had incubation experiences in both general and industry-specific incubators, and they were able to recognise the advantages of participating in industry-specific incubators. According to them, a small cohort, the industry-specific incubator provides effective learning, whereas large cohort, general incubators with structured programmes do not sufficiently cater to the demands of all incubatees.

If I was to be in charge of the incubators in the world, they'd be small cohorts and industry specific. (Interviewee 7)

The big general stuff doesn't work... you can't put all sorts (of start-ups) in one cohort. It should be small and focused on a single industry. (Interviewee 9)

One of the interviewees described his experience with a commercial incubation programme, stating that it is nearly impossible to build relationships with other tenant entrepreneurs in large cohorts because everyone has a separate entry and exit phase, and entrepreneurs come and go.

Incubators want entrepreneurs to network effectively, but the bigger cohort, the less likely that's going to happen because it's too many people and they're changing desks all the time. (Interviewee 7)

According to the participating entrepreneurs, if business incubators accommodate small cohorts of entrepreneurs that offer industry-specific support and information to the tenant start-ups, they will have better chances of successful graduation. General incubators tend to have big cohorts that welcome both small business start-ups and high-tech start-ups. As a result, all incubatee start-ups receive generic help, which is not always appropriate for everyone in the cohort.

- **Personalised support for start-ups**

According to the interviewees, a structured incubator programme is ineffective in meeting the demands of all incubatees during various stages of the incubation process, whereas an unstructured programme has the ability to provide personalised support to the incubatees.

Incubator X had a very defined program, whereas Incubator Y was working out how they were going to run their programme whilst we were with them. And personally, I felt there's a lot more benefit of being almost a guinea pig in programs because you get a lot more attention and the structure of the programme revolves around your needs. (Interviewee 8)

The respondent had stayed at two different incubators at different times, and the first incubator had a well-structured incubation programme that followed a pre-determined process. The second incubator, on the other hand, was newly established and did not have a pre-determined structure, which ensured effective support for all incubatees throughout the incubation programme.

Having structured programme, a scientific help isn't necessary the best approach. (Interviewee 13)

Interviewees suggested that business incubators should not have a pre-determined incubation programme as the incubation journey is dynamic and fast-paced. Therefore, having a pre-defined programme in place during the incubation period may not necessarily meet the demands of all tenant start-ups.

- **Regular assessment of needs**

Several respondents indicated that business incubators should identify the needs of their tenant start-ups on a regular basis and provide support accordingly. This is because a cohort contains a variety of start-ups and entrepreneurs with varying levels of expertise and knowledge, thus the incubator should analyse their needs to ensure that everyone receives appropriate support. Without the assessment of the needs of individual start-ups, it can be difficult to provide personalised support.

Managers and advisers should do analysis on the needs of the company they are going to incubate. Like a doctor examines and diagnoses... incubators should be able to pick from a menu that what the incubatees needs or what's wrong with them. (Interviewee 3)

Another respondent shared similar views regarding the assessment of the needs of tenant start-ups:

I think that there should be more in terms of doing an assessment on what that business needs and how they (incubators) can better fulfil that... (Interviewee 10)

Doing this requirements assessment from the commencement of the incubation process can have various advantages since the incubator can provide tailored support to meet the start-up's needs.

That should be an initial triage by the incubators... so they know what the company needs, but they don't do that. They should do needs assessment. (Interviewee 5)

Participants strongly urged that incubators should be aware of the needs of their tenant incubatees, as only then would they be able to give appropriate support to all incubatees. If they are not aware of the individual needs of the tenant start-ups, they will provide everyone with blanket support that may or may not be beneficial to all start-ups in the cohort. Besides, the needs of the entrepreneurs may change with time, hence it is important to conduct a regular assessment of needs.

- **Financial incentives for entrepreneurs during the research phase**

Interviewees highlighted the financial struggles innovative entrepreneurs go through during the incubation process and suggested that government should provide financial incentives to the entrepreneurs to encourage them to continue their journey. The following respondents discussed not being able to place full focus on their start-ups due to the lack of necessary finance:

We're all kind of like in early 20s and you've been asked to put all your focus and attention into something that you're not getting paid for. For me, I could stay at home, which was amazing because of that locks in any payment and stuff. And but you know, there's other people who are, you know, looking, take high school to study, they need to go work, they need to get a degree get a job. There should be some sort of financial support. (Interviewee 7)

I have seen people drop out of the programme because they can't focus on their project... they got bills to pay, they have to work part-time as well and its all just gets too much. There should be some sort of financial support for entrepreneur's personal expenses during the R&D. (Interviewee 10)

Interviewees revealed the financial struggles innovative entrepreneurs face during the lengthy research and development process. They are unable to monetise their idea or product until it reaches a marketable stage, which might take several months or even years. If entrepreneurs are offered financial assistance for personal expenses during the product development stage, they will be able to focus entirely on their project and may even be able to accomplish it swiftly without having to have a distraction from a part-time job to make ends meet.

- **Collaborations between current and former cohorts**

Interviewees suggested that opportunities should be provided to the current cohort of incubatees to collaborate with alumni cohorts who have successfully graduated from the incubator and are on early-stage or growth stage of their start-ups. They also advised that entrepreneurs within the same cohorts should be encouraged to 'co-create'.

I feel like it's a missing opportunity- in a business incubator, you have a lot of... a large number of entrepreneurs who are all trying to come up with something. Chances are that a lot of these ideas are compatible and supportive of each other, and I'd have liked to see more of a proper effort being made to coordinate, to get those people to work together.... if you can encourage people inside the incubator to co-create, I feel that can add a lot of value. I mean two start-ups being partners and supporting each other. (Interviewee 1)

Entrepreneurs who have successfully completed the incubation programme should be encouraged to work with current cohorts of entrepreneurs because they are both at various phases in their entrepreneurial journeys and can benefit from each other's expertise and experience. Entrepreneurs in the same cohort should also be encouraged to co-design and co-create products or services, as this can foster innovation.

4.4 Summary of the Chapter

The views and experiences of tenant entrepreneurs regarding the university incubation programmes were explored using semi-structured online interviews. A thematic analysis of the data revealed that none of the participating entrepreneurs in the sample had previous business experience, and their main motivation for joining the UBI programme was to acquire the right support and advice and to get access to internal and external financial resources. They revealed that being part of the UBI is essential to get external funding and grants as incubator backed start-ups are seen as reliable and legitimate by external investors. Joining the UBI was a source of learning and gaining new skills which helped them in the new venture creation process. The resources and guidance provided by the incubator, and the university resources greatly helped the entrepreneurs in the new venture creation process. However, some of the respondents mentioned not receiving much support from the university academics or staff.

Many of the participating entrepreneurs believed that joining the incubator programme simplified and accelerated the complicated process of new venture creation. They revealed that incubators' connections with industry experts and experienced professionals were a source of acquiring practical knowledge for them. They also stated that incubator management has a significant impact on the incubation process. Furthermore, the incubator provided a shared working environment and a chance for entrepreneurs to network with other like-minded individuals, and respondents reported receiving peer support and learning from the cohort. They even received technical help from their cohort fellows. Most of the entrepreneurs were able to find clients and services within the cohort. While entrepreneurs actively helped and supported one another, there was a sense of competition and peer rivalry as well when it came down to funding competitions. Incubators were a source of inspiration and motivation to the entrepreneurs. They felt like being part of a community that encouraged them during their entrepreneurial journey. Few of the respondents had joined a commercial incubator prior to joining the university incubator, and they provided a good insight into the primary differences between both types of business incubators. Interviewees mentioned the benefits of being part of a small cohort in an industry-specific incubator and the challenges of being in a big cohort.

While entrepreneurs greatly benefitted by participating in the incubator programme, they also revealed few shortcomings, such as unconscious bias, incubator's preference to university start-ups over other start-ups, the risk-averse culture of the incubator industry, structured programmes and generalised information in the incubators, and entrepreneurs financial struggle during the incubation process. They suggested that incubators should be small cohorts and industry-specific. They also lay emphasis on the needs' assessment of the tenant cohorts to ensure they get the support they require. Besides, they also suggested financial incentives for the entrepreneurs for their personal expenses during the incubation process.

5. DISCUSSIONS OF THE FINDINGS

5.1 Introduction

This doctoral research was carried out to explore the views and experiences of graduated and current tenant entrepreneurs towards the university business incubation programmes in the UK. This study followed the interpretivist research philosophy and utilised qualitative semi-structured interviews for collecting the primary research data. The findings of the analysis of the semi-structured interviews were reported in the previous chapter. This chapter now seeks to discuss the findings of this research by locating them into the broader context and highlighting their contributions to the body of knowledge as well as the professional practice. In order to discuss the findings of this research in a systematic manner and thereby to answer the research objectives, the findings in this chapter are discussed in the context of the research objectives outlined in chapter one of this thesis. Firstly, findings related to the experiences of the entrepreneurs regarding the services, resources and shared work environment provided by the UBIs are discussed, which is followed by a discussion on challenges faced by the entrepreneurs whilst participating in UBI programmes. Finally, suggestions made by entrepreneurs for improving the UBI programmes are discussed and evaluated.

5.2 Objective 1: To explore the views and experiences of tenant entrepreneurs regarding the support and resources provided by university business incubation programmes.

The first research objective was formulated to explore tenant entrepreneurs' experiences regarding the effectiveness of the managerial support, mentorship, advice and guidance, and the resources provided by the university business incubation programmes. Previous studies (such as Almeida et al, 2021; Bacalan et al. 2019; Breznitz and Zhang 2019; Khalid *et al.*, 2017; Lasrado *et al.* 2016; Scillitoe and Chakrabarti, 2010; Soetanto and Jack 2016; Wann *et al.* 2017) have primarily focused on assessing and describing the success of business incubators in terms of tangible or quantifiable metrics such as start-up performance, profitability, survival, etc., however, the soft or intangible metrics of success, such as experience and

learning of tenant entrepreneur, is potentially just as essential in the development of entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurs were asked to shed light on their experiences of getting managerial support, using incubator services and resources, and how it assisted them during their incubation journey. As identified by this research, generally, participants of this research had a positive experience whilst participating in UBIs. UBIs were perceived to have helped the entrepreneurs by simplifying and accelerating the new venture creation process, allowing them to learn from the experience of the managers and advisors, ensuring productive incubation experience, being a source of encouragement and motivation, as well as providing opportunities for gaining practical experiences. Besides, UBI programmes provided entrepreneurs with free or affordable workspace whilst providing access to university resources and external funding opportunities. Figure 5.1 graphically presents the findings of this research objective and the findings that emerged from the participants' responses are discussed in the sub-sections.

Figure 5-1: Tenant entrepreneurs' views and perspectives regarding the support and resources provided by UBIs

Source: Researcher

5.2.1 Simplification and acceleration of new venture creation process

According to the findings, participants in this study had a generally positive experience when participating in UBIs. UBIs were perceived to have helped the entrepreneurs by simplifying and accelerating the new venture creation process. The support and guidance they received during the incubation process were seen as quite valuable by the entrepreneurs in the sample, as it assisted them in becoming more accomplished entrepreneurs. The findings of this research are consistent with previous studies (i.e., Al-Mubarak and Busler, 2013; McAdam and Marlow, 2007; Zhang, *et al.*, 2016) in demonstrating training, guidance, and assistance provided by managers and business advisors can be tremendously valuable to the new entrepreneurs. This is mainly because the early stages of new venture creation are fraught with uncertainty (LeBrasseur, *et al.*, 2003; Van de Ven and Engleman, 2004) and one of the reasons for the failure of nascent and small enterprises is entrepreneurs' lack of experience and shortage of management skills (Allen and Rahman, 1985), especially in tech start-ups entrepreneurs typically have specialized knowledge but lack broad managerial abilities (Lyons, 2000). Thus, training and support delivered through UBIs can be a way for teaching managerial abilities to new entrepreneurs, which was observed in the responses of the participants of this research.

Participating entrepreneurs in this study did not have previous enterprise experience and most of them joined the incubation programme immediately after completing their higher education. Dealing with the complicated process of starting a new business and the essential procedures it involves could be exhausting and overwhelming (Haugh, 2007; Reynolds and Curtin, 2008), especially if entrepreneurs are new to this. Several studies have identified entrepreneur's experience, and the managerial abilities and business knowledge that come with it, as a critical component of a new venture's success (i.e., Huang *et al.*, 2012; Nikolaeva, 2007), while the absence of experience and business management skills have been widely reported as a reason for new venture's demise (i.e., Allen and Rahman, 1985; Cardon *et al.*, 2011; Gerber, 2001).

The main purpose of business incubators is to stimulate and promote entrepreneurship by providing crucial support and resources to nascent entrepreneurs (Dee *et al.*, 2015; NBIA, 2014), and incubation programmes are designed to provide tenant entrepreneurs with a variety of business services and training (i.e., financial,

legal, and marketing) that they would not be able to access as efficiently without the assistance of the incubation programme (Stokan *et al.*, 2015). This targeted support is intended to compensate for the absence of managerial skills and experience that are essential for a start-up's success. The findings of this study in the context of the UK university business incubation are consistent with the findings of previous studies and indicates that the guidance and assistance provided by the incubation programme helped these nascent entrepreneurs absorb more and more intricate information while processing new information in less time.

5.2.2 Learning from the experience of managers and advisers enabled entrepreneurs to move forward in the right direction

This research identified that, by joining the incubation programme, nascent entrepreneurs in the sample were able to develop business skills, as previously also noted by Nguyen-Duc *et al.* (2020), which not only abridged the complicated process of new venture creation, but also ramped it up, allowing the entrepreneurs to move forward in their entrepreneurial journey, which is similar to findings of Al- Mubarak and Busler (2013) and Zhang, *et al.* (2016). Joining the programme and meeting with the assigned business advisors established a sense of accountability in the entrepreneurs, which helped them continue to move in the right direction, which is similar to Mattushek's (2020) findings. Furthermore, founders of small business start-ups or ventures of less innovative nature particularly found the business training and guidance useful as their start-ups did not require extensive research for product design and development, and with the essential support, guidance and resources provided by the incubation programme, they were able to set up a venture within a year of incubation. In the case of innovative start-ups, advice and support from managers, mentors and industry experts helped the entrepreneurs develop their ideas further (Nguyen-Duc *et al.*, 2020).

Numerous previous studies have emphasised the importance of the role of mentors in business incubation programmes (Haines, 2016; Tripathi and Oivo, 2020; Tripathi *et al.*, 2019), their role is especially significant for the university incubation programmes because, while university academics and staff have a strong theoretical understanding of entrepreneurship, they lack practical business experience, which a mentor can provide. The present research contradicts previous findings and offers a

different perspective on the role of mentors in BIs, revealing that not all entrepreneurs who participated in UBI were able to benefit from the mentorship they received. The role of the mentors is voluntary in the incubation programmes, particularly in the context of the UK UBIs, and they had their own busy schedules and priorities which prevented them from completely dedicating their time and attention to the development of mentees. However, the support offered by incubator managers and business advisers compensated for this shortcoming. Therefore, the findings of this study make contributions by adding new insights to the literature and indicating that having a mentor from an industry not necessarily provides incubatees with practical learnings; rather it depends on the quality of the mentorship they receive. In the case of non-innovative start-ups, business advisers offered support and mentorship which enabled them to grasp various aspects of enterprise more clearly and establish clear strategic plans. The role of mentors is especially significant for tech-start-ups as they require guidance on shaping their innovative ideas (Nguyen-Duc *et al.*, 2020). This study's findings indicate that managers took on the role of mentors, guiding and supporting tech start-up founders by signposting them to the desired support and linking them to industry experts. This support and direction helped entrepreneurs save time by enabling them to acquire what or who they needed when they needed it.

5.2.3 An efficient incubator manager ensures a productive incubation experience

Findings of this study suggest that managerial support is a unique and integral aspect of business incubation programmes as identified by previous studies (such as Autio and Klofsten, 1998; Bøllingtoft and Ulhøi, 2005; Kakabadse *et al.*, 2020; Rice, 2002) since it provides tenant entrepreneurs with the opportunity to learn valuable knowledge from the experienced managers. Indeed, the incubator manager has been identified as a vital success factor in business incubation by numerous researchers (Allen and Bazan, 1990; Duff, 2000; Hackett and Dilts, 2004a, 2008; Lalkaka, 2002; Theodorakopoulos *et al.*, 2014). The findings of the present study confirm the existing literature and highlight the significance of the role of incubator managers, with all respondents citing efficient and supportive management as the crucial factor determining the success and effectiveness of a business incubation programme. Participants were assisted by incubator managers and advisors who had years of experience and were able to learn from their experience which aided them during the early stages of new venture creation. There was some overlap as well, with the

managers also acting as a mentor or business advisor in some instances.

This study's findings reveal that the incubator manager is not only a critical success factor for tenant start-ups, but also has a substantial impact on the entrepreneurs' overall experience of the incubation programme. Respondents' perceptions of the incubator programs' effectiveness were based on their interactions with the incubator manager which supports the findings of Scillitoe and Chakrabarti (2010). If they had a good connection with the manager, it compensated for the incubation programmes' inadequacies, whereas the lack of absence of a supporting managerial figure cast a negative light on the overall programme. Entrepreneurs' strong bonding with the managers was a result of managers' consistent support as some managers went above and beyond to assist the incubatees, and take decisions in incubatees' favour, even if that meant going against the policies of the incubator and the sponsor institution. It appears that assisting tenant start-ups was not only a job for those managers, but also a passion, as they seemed to take ownership of their role, and their assistance was not limited to the incubation phase, but they also provided advice and guidance after the entrepreneur graduated from the programme. Hence, this study highlights that a dedicated manager is crucial not only for the success of tenant entrepreneurs but also for the success and effectiveness of the incubator itself. Furthermore, findings of this study also demonstrate that management support is attributed to the manager's personal characteristics rather than the institution, which is an essential aspect to consider when selecting an incubator manager. These findings make a significant contribution to the literature by reaffirming the importance of mentorship and coaching on the success of a start-up.

5.2.4 Entrepreneurs' Responsibility

Responses from the participants in this study revealed that the tenant entrepreneurs are responsible for their own independent learning, and the incubation programme merely facilitated the process, which supports the findings of Guo *et al.* (2016). Although the incubator provides important support, guidance and opportunities for the entrepreneurs to enhance their learning, it is the ultimate responsibility of the incubatees to take advantage of those opportunities – also noted by Rice (2002) – because the role of the incubator manager, as seen in the sample, was more akin to that of a mentor, and a mentor's duty is listening to the mentee's struggles and encouraging dialogue to help the mentee develop new ideas and perspectives

regarding an issue, instead of forcing the mentee to adopt a specific course of action (Burke, 1984), or teaching the mentee. Incubation programmes provide various opportunities, events, training sessions, etc. so the entrepreneurs can enhance their learning and expand their network. It is the responsibility of the tenant entrepreneurs to fully engage and utilise those opportunities and improve their entrepreneurial knowledge. The respondents who were actively engaging and participating in cohort activities made useful connections and acquired useful knowledge that helped them during their journey. A study conducted by Motoyama and Knowlton (2017) reported the same findings that entrepreneurs who were more active in the cohort made useful business links. However, not all UBIs in the sample made participation at such events, and training sessions mandatory for incubatees, resulting in the majority of the entrepreneurs not attending those events. In the end, this had a negative impact on their learning. These findings suggest that entrepreneurs who do not take the initiative to improve themselves or who do not actively participate in UBI programmes are unlikely to benefit greatly from the training and development opportunities provided by UBIs. These findings make a contribution to the professional practice by suggesting UBI should not only be focusing on providing mentorship and guidance to the participating entrepreneurs rather they should also ensure that entrepreneurs are actively engaging throughout the process.

5.2.5 Source of encouragement and motivation

Apart from providing support, guidance, and business training, as revealed by this investigation, another essential feature of joining the incubator was that it provided a source of encouragement and motivation for the tenant entrepreneurs. This corroborates with the findings of Stenholm and Nielsen's (2019) investigation which identified that the support and funding provided to the entrepreneurs was a source of igniting their entrepreneurial passion. The entrepreneurial journey is frequently described as emotionally intense (Cope, 2005; Cope and Watts, 2000; Lackéus and Middleton, 2011), which means entrepreneurs require encouragement and inspiration to continue their entrepreneurial pursuit. The study's findings indicate that UBIs play a vital role in supporting entrepreneurship not only by providing support and resources but also by instilling a sense of encouragement in entrepreneurs by demonstrating confidence in their entrepreneurial idea.

Additionally, as part of the incubation programme, the entrepreneurs were connected to the wider entrepreneurial ecosystem (Lewis *et al.*, 2011), which made them feel part of a community and boosted their morale. Several studies indicate that universities play an important role in nurturing and promoting entrepreneurship and innovation (i.e., Kolympiris and Klein 2017; Stal *et al.* 2016; Wonglimpiyarat 2014), and the present research supports these findings. Entrepreneurs that have taken part in UBIs have found the sponsor institutions to be tremendously encouraging, supportive, and accepting. They not only encouraged the respondents to join the programme but also provided entrepreneurs with the opportunity to turn their business ideas into reality by putting their faith in entrepreneurs' abilities. These individuals probably would not have pursued the entrepreneurial path if it had not been for that encouragement and support.

5.2.6 Source of getting practical experience

According to the findings of this study, the majority of incubatees join university incubation programmes right after graduation and have no prior industrial or entrepreneurial experience. Several researchers have highlighted an entrepreneur's experience, as well as the managerial abilities and business knowledge that come with it, as an important determinant of a new venture's success (i.e., Huang *et al.*, 2012; Nikolaeva, 2007), whereas the lack of experience and business management skills have been widely reported as a cause of new venture failure (i.e., Allen and Rahman, 1985; Cardon *et al.*, 2011; Gerber, 2001). The primary goal of business incubation programmes organised by universities is to encourage and develop entrepreneurship by offering vital support and resources to aspiring entrepreneurs (Dee *et al.*, 2015; NBIA, 2014).

Findings of this study indicate that tenant entrepreneurs received valuable practical insight and essential business training on various aspects of starting and managing a start-up which prepared them to deal with real-world business scenarios, such as dealing with the investors, conducting board meetings, writing a press release, and taking strategic business decisions. Cohen (2013) investigated the role of accelerator programmes on expediting tenant enterprises' learning and suggested that accelerator programmes can indeed help to speedily prepare entrepreneurs to face the real world and succeed. The purpose of both accelerators and incubators is to encourage innovation and

entrepreneurship by providing tenant entrepreneurs with the appropriate assistance and resources (Dee *et al.*, 2015). Participants in the current study stated that university incubation programmes provided them with appropriate training that prepared them for real-world business settings. This training increased their self-assurance and benefited them in the early stages of their entrepreneurial journey. The findings of this research, therefore, are consistent with the existing literature and reaffirm the importance of incubation programmes as a tool for preparing entrepreneurs to succeed, thus contributing to the body of knowledge by making the area of investigation further strong.

5.2.7 Access to free or affordable office space and funding opportunities provided cost saving opportunities for entrepreneurs

UBIs provide a range of resources to tenant entrepreneurs, such as office space, shared facilities, funding and grant opportunities, access to internal and external networks, access to university resources (Nicholls-Nixon *et al.*, 2018), and generate learning opportunities and situations for them (Harper-Anderson and Lewis, 2018). Participants in the present study indicated that by joining the programme they greatly benefitted from these resources and opportunities provided by the incubation programmes during the early stages, and it helped them progress in their journey. Several studies have identified business incubators as a means to address the issues of newness and smallness that start-ups frequently experience as they lack the resources needed to handle critical challenges and their potential customers may regard them as illegitimate (i.e., Aldrich and Auster, 1986; Bennett *et al.*, 2017; Bøllingtoft and Ulhøi, 2005; Mian, 1997; Stokan *et al.*, 2015).

Findings of the present research indicate that the UBIs provided entrepreneurs with not only a cost-saving opportunity during the early stages of their enterprise creation but also a professional work address that increased their credibility. Prior studies also suggested that such small assistance can be significant in determining the survival of a start-up (i.e., Meckel, 2014; Todorovic and Moenter, 2010; Zhang and Sonobe 2011). This is because, small and nascent ventures find it difficult to obtain external financing due to their high risk of failure (Hottenrott *et al.*, 2016). Most of the respondents reported that they joined the UBI to legitimise their business idea in the eyes of the investors and that it not only verified their idea but also guided them through the process of obtaining funds and grants, as UBIs have a thorough

understanding of funding criteria of the local funding organisations; Shih and Aaboen (2019) suggested that incubators act as a mediator between start-ups and the funding organisations which is why UBIs not only have information about funding opportunities and competitions but also have a comprehensive understanding of the selection criteria of funding organisations and grants. Therefore, the outcomes of this study show that business incubators may considerably assist tenant entrepreneurs in reducing the risks associated with new venture creation, such as liability of newness and smallness.

5.2.8 Access to university resources provide cost saving opportunities

Incubator's affiliation with a university allows the tenant entrepreneurs access to the university's resources and facilities such as a network of alumni, academic resources, lab and equipment, etc. (Dahms and Kingkaew, 2016; Harper-Anderson and Lewis, 2018). Findings of this study indicate that by joining university business incubation programme, the incubatees were able to access university resources such as specialised equipment, lab and human resources which helped them a great deal during their incubation journey. However, tenant entrepreneurs in this study expressed mixed views regarding university academics involvement, and it appears that most institutions were not actively engaging with the entrepreneurial activities, which caused frustration among the entrepreneurs and delays in product or service development.

Several studies have suggested the benefits of faculty involvement in the start-up process as they can provide specialised scientific knowledge in the areas of product creation and enterprise innovation (Breznitz and Zhang, 2019; Mosey and Wright, 2007; Wright *et al.*, 2017). It was observed in the sample that compared to non-innovative start-ups, the innovative tech start-ups require university assistance in terms of support from academics during the research and development phase. Non-innovative start-ups, on the other hand, found access to specialised equipment such as studio equipment to be tremendously helpful because it saved them a significant amount of money. Given the low funding in the early stages, they would not have been able to rent or buy the required instruments if they did not have access to university equipment. Therefore, findings of this study indicate that the incubator's affiliation with the university benefitted them hugely.

In summary, the managerial support and guidance, and the resources provided by UBIs aided the incubatees to cope with the challenges of starting a new venture and enabled them to transform their start-up idea into a company. As new entrepreneurs have no prior enterprise experience and little practical knowledge regarding the industry they are working in, coaching and mentorship programmes provided by managers and industry experts helped them to have a better understanding of how businesses function in the real world as well as to understand possible challenges start-ups may face. In general, incubator programmes are highly effective in terms of reducing start-up failure rates and it is important to promote these programmes so that entrepreneurs are well-prepared prior to entering the industry, and resources are not wasted. The findings of this research are consistent with the findings of the prior studies and make contributions to the body of knowledge by making the area of study further strong.

5.3 Objective 2: To explore views and experiences of tenant entrepreneurs regarding the shared work environment provided by the university business incubation programmes.

UBIs offer tenant entrepreneurs an opportunity to work with other like-minded individuals who have the same entrepreneurial aspirations. This is a unique aspect of business incubators since it offers entrepreneurs access to the entrepreneurial network. The purpose of this research objective was to learn about entrepreneurs' experiences of working in a cohort and evaluate how it helped them in their entrepreneurial journey. This research objective was developed to conduct an in-depth examination of associations among tenant entrepreneurs in the cohort, rather than investigating the correlation between business incubator facilities and services and the achievement of tenant start-ups, which had been the focus of several previous studies (such as Al-Mubarak and Wong, 2011; Ayatse *et al.*, 2017; Hannon 2003; Hackett and Dilts 2008; Khalid *et al.*, 2017; Lee and Osteryoung 2004; Todorovic and Moenter 2010; Zhang and Sonobe 2011).

Entrepreneurs were asked to shed light on their experiences of working in a cohort of entrepreneurs and how it assisted them during the incubation process. As reported in the earlier chapter, numerous themes were identified following an analysis of the

research data. Participants mentioned receiving peer support and learning in the cohort, as well as technical assistance from their cohort fellows. Within the cohort, some of the entrepreneurs were also able to find clients. While entrepreneurs actively helped and supported one another, there was a sense of competition and peer rivalry as well when it came to funding competitions. Figure 5.2 graphically presents the findings of this research and the identified themes are discussed in the sub-sections.

Figure 5-2: Tenant entrepreneurs' views and perspectives of cohort involvement

Source: Researcher

5.3.1 Peer learning and support

The entrepreneurial network is a crucial aspect of university business incubation and several previous studies have identified access to entrepreneurial networks as a critical component of university incubation programmes (i.e., Bennett *et al.*, 2017; Haapasalo and Ekholm, 2004). Social support has been regarded as a crucial aspect of incubator participation (Cooper and Hamel, 2012), and entrepreneurial networks within a cohort have been observed to cause a positive influence on the development and performance of tenant start-ups (Pearsall and Ellis, 2006).

In this study, the opportunity to network with other entrepreneurs in the cohort was deemed the most valuable aspect of the UBI program, which was in accordance with the literature findings. In fact, in the present study, access to internal networking opportunities was determined to be more valuable during the incubation phase than access to external networks. Cohort involvement provided opportunities for the entrepreneurs to gain new knowledge which aligns with the findings of Cohen (2013). Even the casual interactions among the cohort proved to be a source of learning for the respondents. Motoyama and Knowlton (2017) described such meaningful interactions among the cohort as conversations that had a greater impact on the incubatees or their start-up than merely seeing the other entrepreneur sitting around in the incubator. It was observed in the dataset that these interactions were a source of business advice, technical guidance, resource recommendations and emotional support as well.

Respondents in the sample also reported that being a part of the cohort benefited them much since diverse entrepreneurs provided a variety of experiences and expertise to the group. The entrepreneurs in the cohort were facing similar challenges and had the same goal, but they had a wide range of backgrounds and competencies. This allowed for the exchange of knowledge and ideas, as well as entrepreneurs learning from one another, making the incubation experience tremendously productive for everyone. Petterson and Gotsen's (2016) investigation of knowledge transfer in BIs also demonstrated that incubatees learned mostly through indirect learning obtained from other actors in the incubation programme such as fellow entrepreneurs and managers. Hence, it is determined that interactions between peers are essential for the growth of entrepreneurs.

Moreover, cohort involvement has also been reported by researchers to result in experiential learning and entrepreneurs' personal growth and development (Mattushek, 2020; Meckel, 2014). The present study also identified that participating entrepreneurs during the incubation period acquired new skills from their peers that not only aided in their personal development but also the development of their start-up venture. When even the incubator could not assist them, entrepreneurs with limited technical expertise were able to access technical support and gain new skills from the cohort. Therefore, peer interaction facilitated specialized technical knowledge transfer which would otherwise take a long time and effort (Cooper and

Park, 2008).

This support and help went beyond technical and business assistance, as being a part of the cohort also provided emotional support to the incubatees. A study conducted by Stenholm and Nielsen (2019) highlights the significance of emotional support for entrepreneurs and argue that perceived emotional support stimulates positive emotions, making entrepreneurs more inclined to interact with their surroundings. This was observed in the findings of the present study as respondents reported getting emotional support from the cohort to help them get through difficult times when their own family and close friends could not grasp the challenges they were undergoing. The entrepreneurial path is covered with uncertainties and risks (Magnani and Zucchella, 2018), and its challenges are often misunderstood by non- entrepreneurs. Innovative start-ups require extensive research that can take years before the product is ready for the market. Since entrepreneurs in the cohorts were going through the same struggles, they were able to share their problems with one another and seek emotional support.

5.3.2 Learning through social interactions

Findings of this study also identified the social aspect of learning in the UBIs as the findings revealed that learning was not confined to the physical boundaries of the incubator and socialising with cohort members outside of working hours proved to be extremely beneficial to the incubatees. This finding is consistent with Aldrich and Martinez (2001), who cited the benefits of social interactions as essential aspects of entrepreneurial success, particularly enabling access to what is not available to entrepreneurs through personal ties. Cohort based incubation programmes provide an opportunity to the tenant entrepreneurs to build and expand their network while working in a cohort of like-minded individuals. The present study indicate that cohort involvement was a crucial element of university business incubation programmes and greatly benefitted the tenant entrepreneurs. According to the participating entrepreneurs, they were able to learn from one another through socialising with the cohort fellows after business hours.

Effective learning is widely acknowledged as critical to entrepreneurship success (Cope, 2005a; Corbett, 2005; Man, 2007; Politis, 2005; Wang and Chug, 2014). A review of the entrepreneurial learning literature suggested that most of the

entrepreneurial learning occurs in the workplace environment, where nascent entrepreneurs learn from their decisions, failures, experiences, and connections (Davidsson and Honig, 2003; Man, 2007; Tell, 2008; Rae, 2006). The findings of the current study support different approaches of the entrepreneurial theory discussed in the literature namely experiential learning, situated learning, cognitive-affective learning and collaborative learning. Findings indicate that the incubation process and incubatees' day to day activities that involve social interactions, networking, and peer communications reflect experiential learning. Also, a supportive environment provided by the incubation programme facilitates experiential learning by allowing the entrepreneurs to 'learn by doing', develop required capabilities and competencies through experience (Man, 2007).

Moreover, the cognitive-affective perspective of entrepreneurial learning identifies a broader range of behavioural, motivational, and personality factors, such as self-worth, self-assurance, desire to accomplish and perseverance, as playing a key part in encouraging entrepreneurial learning (Rae and Carswell, 2001). The findings of this study support the cognitive-affective approach to entrepreneurial learning. Respondents indicated that being part of the incubation programme was a source of encouragement and motivation to them, which not only inspired them to pursue their entrepreneurial dreams but also gave them confidence in their abilities, enabling them to gain the most out of their learning journey. Furthermore, according to the networking perspective, networking may teach an entrepreneur, not just technical and specialised information, but also dynamic, non-expert driven guidance and experience, that can bring continuing gains for the firm (Man, 2007). This study indicates that by providing a shared work environment business incubation programmes facilitate collaborative learning. In the sample, respondents from diverse backgrounds and competencies were able to gain valuable knowledge and expertise from one another. The findings of this research, therefore, make a contribution to the entrepreneurial learning theory by reconfirming it in the context of the UK UBI.

5.3.3 Acquiring clients and services from within the cohort

The findings of this study show that tenant entrepreneurs benefitted from cohort involvement not just in terms of peer support and learning, but also in terms of

acquiring clients from their cohort fellows. This was especially the case with start-ups that do not require extensive research before offering their business services to potential clients. Entrepreneurs in the sample who established such start-ups in university business incubators reported getting their first clients from within the cohort. This not only strengthened their self-assurance, but also elevated their profile and provided financial assistance during the early and critical stages of their entrepreneurial journey.

According to some studies, entrepreneurial networks can help incubatees identify and exploit opportunities (Bøllingtoft and Ulhøi, 2005; Lewis *et al.*, 2011), as well as assist them in gaining access to affordable market services, as they often lack funds in the early start-up stages to pay for such resources through market-based transactions (Aldrich and Ruef, 2006; Motoyama and Knowlton, 2017). The present study identified that entrepreneurs were able to utilise new opportunities and acquire clients and services within the cohort. For instance, one of the respondents who joined the UBI programme to initiate a web development and designing studio was able to secure the first few clients from the cohort, giving her start-up a strong foothold. Similarly, some other respondents mentioned getting services such as product designing at affordable prices from the cohort. This helped the entrepreneurs keep the start-up cost down. Nguyen-Duc *et al.* (2020) reported similar results in a study of start-ups in the Brazilian ecosystem that used Business-To-Business (B2B) services within the cohort. In short, findings of this study indicate that peer networking in the business incubators can lead to the identification and exploitation of opportunities.

5.3.4 Peer-rivalry

Findings of this study indicate that tenant entrepreneurs greatly benefitted from the shared working space and opportunities to network with other like-minded entrepreneurs provided by the university business incubators. This cohort involvement provided them numerous opportunities and benefits during their incubation journey. However, it was noted that peer support and cohort involvement also had their downsides, complicating the ties amongst the entrepreneurs in the cohort. Despite all the cooperation and support, there was a sense of competition among the tenant entrepreneurs, which caused conflict when it came to acquiring finances and grants, as entrepreneurs competed for the same sources of funding. This

is consistent with the findings of McAdam and McAdam (2006) who reported a hostile and competitive work environment due to entrepreneurs competing for the same funding and grants.

Similarly, Ooiu *et al.* (2019) investigated the impact of team rivalry in collaborative learning groups outside the context of business incubation and concluded that peer rivalry among team members has a negative impact on team performance due to its detrimental impact on team learning activities. The findings of the current study corroborate the theory, indicating that competition for funding generated a hostile environment in the incubator, which not only disrupted entrepreneurs' daily work routines but also frustrated the manager. It might be argued, however, that while working in groups can result in peer rivalry, this does not necessary that such rivalry always affects entrepreneurs negatively; rather, it can rather provide them encouragement to work harder and achieve more.

Overall, whilst participating in UBIs, entrepreneurs not only benefit from the resources and services available to them, but they also greatly benefit from peer involvement and coordination with other incubatees. Having an opportunity to communicate and coordinate with peers that are also going through similar struggles, entrepreneurs can benefit in both physical and psychological ways. Having able to share their story with someone that is also going through similar struggles can help entrepreneurs to feel like they are not alone, which eventually helps them to stay focused and motivated. Besides, the networking opportunities UBIs provide can result in significant financial gains for all parties. Nonetheless, in general, business incubators are great tools; incubators not only prepare entrepreneurs to face the real world by equipping them with the necessary knowledge, resources, and skills but they can also be highly useful in developing great networks that can be essential in the future entrepreneurial journey. These findings make substantial original contributions to the body of knowledge by adding new insights to the literature as well as indicating business incubation programmes are great tools for reducing start-up failure rates. The subsequent section now presents the challenges entrepreneurs experience whilst participating in business incubation programmes.

5.4 Objective 3: To identify any challenges that entrepreneurs experience whilst participating in university business incubation programmes.

The third objective of the study was to identify the challenges experienced by entrepreneurs during the incubation phase through the perspectives of tenant entrepreneurs of the UK UBIs. To the best of the researcher’s knowledge, no prior study has been conducted to conceptualise the obstacles faced by incubatees during the incubation stage. According to BEIS (2017) report, the UK devotes a significant amount of funds to business incubation programmes each year. This study revealed numerous challenges and barriers that entrepreneurs experience during the incubation period, such as incubator bias, ulterior motives of incubators and external stakeholders, investors’ reluctance to take risks, lack of industry-specific information, inclusion, and entrepreneurs’ financial struggles. Some of those challenges are related to the internal factors of the incubation programme such as incubator policies and procedures, while others are associated with external elements including external stakeholders and investors and entrepreneurs’ financial struggles. The challenges that incubatees encounter while participating in university business incubation programmes are depicted in Figure 5.3 and the relevant findings are discussed in the subsections.

Figure 5-3: Challenges faced by entrepreneurs whilst participating in UBIs

Source: Researcher

5.4.1 Incubator bias

Incubator bias refers to the prejudice and favouritism experienced by the participants during their incubation journey. Incubator bias was reported in the selection process and the support provided to alumni start-ups, as well as favouritism in terms of increased support given to start-ups that are more likely to succeed or produce more investment. Incubators act as intermediaries or brokers (van Rijnsoever, 2020) and connect tenant start-ups with potential investors and clients (Cooper *et al.* 2010; van Weele *et al.*, 2016), and with the wider ecosystem (Lewis *et al.*, 2011). However, few of the respondents in the present study claimed that their respective UBIs were more supportive of certain start-ups based on their likelihood of success, affiliation with a sponsor institution, or relationship with the start-up founder. According to them, UBIs were actively endeavouring to connect those start-ups, particularly alumni start-ups, with investors and potential clients when they should have been offering equal support to all the incubatees. This indicates incubator bias toward start-ups founded by alumni of sponsoring institutions, which contradicts their stated mission. The purpose of the UBIs is to promote innovation and entrepreneurship (González Moreno *et al.*, 2019; Hassan, 2020), and contribute to regional and economic development (Jamil *et al.*, 2015), however, if they are more inclined to promote and support university start-ups for the sake of completing the targets and quotas, this indicates that they are not accomplishing their primary goal. This implies that UBIs prioritise their own agenda, which was to meet the sponsor institution's targets and quotas, instead of promoting innovation and entrepreneurship in the region.

Moreover, in a study to assess the impact of business incubation on start-ups, Bone *et al.* (2019) also highlighted the issue of selection bias and stated the many incubation programmes strive to accept only the brightest start-ups. Other studies (i.e., Aerts *et al.*, 2007; Nair and Blomquist, 2019) have supported this selection process and justified it as a failure prevention approach. There is an ongoing debate about whether incubators' 'pick-the-winners' or 'recognise promising ventures' when it comes to the selection criteria, support and mediation strategies. Few studies (i.e., Bergek and Norrman, 2008; Clarysse *et al.*, 2005) have identified different frameworks and models, as well as justified incubator's picking-the-winners approach, based on the distinct objectives of the incubators. Authors have varying views regarding incubator's approach, for instance, according to Hackett and Dilts (2004b),

incubators can enhance their performance and the success of incubatees if they act like venture capital firms, whereas Bergek and Norrman (2008) suggest that incubator model must be tailored to the incubator's goals and surrounding environment, as well as internally consistent. However, this researcher believes that since the primary objective of a UBIs is to promote regional entrepreneurship, their selection criteria, assistance, and mediation mechanisms should align with that sole objective. In terms of the picking the winners notion, if UBIs truly select and support start-ups based on their chance of success, this raises a question about the role of the UBIs input in the success of these start-ups.

5.4.2 Hidden motives of incubators and external stakeholders

Another problem the participants encountered during the incubation stage was the 'hidden motives of external stakeholders' of the university business incubators. According to them, some of the UBI programme's guest speakers had hidden motives that included promoting their own product or service to the entrepreneurs rather than actually assisting or mentoring them, as they were invited to do. Entrepreneurs were demoralised as a result of this behaviour, as it was a missed learning opportunity.

According to the entrepreneurs that took part in this study, this also discouraged them and their colleagues from attending future events organised by the incubators. This also indicates a lack of efficiency of the university business incubation programme. Incubator managers and organisers are responsible for inviting external guest speakers so that they could provide valuable advice and guidance to the tenant entrepreneurs, as well as an opportunity for the entrepreneurs to expand their network. Access to external networking opportunities is regarded as an important aspect of business incubation programmes (Nicholls-Nixon *et al.*, 2018). External speakers who do not serve the purpose and are only interested in pursuing their individual objectives entirely fail to fulfil this critical function provided by business incubation programmes.

Learning often occurs in entrepreneurial undertakings as a result of the interaction of a number of players, some of whom are external to the organization (Ravasi and Turati, 2005), and guest speakers are brought in by incubators to provide vital insight into the sector to nascent entrepreneurs. However, their lack of concern for the tenant entrepreneurs can lead to a sense of demotivation among the entrepreneurs, which

can stymie the progress of their venture. As identified by Munir and Rahman (2016), demotivation at the workplace leads to decreased productivity, stress and conflict. This implies that demotivation among incubatees may hinder them from realising their full potential or prevent them from attending subsequent events.

5.4.3 Lack of inclusion

Another challenge identified by this study is inclusion which refers to incubatees' struggle to feel included in the environment of the university business incubators due to different reasons, such as language, cultural or social barriers. A BAME respondent in the sample stated that he had witnessed and personally experienced racial prejudice from investors and that entrepreneurs from ethnic minorities, as well as white British entrepreneurs from less privileged backgrounds, face harsh scrutiny from investors. According to the respondent, incubation programme prepares the entrepreneurs to present their start-up idea in the best possible light, but it is beyond the incubator's control if investors, who are mostly from the upper class of society, hold unconscious biases against entrepreneurs based on their race or social background and disregard their ideas.

Another respondent, who was from a European background and was the solo founder of his small business start-up, mentioned his struggle to network and socialise with other local British entrepreneurs in the cohort. This suggested that certain entrepreneurs from minority backgrounds were experiencing social or cultural challenges that were prohibiting them from fully utilising the incubation experience and prospects. This finding is consistent with the findings of Looze and Desai's (2020) investigation of the challenges that entrepreneurs encounter in the United States, in which they identified inclusion based on race, ethnicity, gender, income, or other variables as a barrier to entrepreneurs' success. However, it is worth noting that the present study's sample included a number of BAME community and European founders, however, not all participant expressed concerns about racial prejudice from the UBI's internal or external stakeholders or language or cultural barriers that made it difficult for them to socialise. Other entrepreneurs of European origin were not solo founders, implying that they may not have a tough time socialising because they had a co-founder. Yet, Bone *et al.* (2019) identified a lack of diversity and a scarcity of ethnic minority founders in the UK start-up sector, which validates the current study's

findings. Similarly, Brodnock (2020) reported that women and minority founders, and founders from less privileged backgrounds received less venture funding in the UK, which supports the current study's findings.

5.4.4 Investor's reluctance to take risks

According to this findings of this study, investors' risk-averse approach was identified as another barrier affecting the entrepreneurs during the incubation stage. Risk aversion refers to investors avoidance to invest in risky entrepreneurial endeavors as well as projects initiated by founders who had previously failed. Investors' lack of willingness to invest in risky ventures or in entrepreneurs who had previously failed was cited by interviewees as a major impediment to innovation. It appears that investor's inclination to invest in ventures that are more likely to succeed is similar to incubators' pick-the-winners' approach.

Kuczmarski (1996) beautifully explains this risk-averse mindset of the corporate world. According to him, most CEOs profess to believe in novel ideas and claim to be oriented to innovation; however, in reality, innovation intimidates most organisations and their executives as they consider it a high-risk, high-cost venture with dubious outcomes. The respondents in this study described the same risk- avoidance culture, which is the exact opposite of innovation and entrepreneurship. Any economic activity's progress and productivity are dependent on innovation (Timur and Antanas, 2017), and risk-bearing is the essential requirement of entrepreneurship (Wärn-eryd, 1988, cited in Macko and Tyszka, 2009), which implies that innovation should ideally be deemed by the investors as high-risk high-return investment, instead of high-risk, high-cost. Since incubators are supposed to promote innovation and entrepreneurship, investors' aversion to riskier initiatives can hamper innovation and the fundamental aim of business incubation. Some authors (such as Nair and Blomquist, 2019; Klotz *et al.*, 2014) rationalise the incubation industry's risk avoidance by claiming that entrepreneurs are often overconfident in the success of their new endeavour, and as a result, they may make mistakes in their judgment and decision- making. Hence, incubators and investors make selective choices based on their collective experience to mitigate chances of failure (Nair and Blomquist, 2019).

5.4.5 Lack of industry specific information

Lack of industry-specific information was identified as another challenge that negatively affected tenant entrepreneur's incubation experience. Findings of this study indicate that the tenant entrepreneurs were offered a generic information by the university business incubation programmes and that they struggled to receive personalized and industry specific information. According to Bone *et al.* (2019), a majority of incubators operating in the United Kingdom do not have a specific industry focus and generally accommodate all types of digital start-ups. Participating entrepreneurs in the present study expressed similar concerns and mentioned receiving generalised support in terms of sessions from external speakers, mentors, and industry experts. This is particularly the case with incubation programmes that facilitate both high tech innovative start-ups and non- innovative small business start-ups in the same cohort. While small business start-ups require business assistance, innovative tech start-ups need technical support such as product or software development and the lack of such specialised support is regarded as a significant impediment that software start-up entrepreneurs confront (Pompermaier and Prikladnicki, 2020). Evidently, the needs of both types of start-ups are rather varied, and in order to cater for the needs of both types of incubatees, the programme offers generalised support that benefits neither.

Khalid *et al.* (2017) have reported the same finding that incubation programmes' one size fits all approach is ineffective. Entrepreneurs join incubation programmes seeking individual and personalised support during the early and most critical stages of their entrepreneurial journey. Thus, this lack of a specialised, industry-specific approach can cause demotivation among the incubatees which can lead to lower outcomes. A study conducted by Munir and Rahman (2016) beyond the context of business incubation shows association between lack of motivation among employees and poor achievements. This is an important finding and indicates that the organisers and directors of business incubation programmes should do a regular need assessment and provide industry specific information to the tenant start-ups as a failure to do so might have a detrimental impact on the development of their ventures.

5.4.6 Tenant entrepreneurs' financial struggles during the incubation stage

Entrepreneurs' financial struggle during the incubation stage was another challenge mentioned by the respondents. This is consistent with the findings of Bawaneh and Al-kayyali's (2014) investigation that highlighted entrepreneurs financial challenges during the early stages of start-up development. This is especially the case with innovative start-ups that require extensive research and development before they could reach the stage of monetising their entrepreneurial endeavours. Small business start-ups in this study reported receiving clients during the incubation phase from within the cohort as well from external sources, and since they did not require extensive research and development before launching their project, they were able to establish their own company and begin offering services within a year of incubation. On the other hand, tenant entrepreneurs of highly innovative ventures require extensive research for product development. Since start-ups of innovative nature need to spend a long time in the incubator, and it can often be challenging for them to continue their entrepreneurial endeavour without any financial assistance in the early stages. According to the participants in the current study, some of their cohort fellows had to discontinue their entrepreneurial endeavour due to such difficulties.

In addition, tenant entrepreneurs who actively participate with the cohort form valuable connections which help them progress in their journey (Motoyama and Knowlton, 2017). Although the incubator provides crucial support, assistance, and opportunities for entrepreneurs to improve their learning, it is the incubatees' ultimate obligation to fully engage in the programme and take advantage of those opportunities (Rice, 2002). Respondents in the present study reported that they witnessed some of their cohort fellows juggling several responsibilities and working a part-time job to sustain themselves while still focusing on their start-up. This had an impact on their capacity to achieve their maximum potential during the incubation stage. Due to other obligations, they were unable to fully devote their time to their project or attend the incubator on regular basis. It can sometimes lead to individuals abandoning the entrepreneurial path and pursuing other more conventional professional options (Folta *et al.*, 2010).

As discussed in the previous chapters, although earlier studies have been undertaken to identify the difficulties entrepreneurs face along the entrepreneurial journey, no prior study has been conducted in the specific context of university business

incubation. The findings of this research, therefore, make contributions to the body of knowledge by revealing the challenges entrepreneurs face whilst participating in UBIs.

5.5 Objective 4: To seek suggestions of tenant entrepreneurs on making the current business incubation programmes more effective.

The fourth research objective was to seek entrepreneurs' opinions on addressing the challenges faced by them during the incubation stage. No previous study, to the best of the researcher's knowledge, has aimed at seeking incubatees views on improving the current business incubation programmes. This research objective intended to elicit tenant entrepreneurs' perspectives on enhancing the effectiveness of the current business incubation programmes. Participating entrepreneurs highlighted suggestions such as having small and industry-specific cohorts, regular needs assessment and personalised support for the tenant start-ups, offering financial incentives for entrepreneurs during the R&D phase and opportunities for collaboration among former and current tenant start-ups. Tenant entrepreneurs' suggestions on enhancing the effectiveness of the current business incubation programmes are depicted in Figure 5.4. Since the findings are intertwined and necessitate a collective discussion, the pertinent findings are discussed collectively in this section.

Figure 5-4: Tenant entrepreneurs' suggestions for improving the current business incubation programmes

Source: Researcher

Respondents suggested that incubatees could benefit substantially more from the incubation stage if cohorts are industry-specific and modest in size. Although a big and general cohort provides possibilities to network with a large number of entrepreneurs from diverse backgrounds and skillsets, at the same time, it limits the ability of the incubator manager to effectively respond to the needs of various start-ups in the cohort. Additionally, it was observed in the sample that considering the diversity of the cohort, the incubator would welcome external stakeholders that are not from specialised industries, which frequently results in external stakeholders providing generalised counsel and extending generalised support that is not valuable to all of the tenant start-ups.

As identified in this study, moderate cohort sizes allow incubatees to build strong bonds with their peers and engage in meaningful interactions, that can facilitate enhanced learning. In a study comparing the benefits of small vs big groups in a classroom context, Pollock (2011) emphasized the benefits of small groups for participants; smaller groups appeared to be better for critical thinking and learning than bigger groups. Similar views were shared by the respondents of the present study regarding the benefits of a smaller cohort size. A few of the respondents in the sample had previous incubation experience in commercial incubators, which often allow for large and diverse cohorts. Given the high number of cohorts and entrepreneurs continually coming in and departing from the incubator, entrepreneurs expressed their struggle to extend their network and form connections with their colleagues. This implies that in both commercial and university incubators, a small cohort size can significantly improve the incubation experience of entrepreneurs.

Additionally, if the cohort is made up of industry-specific start-ups, the tenant entrepreneurs can have a better incubation experience because they will be able to make meaningful connections with others in the cohort and obtain relevant knowledge. It was also reported in Motoyama and Knowlton's (2017) investigation to examine entrepreneurs' relationships within the start-up ecosystem that start-ups from the same sector were able to assist one another with specific challenges because they were from similar businesses. Motoyama and Knowlton's (2017) reported that Biotech enterprises primarily networked with other biotech firms in the cohort, whereas IT firms predominantly networked with other IT firms, and as a result of the associations, they were able to improve their industry-specific knowledge and

expertise. Similarly, Marshall (1947, cited in Cooper and Pak, 2008) reported similar findings, stating that learning between enterprises is promoted when similar firms are placed close together because knowledge can be easily shared. Small industry-specific cohorts can thus be highly advantageous to incubatees. The findings of this study are consistent with the findings of the prior studies and thus make contributions to the body of knowledge by making the area of investigation further strong.

The respondents in this study also suggested that the incubators should conduct regular needs assessments of the tenant entrepreneurs so that they can provide them with more personalised support, as they did not hugely benefit from the incubator's generic information. Fledgling start-ups require a wider range of services (Bruneel *et al.*, 2012), and UBIs must tailor their services to the requirements of entrepreneurs in order to be effective (Nikoloski *et al.*, 2013). Incubators can only give value to incubated firms if their services address a need that the incubated ventures have (Alsos *et al.*, 2015). Furthermore, due to the dynamic nature of the new venture formation process, the current study discovered that the needs of tenant start-ups change over time during the incubation phase. Therefore, it is essential for business incubators to regularly assess the needs of the tenant start-ups and structure their programmes accordingly.

Participating interviewees also suggested that entrepreneurs should be offered financial incentives during the research phase because innovative tech start-ups require significant research and development before they can begin to profit from their venture. Their financial difficulties appear to be similar to those endured by self-funded PhD researchers. In a study to explore the experience of self-funded international PhD students in the UK, Mogaji *et al.* (2021) identified that the financial struggle of self-funded doctoral researchers put them under a lot of stress. This has the potential to affect researchers' capacity to fully concentrate, as indicated by respondents of the current study. Entrepreneurs will be able to fully engage with the incubator activities instead of working a part-time job to sustain themselves during the research phase if they are given a financial incentive to cover their personal expenses. This finding makes substantial contributions to the professional practice by suggesting providing financial aid can enhance the chances of the success of a start-up.

Besides, respondents also suggested that current incubatees should be given an opportunity to work with alumni cohorts who have successfully graduated from the incubator and are in the early stage of the development stage phase since this can foster innovation and innovative ideas even more. They also recommended that entrepreneurs in similar cohorts be encouraged to collaborate with one another. Although these suggestions are solely based on the perspectives of entrepreneurs, they still provide valuable insights. Besides, many of the findings of this research are consistent with the prior literature whilst some of them are unique. The findings, therefore, make contributions to the literature by adding new insights. These contributions are significant as the number of empirical studies conducted in the area of UBI is limited.

5.5 Summary of the Chapter

This chapter discussed the research findings by locating them in a broader context in an attempt to highlight the contribution of the research. This study examined the incubation process from the perspective of tenant entrepreneurs rather than the incubator managers and organisers, as incubatees' perspectives have been widely overlooked in the business incubation literature. As identified by this study, joining the UBI simplified and expedited the complex process of new venture creation. The entrepreneurs benefited from managerial guidance and support, as well as access to various resources, which not only helped them develop their start-up ideas, but also enabled them to transform those ideas into a company. It is worth noting that the managerial support, rather than the UBI's resources or facilities, was the determining factor in the entrepreneurs' productive and positive incubation experience. A discussion presented in this chapter confirmed that the findings of this research are consistent with the literature evidence and thereby make contribution to the body of knowledge by making the area of investigation stronger. This study achieved its aim and the rich findings of the semi-structured interviews facilitated an in-depth understanding of the associations among tenant entrepreneurs in the cohort, as well as between the tenant entrepreneurs and the UBI. The findings of this research, unquestionably, make significant new additions to the literature, mainly because little work has been done in the area of the university business incubations.

6. CONCLUSIONS, CONTRIBUTIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Introduction

This chapter summarises the research findings and explains how they helped in achieving the research objectives. In this chapter, all research objectives are revisited, and the methods utilised to achieve them are detailed, as well as the significance of the findings is assessed. In addition, the findings' theoretical and practical contributions are illustrated. Also, suggestions and recommendations for enhancing the effectiveness of the current business incubation programmes are made to the UK business incubation sector. Finally, this chapter also highlights the possible limitations of the research followed by suggestions for future research.

The following section presents a brief overview of the study's findings before delving into how the research objectives were met, as well as the study's contributions and suggestions.

6.2 A Brief Overview of the Research

Most start-ups struggle to survive in their early stages of creation which could be owing to the complexity of the entrepreneurial process, a lack of managerial competency, or a lack of capital (Berger, 2015; Posza, 2019; Zacharakis *et al.*, 1999). Business incubators can help minimize the number of venture failures and increase the survival rates of new and innovative enterprises (Posza, 2019). Nascent entrepreneurs join the incubation programmes with the aim to advance their start-up idea and with the expectation that such development will require learning.

Over the years, many researchers have focused on business incubation, particularly the influence of incubation on tenant start-ups (i.e., Aernoudt, 2004; Bone *et al.*, 2019; Chan and Lau, 2005; Chen and Wang 2008; Hansen *et al.*, 2000; Hughes *et al.*, 2007; Patton, 2014; Rothaermel and Thursby, 2005; Scillitoe and Chakrabarti, 2010; Schwartz, 2012; Sehitoglu and Ozdesmir, 2013; Voisey *et al.* 2013). Some studies show a positive impact of incubation on the performance of tenant start-ups (i.e., Hansen *et al.*, 2000; Hughes *et al.*, 2007; Patton, 2014), while others indicate no impact of incubation on firm performance (i.e., Chan and Lau, 2005; Oakey, 2007; Soetanto and Jack, 2013). Researchers have primarily focused on assessing the

success of business incubators in terms of tangible metrics such as firm's performance, profitability, survival, etc., and success of business incubators is often described in quantifiable metrics or measures; however, little work has been done in addressing the intangible metrics of success, such as learning and incubation experience of tenant entrepreneurs in the development of entrepreneurship. Incubator's practices and services are considered as the most pivotal determinant of its effectiveness (Ayatse *et al.*, 2017; Lewis *et al.*, 2011) and tenant entrepreneur or incubatee is a crucial element of the incubation process. However, an extensive review of the literature indicated that incubatees' perspective has been widely overlooked in the business incubation literature, thus leaving a knowledge void in the literature. Therefore, this research was initiated to bridge the existing knowledge gap by investigating the perceptions and experiences of tenant entrepreneurs of university business incubation programmes as well as evaluating the effectiveness of the support provided by these programmes in an attempt to provide recommendations to the UK business incubation industry for improving the current business incubation programmes.

This study explored experiences and perspectives of current and former tenant entrepreneurs of the university business incubation programmes in the UK. In order to explore the feelings and perceptions of the entrepreneurs towards the current university business incubation programmes, the interpretivist research philosophy was considered appropriate as it would enable the researcher to explore the phenomenon in a comprehensive manner. The interpretivist research philosophy was also considered relevant as little academic work has been previously done in the area. A qualitative research method was used for collecting the primary research data and semi-structured interviews with fourteen current and former tenant entrepreneurs were conducted with each interview lasting between forty-five to one hour and fifteen minutes. A qualitative method was considered most appropriate as the purpose of the study was to investigate tenant entrepreneurs' experiences of the support and resources provided by UBI programmes in the UK rather than confirming any existing theories or hypotheses. Research data was collected using an interview guide comprising of open-ended questions, the interview sample was selected purposively after carefully considering factors such as time, accessibility, and resources, and data was acquired and analysed concurrently. Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-step thematic analysis were used to analyse the interview data. The findings were constantly

evaluated in order to interpret and generate the meaning of respondents' perspectives of UBI experience.

Upon a thematic analysis of the research data, it was identified that nascent entrepreneurs greatly benefitted from the services and resources provided by UBIs. Managerial assistance and cohort participation were regarded as major contributors to the incubatees' entrepreneurial learning. In addition, access to financial resources, university resources, office space and access to external networking opportunities also contributed to entrepreneurs' productive incubation experience. The lack of industry-specific information and personalised support was regarded as the main challenges by the respondents in this study. Few respondents also reported concerns such as incubator's bias towards alumni start-ups and favouritism in terms of additional support, hidden motives of some of the external stakeholders of the incubator, struggles to feel included in the incubation industry, investor's bias and avoidance to taking risks, and entrepreneurs' financial struggle, particularly during the R&D stage.

As revealed by this study, the resources and guidance provided by the incubator, and the university resources greatly helped the entrepreneurs in the new venture creation process. Few of the respondents mentioned not receiving enough support from the university academics or staff. Participating entrepreneurs believed that joining the UBI simplified and accelerated the complicated process of new venture creation. They also revealed that incubators' connections with industry experts and experienced professionals were a source of practical knowledge for entrepreneurs. Interviewees revealed that incubator management has a significant impact on the incubation process. Incubator provided a shared working space and opportunities for entrepreneurs to network with other like-minded entrepreneurs and interviewees mentioned receiving peer support and learning in the cohort. Entrepreneurs even received technical help for their cohort fellows. Some of the entrepreneurs were able to find clients within the cohort. While entrepreneurs actively helped and supported one another, there was a sense of competition and peer rivalry as well when it came to funding competitions. Incubators were a source of inspiration and motivation to the entrepreneurs. They felt like being part of a community that encouraged them during their entrepreneurial journey. Few of the respondents had joined a commercial incubator prior to joining the university incubator, and they provided a good insight into the primary differences between both types of business incubators. Interviewees

mentioned the benefits of being part of a small cohort in an industry- specific incubator and the challenges of being in a big cohort.

While entrepreneurs greatly benefitted by participating in the incubator program, they also revealed few shortcomings, such as unconscious bias, incubator's preference to university start- ups over other start-ups, a risk-averse culture of the incubator industry, structured programs and generalised information in the incubators, and entrepreneurs' financial struggle during the incubation process. They suggested that incubators should be small cohorts and industry- specific. They also laid emphasis on the needs' assessment of the tenant cohorts to ensure they get the support they require. They also suggested financial incentives for the entrepreneurs for their personal expenses during the R&D stage.

This research makes contributions to the knowledge by adopting an incubatee-centred approach and focusing primarily on perspectives and experiences of the tenant entrepreneurs rather than the incubator managers and organisers. The rich findings of the semi-structured interviews facilitated an in-depth understanding of the associations among tenant entrepreneurs in the cohort, as well as between the tenant entrepreneurs and the UBI. Contrary to previous studies that mainly focused on identifying the relationships between incubator facilities and services and tenant start-up performance (i.e., Al-Mubarak and Wong, 2011; Ayatse *et al.*, 2017; Hannon 2003; Hackett and Dilts 2008; Khalid *et al.*, 2017; Lee and Osteryoung 2004; Todorovic and Moenter 2010; Zhang and Sonobe 2011), this study focused on the perceptions and challenges faced by the tenant entrepreneurs themselves. The forthcoming section now details upon how each research objective was achieved.

6.3 Achieving Research Aim and Objectives

This study aimed to explore tenant entrepreneurs' perceptions towards the support and resources supplied by university business incubation programmes, and how that assist them during the start of their entrepreneurial journey. In order to achieve the research aim, five research objectives were formulated. This section outlines how each of the objectives was addressed.

6.3.1 Objective One

To explore the perceptions of tenant entrepreneurs regarding the support and resources provided by UBIs.

The first objective of this research was designed to investigate the perceptions of incubatees regarding the support services and resources provided by the UBI. This objective was achieved by exploring the views of participating entrepreneurs towards the managerial support, mentorship and guidance, business advice, and access to resources such as office space, university resources, external network and industry experts, and funding opportunities received during the incubation stage. The findings of the first objective contribute to the literature by focusing on the incubation experience of tenant entrepreneurs and how that process supported them during the early stages of new venture creation. Despite the abundance of literature on the impact of business incubation, previous studies have primarily focused on evaluating the success of BIs in terms of quantifiable metrics such as profitability, survival rate, etc. (i.e. Brooks 1986; Grimaldi and Grandi 2005; Hannon 2003; Hackett and Dilts 2004a, 2008; Hannon 2005b; Kakabadse *et al.*, 2020; Lee and Osteryoung 2004; O'Neal 2005); however, the intangible metrics of success, such as tenant entrepreneur learning and experience, have been widely overlooked.

The findings of this study suggest that incubator managers play a crucial role and incubatees were able to learn from their experiences. Entrepreneurs' views of the effectiveness of incubator programs were based on their interactions with the incubator manager. As a result, this study emphasizes the importance of a devoted manager not only for the success of tenant entrepreneurs but also for the success and effectiveness of the incubator itself. In addition, it appears that management support is ascribed to the manager's personal attributes rather than the incubator, which is an important factor to consider by incubator organisers when hiring an incubator manager.

Furthermore, this research found that incubatees are accountable for their own independent learning, with the incubator serving as a facilitator. Although the incubator provides valuable support, coaching, and opportunities for entrepreneurs to expand their knowledge, it is ultimately the incubatees' responsibility to take advantage of those opportunities. Finally, entrepreneurs have found the sponsoring

institutions to be extremely supportive, encouraging, and accepting, as they not only encouraged respondents to participate in the programme but also gave entrepreneurs the opportunity to turn their business ideas into reality by placing their trust in their abilities. Their passion and zeal for entrepreneurship were sparked by the encouragement and support they received, and if it was not for the encouragement and assistance, these individuals would most likely not have pursued the entrepreneurial path. The study has filled this gap by adopting an entrepreneur-centred approach and focusing solely on the perspectives and experiences of the tenant entrepreneurs rather than the incubator managers and organisers. The first objective was fully achieved as the researcher was able to gain a rich insight into the tenant entrepreneurs' experience of receiving support and access to resources during the incubation stage.

6.3.2 Objective Two

To reveal the perceptions of tenant entrepreneurs regarding the shared work environment provided by the UBIs.

The second objective of this study was established to understand the perspectives of tenant entrepreneurs about the cohort involvement and shared work environment provided by UBIs and how it influences their incubation experience. The findings of the second objective corroborate the widespread concept in the literature that access to entrepreneurial networks is an important component of university incubation programs and having an entrepreneurial network within a cohort has a positive impact on tenant start-ups' development and performance. The findings of this objective contribute to the literature by focusing on an in-depth examination of associations among tenant entrepreneurs in the cohort, instead of investigating the correlation between incubator's facilities and services and the achievements of tenant start-ups which had been the focus of several previous investigations (such as, Al-Mubarak and Wong, 2011; Ayatse *et al.*, 2017; Hannon 2003; Hackett and Dilts 2008; Khalid *et al.*, 2017; Lee and Osteryoung 2004; Todorovic and Moenter 2010; Zhang and Sonobe 2011).

This research revealed access to an entrepreneurial network and its social aspect as a crucial element of incubator participation. In fact, access to internal networking opportunities was considered to be more important than access to external networks

during the incubation phase. Cohort involvement was a source of business advice, technical guidance, resource recommendations and emotional support as well. Existing literature suggested that cohort involvement can result in experiential learning and entrepreneurs' personal growth and development of the incubatees, which was also confirmed in this study that entrepreneurs were able to broaden their knowledge and acquire new skills from their peers, which assisted not only their personal development but also the development of their start-up venture. In addition, entrepreneurs were able to acquire clients and services within the cohort. Moreover, findings of this objective provide interesting insight into cohort complications that arise when entrepreneurs compete for the same funds and grants. As the researcher was able to acquire a thorough understanding of the incubatees' experience of cohort involvement, the second research objective was also fully achieved.

6.3.3 Objective Three

To identify any challenges that tenant entrepreneurs face during the incubation process.

The third objective of the study was designed to learn about the issues that entrepreneurs confront during their incubation journey, as it is critical to identify any deficiencies in order to be able to provide recommendations for improving current UBI programmes. The findings of this study indicated that entrepreneurs encounter different challenges during the incubation. Some of these challenges are related to internal factors of the incubation programme such as incubator policies and procedures, whereas others are related to external components including external stakeholders and investors, and entrepreneurs' financial struggles. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, no prior research was conducted to determine the challenges faced by entrepreneurs during the incubation period, precisely in the context of the UBI. Therefore, the findings of this research contribute to the existing literature by bridging the existing knowledge gap. The research objective was fully achieved as the findings not only shed light on the problems that tenant entrepreneurs encountered but also gave solutions to those problems.

6.3.4 Objective Four

To explore the suggestions of the tenant entrepreneurs on making the current business incubation programmes more effective.

The fourth objective was established to explore entrepreneurs' suggestions based on their experience of the incubation programme, as they may recognise areas where the current business incubation industry may be improved. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, no previous study has been conducted to solicit tenant entrepreneurs' recommendations for improving the business incubation practices. The findings of this objective provide valuable recommendations from the perspective of incubatees that can be adopted by the business incubation industry to enhance the overall experience of future incubatees in both BI and UBIs.

Furthermore, the practices and services provided by incubation programmes vary from incubator to incubator based on their resources and policies. Therefore, the suggestions offered by the respondents differ depending on their experience with the incubation programme. As a result of the findings of this objective, recommendations have been made for small and industry-specific cohorts, regular needs assessments and individualised support for tenant start-ups, financial incentives for entrepreneurs during the R&D phase, and opportunities for collaboration between former and current tenant start-ups. These suggestions also provided guidance to the researcher to fulfil the fifth research objective which sought to make recommendations to the incubation industry to enhance the current business incubation programmes.

6.3.5 Objective Five

To provide recommendations to the UK business incubation industry for enhancing the current UBI programmes.

The fifth and final objective was established to provide the UK business incubation sector and the relevant stakeholders such as incubator organisers and directors, sponsor universities, and current and future incubatees recommendations and suggestions to enhance the efficiency of the current incubation programmes. Section 6.5 of this chapter provides recommendations to the business incubation industry based on the findings of the current study. However, the researcher believes that this objective is partially achieved due to the researcher's lack of experience and practical knowledge of the incubation industry. The recommendations were purely based on

the insights gathered from the tenant entrepreneurs' interviews and the findings of the existing literature. Nevertheless, this lack of industry knowledge and experience allowed the researcher to be independent of the research context and maintain a neutral or unbiased stance (Bhattacharjee, 2020).

6.4 Contributions of the Research

The contributions of this research are presented under two categories: theoretical and practical. Below, contributions related to each category are detailed:

6.4.1 Theoretical Contributions

6.4.1.1 Contributions to the entrepreneurial learning theory

The primary aim of this research was to explore tenant entrepreneurs' experiences and perspectives towards business incubation in a UBI context. The study employed entrepreneurial learning theory as the purpose of nascent entrepreneurs who attend incubation programmes is to advance their start-up idea, with the premise that this advancement will require some aspect of learning. The findings of the study, as discussed in chapter 5.2.1, indicate that business incubation programmes support entrepreneurial learning by providing tenant entrepreneurs with the opportunity to work in a shared environment where they not only learn from experienced managers and mentors but also acquire useful knowledge from one another.

The findings of the current study support different approaches of the entrepreneurial learning theory discussed in the literature namely experiential learning, situated learning, cognitive-affective learning and collaborative learning. As identified, the incubation process and incubatees' day to day activities that involve social interactions, networking, and peer communications reflect experiential learning. Also, a supportive environment provided by the incubation programme facilitates experiential learning by allowing the entrepreneurs to 'learn by doing', develop required capabilities and competencies through experience. Besides, the findings of this study support the cognitive-affective approach to entrepreneurial learning as the respondents indicated that being part of the incubation programme was a source of encouragement and motivation to them, which not only inspired them to pursue their entrepreneurial dreams but also gave them the confidence in their abilities, enabling them to gain the most out of their learning journey. Hence, this study makes a significant contribution to the entrepreneurial learning theory by reconfirming it in

the context of the UK UBIs.

6.4.1.2 A conceptualization of challenges faced by entrepreneurs whilst participating in university business incubation programmes

Although numerous studies were previously conducted for identifying the challenges faced by entrepreneurs whilst working on start-ups, as identified following an extensive literature review in chapter 2, no empirical study was conducted precisely in the context of the university incubation in order to explore the challenges entrepreneurs face whilst participating in university incubation programmes. This research, therefore, qualitatively investigated the UK UBI sector and interviewed current and graduated tenant entrepreneurs that participated in the UK UBIs for exploring the challenges they faced whilst participating in these programmes. This research identified numerous challenges such as unconscious bias, incubator's preference to university start-ups over other start-ups, a risk-averse culture of the incubator industry, structured programs and generalised information in the incubators, and entrepreneurs financial struggle during the incubation process. This research makes theoretical contributions to the literature by empirically conceptualising the challenges faced by entrepreneurs whilst participating in university incubation programmes. These research findings fill the knowledge gap that previously existed in the literature. The discussion of the findings, as presented in chapter 5, indicate that these contributions may be generalisable not only to university business incubation but also to business incubation in general.

6.4.2 Practical Contributions

Based on the incubatees' perspectives explored in this investigation, the study provides useful insights to the policymakers and business incubator directors. The findings are original since they are based on the analysis of primary data that was gathered specifically for this study. Some of the key practical contributions of this doctoral research are presented below.

6.4.2.1 Better results can be achieved if business incubators collaborate with universities

As discussed in chapter 5, respondents greatly benefitted from university involvement in the UBI and access to specialised equipment. Faculty involvement in

the incubator helped the tenant start-ups to save costs by providing them university students as interns to work on their research projects. Similarly, access to university labs and equipment provided cost-saving opportunities. This study suggests that all business incubators should be affiliated with local universities as it can provide cost-effective opportunities to the incubatees while simultaneously providing students with a plethora of opportunities to gain practical work experience. This can also expose students and recent graduates to the entrepreneurial ecosystem, which can lead to them embracing an entrepreneurial mindset, that could eventually help to stimulate regional and national entrepreneurship in the long run.

Moreover, the findings of the study indicate that not all UBIs ensure academics' involvement in incubator activities. UBIs should take effective measures to promote academics involvement in incubation activities, particularly during the research and development stage, as nascent entrepreneurs can benefit from the expertise of academics with extensive research experience in the associated field. However, it is critical that partner universities consider the necessary measures to balance academic workloads. This contribution is expected to be generalisable across all UBI globally.

6.4.2.2. Business incubators should provide equal support to all tenant start-ups

The findings of this study indicate that UBIs are biased towards sponsoring university alumni start-ups, and start-ups that are more likely to succeed or manage to achieve substantial funding. These start-ups are favoured by UBI managers, who actively promote them in addition to providing extra support. The role of the UBIs is to promote regional entrepreneurship by providing support and opportunities to all tenant entrepreneurs regardless of their affiliation with the home university or any other factor. Besides, some of the respondents in the sample felt discriminated against due to their ethnic and social backgrounds, which can have far-reaching negative consequences. During an evaluation of the similarities between the findings of this research and other industry reports, it was noticed that there is a lack of diversity in the UK start-up sector. Thus, UBI should address this issue and focus on providing equal opportunities for everyone. This contribution is expected to be generalisable across all start-up support mechanisms in the UK.

6.4.2.3 Tenant entrepreneurs' collaborations and partnerships in the cohort can significantly promote regional entrepreneurship and innovation

Findings of this study indicated that entrepreneurs benefit significantly from the cohort involvement in terms of peer learning and support, as well as acquiring clients and services from within the cohort. Diverse backgrounds, experiences, and skillsets of entrepreneurs in the cohort can contribute to one another's knowledge and effective incubation experience in the cohort. Cohort engagement can be used for peer partnerships, and entrepreneurs with varied skillsets and unique ideas should work together to create a venture. This study suggests that incubators provide opportunities for tenant start-ups to collaborate with one another as well as with graduated start-ups farther along in their entrepreneurial path. Entrepreneurs with varying levels of skill and ability can work together to develop more inventive ventures, which can help to stimulate innovation. This contribution is believed to be generalisable to all types of business incubators.

6.4.2.4 Tenant entrepreneurs that have a good relationship with the incubator manager are more likely to succeed

The findings of this study highlighted the significance of the incubator manager's role, indicating that incubator manager is not only a key success factor for tenant start-ups, but also has a substantial impact on the incubator's overall performance. As discussed in the preceding chapter, tenant entrepreneur's learning and positive incubation experience are linked with their interactions with the incubator management, not the incubator's facilities and resources. This suggests that incubator managers can have a substantial impact not only on the start-up's success but also on the personal development of the entrepreneur. Therefore, when recruiting a manager, incubator organisers should recognise the complexity of the manager's role, as well as provide regular training opportunities for managers to ensure optimum performance. As the existing literature has widely overlooked tenant entrepreneurs' perspectives, these findings make significant contributions to the professional practice by highlighting the importance of the incubator and incubatee relationship. It is expected that this contribution is generalisable across all incubators and accelerators globally.

6.5 Recommendations

6.5.1 Recommendations to the business incubator organisers

6.5.1.1 Ensure effective mentorship

According to Relan (2012), lack of effective mentorship in incubation programs is one of the key reasons for start-up failure. Effective mentorship is essential to transform a promising start-up idea into a successful business. The significance of mentorship for the early stages of entrepreneurship has been highlighted by several studies such as Foo and Turner (2019) and Sullivan (2000). However, findings of the current study indicate that not all incubatees in the sample received ideal support from the mentors and in most cases, the incubator manager had to take on the role of a mentor as well. Mentors can provide incubatees with necessary professional experience and competencies as well as rigorous feedback and emotional support. Considering the variety of responsibilities that a mentor ought to do while working with early-stage start-ups, it may be necessary to assign more than one individual to an incubator. Mentors should be chosen not only for their experience and skill but also for their desire to dedicate time and knowledge to the start-ups. In addition, devising a concise set of rules detailing expectations for both mentors and mentees, at the beginning of the contract, could be useful for both mentors and the tenant entrepreneurs.

Moreover, opportunities for formal peer mentoring can greatly benefit the tenant entrepreneurs as recent and relatively more experienced entrepreneurs not only understand the struggle of the inexperienced entrepreneurs but also share their perspectives. This can further promote peer learning which can be advantageous to both parties. In a nutshell, effective mentorship may substantially contribute to the success of start-ups and ultimately for the success of the incubator.

6.5.1.2 Careful selection of incubator managers

This study's findings reveal that incubator manager is not only a critical success factor for tenant start-ups, but also has a substantial impact on the entrepreneurs' overall experience of the incubation programme. Respondents' opinions of the incubator program's effectiveness were dependent on their relationships with the incubator manager in this study, and a supportive manager resulted in the entrepreneurs' overall productive experience with the programme. Previous studies (such as Breznitz and Zhang, 2019; Wise and Valliere, 2014) has shown that having an incubator manager

with prior entrepreneurial experience is critical since they are better equipped to guide tenant start-ups and connect them with industry. The findings of the present study indicate that a manager's willingness to provide unwavering support to the entrepreneurs is as important as their relevant industry experience. This is an important aspect that should be considered by the incubator organisers while recruiting an incubator manager.

6.5.1.3 Small and industry-specific cohorts

According to Bone *et al.* (2019), the vast majority of incubators operating in the United Kingdom do not have a specific industry focus and generally accommodate all types of digital start-ups. This is especially the case with commercial incubators that follow the Y-Combinator business model and allow a large number of start-ups in a cohort. The findings of this study indicate that entrepreneurs can substantially benefit from the personalised support and industry-specific information in a smaller industry-specific cohort rather than a large, generic cohort that supports both small business and innovative start-ups. However, it was also observed in the dataset that entrepreneurs of both types of start-ups were able to learn from one another and even identify business opportunities.

When similar start-ups are clustered together, learning between them is facilitated since information can be easily exchanged (Marshall 1947, cited in Cooper and Pak, 2008). However, having multiple small and industry-specific cohorts in an incubator simultaneously can allow enhanced learning among the entrepreneurs. Findings of this study indicate that tenant entrepreneurs benefited by expanding their experience and knowledge by actively engaging with their peers in the cohort, who had diverse experience, knowledge, expertise, and social contacts. It is recommended that incubators should have small industry-specific cohorts within them, as this will allow for more efficient use of incubator resources while also allowing different types of tenant start-ups with different expertise to benefit from one another.

6.5.1.4 Organise informal networking opportunities

Previous studies (such as Bennett *et al.*, 2017; Haapasalo and Ekholm, 2004) has recognized a shared working space and the access to an entrepreneurial network that it provides as an important feature of business incubators. The findings of this study

indicate that cohort involvement was advantageous for the tenant entrepreneurs, and it allowed them to form useful ties with their peers, however, it was also observed in the dataset that not all UBIs organise informal networking events to promote socialisation among the tenant entrepreneurs. Having regular networking events can allow entrepreneurs to actively socialise and expand their network. A small percentage of the respondents raised the issue of BAME entrepreneurs struggling to fit into the incubation industry's culture due to language, social or cultural barriers. Organised networking events can serve as an icebreaker and can be beneficial for entrepreneurs who otherwise find it difficult to engage with others in the cohort.

In addition, incubator managers should create and sustain a pleasant work atmosphere for the tenant entrepreneurs. This setting should also foster a sense of trust among the entrepreneurs, allowing for more productive networking and interactions. Informal networking events can promote friendly relationships and strong ties among the incubatees. Also, throughout the incubation period managers should promote and reinforce the concept of 'one team' to mitigate peer rivalry and negativity in the cohort. To summarise, it is recommended that incubator organisers and directors hold regular networking events to foster a pleasant work environment in the cohort, allowing entrepreneurs to gain maximum benefit from peer networking opportunities.

6.5.2 Recommendation to the UK universities

6.5.2.1 Faculty involvement

The importance of faculty involvement in the founding team has been already emphasised by few prior studies (such as Breznitz and Zhang, 2019; Wright *et al.*, 2017) as they can be a source of advanced scientific knowledge in start-up innovation and product development. The findings of this study reveal that not all UBIs get the support of faculty members which can hinder the progress of the tenant start-ups. University support is the key feature that distinguishes university business incubation programmes from commercial incubators, and entrepreneurs can hugely benefit from the expertise and experience of faculty members of the affiliated university. It is recommended that universities should take measures to promote and ensure faculty involvement in start-up ventures. Universities can play a significant role and implement policies that encourage faculty members to involve in the start-ups research and product development activities, as this can contribute to the success of

the tenant start-ups.

6.5.3 Recommendation to the policymakers

6.5.3.1 Allocation of funding for training business incubator managers

The findings of this study indicate that helpful and welcoming incubator management helped the tenant entrepreneurs learn most productively during the incubation process rather than the advanced resources or facilities and the absence of such supportive management had a negative impact on the learning and experience of the entrepreneurs. Based on this finding, it is recommended that policymakers should invest in the training of business incubator staff, as it can have a significant impact on the learning of the incubatees. This could contribute to the establishment and maintenance of a more effective incubation programme, as well as the enhancement of entrepreneurial initiatives.

6.5.3.2 Financial incentives for the entrepreneurs

During the early stages of start-up development, entrepreneurs face financial challenges (Bawaneh and Al-kayyali, 2014), particularly those working on innovative tech start-ups that require extensive research and development before their products can be monetised. These entrepreneurs often struggle to support their personal expenses. This results in entrepreneurs not regularly attending the incubator due to part-time jobs to support themselves during the early stages. This can sometimes even result in individuals abandoning the entrepreneurial path and adopting other more conventional professional options (Folta *et al.*, 2010). Therefore, it is recommended that government and policymakers should address this issue and offer more financial incentives to talented entrepreneurs with promising start-up ideas during the early stages. Providing financial incentives to entrepreneurs to cover their personal expenses can enable them to fully concentrate on their start-up idea and actively engage with the incubator activities rather than holding a part-time job to sustain themselves during the research phase.

6.5.4 Recommendations to the tenant entrepreneurs

6.5.4.1 Actively network and participate in the incubation programme during the incubation period

The shared work environment of incubators allows entrepreneurs to network with

other entrepreneurs in the cohort. Social interactions in the cohort are considered an essential aspect of entrepreneurial success (Aldrich and Martinez, 2001). The findings of this study reveal that entrepreneurs who fully utilise this opportunity and expand their network, gain significant benefits and knowledge, as well as obtain business and technical advice and form useful business connections. Based on these findings, it is recommended that entrepreneurs should actively socialise with their peers and grow their network since this can be extremely beneficial to them in their entrepreneurial journey.

Furthermore, incubators offer various activities and sessions during the incubation stage. Findings of this study indicate that entrepreneurs who regularly attend the incubator and actively participate in the events organised by the incubators gain useful knowledge and form useful business links. However, not all entrepreneurs are able to regularly attend the incubator and such events due to other responsibilities and commitments which can have a negative impact on their learning and the progress of their start-up. This study suggests that entrepreneurs should attend the incubator on regular basis and participate in the events and sessions organised by the incubator during their incubation stage as it can contribute to their learning and the development of their venture as well.

6.6 Limitations of the Research

Although this research provides valuable insights into how tenant entrepreneurs view the incubation process in university business incubation settings, there may be certain limitations to this study. The findings of this research may have been affected by the following limitations:

6.6.1 Access to data

This research adopted a qualitative research design and the researcher had intentions to use observations for triangulation purposes, however, due to restrictions imposed by the COVID- 19 pandemic and the subsequent unexpected shift to working remotely from home, as well as time constraints, the researcher was unable to use observations in the incubator setting. Furthermore, the unforeseen situation caused by the national lockdown made the recruitment of research participants more

challenging and time-consuming. In addition, despite the use of appropriate sampling methods, the study may have been constrained by the use of data acquired solely from participants who volunteered to participate in the study.

6.6.2 Researcher's lack of practical experience in the business incubation industry

The interviewees provided in-depth insight into entrepreneurs' experiences with the incubation process; but, due to the researcher's lack of practical knowledge and experience of the business incubation industry, the findings were entirely based on interviewee responses. However, most of the findings were consistent with the findings of prior studies. Nevertheless, it is likely that the researcher may have better interpreted the findings if she had practical work experience in the incubation industry.

6.7 Future Research

Given the dearth of previous research in the area, there is certainly a need for more comprehensive research on the incubatee-perspective of the business incubation process. Future studies could employ exploratory sequential mixed methods approach and apply the in-depth findings of qualitative data to a larger population in the quantitative phase. Furthermore, future researchers could compare the experiences of incubatees in university business incubation programmes to those in commercial incubation programmes to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the strengths and shortcomings of both types of business incubators. The sample of the present research consisted of different types of start-ups. A detailed comparison of small business start-up founders' perceptions of incubation support and services to high-tech start-up founders could be another area for future research.

Moreover, a very small percentage of the respondents from minority backgrounds raised concerns of inclusion in the incubation culture due to social, racial, or language barriers. In a recent Nesta (National Endowment for Science, Technology and the Arts) report, Bone *et al.* (2019) also highlighted the issues revolving around the lack of diversity in the UK start-up sector, citing the paucity of female and ethnic minority founders. This could be another potential area of research to explore the challenges faced by ethnic minority entrepreneurs in the UK incubation sector.

6.8 Summary of the Chapter

This chapter discussed a summary of this doctoral research, offered an examination of how each research objective was achieved, discussed the theoretical and practical contributions of the study, and provided recommendations to various stakeholders, namely business incubator organisers, UK universities, policymakers, and current and future tenant entrepreneurs. The overall purpose of this study was to investigate the perspectives and experiences of entrepreneurs who had taken part in a university business incubation programme in the UK. The study employed a qualitative method and conducted fourteen semi-structured online interviews with current and former incubatees from six different university business incubators across the UK. The findings of this research, unquestionably, make significant new additions to the literature, mainly because little work has been done in the area. The study revealed a wealth of information about tenant entrepreneurs' experiences of getting help and resources during the incubation stage. It also demonstrated a solid comprehension of the incubatees' cohort involvement experience. In addition, the findings not only shed light on the challenges that tenant entrepreneurs encountered during the incubation stage but also offered solutions to those problems. The findings of this research make significant contributions to the literature by comprehending the challenges faced by entrepreneurs while participating in UBI and by making contributions to the entrepreneurial learning theory. Study findings support different approaches of ELT, namely experiential learning, situated learning, cognitive-affective learning and collaborative learning. Increased academic involvement in incubator activities, equal support and opportunities for all tenant entrepreneurs regardless of their affiliation with the home university or any other factor, tenant entrepreneurs' collaborations and partnerships in the cohort, regular training opportunities for incubator managers to ensure optimum performance, effective mentorship, small and industry specific cohorts, informal networking opportunities and financial incentivising were among the recommendations made to policymakers, university incubation management, and sponsor institutions for improving current UK business incubation programmes. This study has some limitations, despite the fact that it provided useful insights on how tenant entrepreneurs perceive the incubation process in university business incubators. Future studies might adopt an exploratory sequential mixed methods strategy, compare incubatees' experiences in university business incubation

programmes to those in commercial incubation programmes, or look at the issues faced by ethnic minority entrepreneurs in the UK incubation sector.

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8. APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Participant Information Sheet

Title of Study: **Entrepreneurs' Perceptions of University Business Incubation Programmes**

I would like to invite you to take part in a research study. Before you decide you need to understand why the research is being done and what it would involve for you. Please take time to read the following information carefully. Ask questions if anything you read is not clear or if you would like more information.

WHO I AM AND WHAT THIS STUDY IS ABOUT?

My name is Rabia Arshad (Student ID: B00336805) and I am research doctorate (DBA) student at the University of the West of Scotland, and I am conducting this research as part of the partial fulfilment of my doctorate studies.

WHAT WILL TAKING PART INVOLVE?

Participation would require maximum of forty-five minutes to one hour thirty in total from you. Interview will be conducted online. I would like to know

about your experience of being part of university business incubation programme and how did it help you in setting up your venture. I would like to know your views and experience about different aspects of the incubation programme, such as shared work place, mentorship and coaching, business advice, support and training, engagement with other entrepreneurs, access to various resources and opportunities, etc.

WHY HAVE YOU BEEN INVITED TO TAKE PART?

For this study, I am focusing on UK university business incubators, as these are the world class research-intensive universities. You are being invited to take part in the study as your incubator is affiliated with / or part of a UK university.

DO YOU HAVE TO TAKE PART?

Please be aware that your participation is completely voluntary, and you can decide at any stage of the study whether you want to continue to participate in this research or not. However, I would appreciate your participation for this academic research.

WHAT ARE THE POSSIBLE BENEFITS OF TAKING PART?

There will be no direct benefits to you, but your contribution would help understand how university incubators impact nascent entrepreneurs and support entrepreneurial ecosystem and the results of this research may help to further improve and identify best incubation practices.

WHAT ARE THE POSSIBLE RISKS AND DISADVANTAGES OF TAKING PART?

None

WILL TAKING PART BE CONFIDENTIAL?

All responses will be kept confidential, and all your details would remain

anonymous neither would it be considered for any other use apart from this dissertation.

HOW WILL INFORMATION YOU PROVIDE BE RECORDED, STORED AND PROTECTED?

Data collected through interviews will be recorded and a transcript will be produced. You will be sent the transcript and given the opportunity to correct any factual errors. The transcript of the interview will be analysed by the researcher and access to the interview transcript will be limited to the researcher. Any summary interview content, or direct quotations from the interview, that are made available through academic publication or other academic outlets will be anonymized so that you and your institution cannot be identified, and care will be taken to ensure that other information in the interview that could identify yourself is not revealed. The actual recording will be destroyed after completion of research thesis. Any variation of the conditions above will only occur with your further explicit approval.

WHAT WILL HAPPEN TO THE RESULTS OF THE STUDY?

This research is being conducting as part of the partial fulfilment of my doctorate studies (dissertation) and I also intend to send this study for publication in academic journals. The results of the study will be disseminated to the participants.

CONTACT

Please contact me if you require further information.

Rabia Arshad Student ID:

Email:

School of Business and Creative Industries University of the West of Scotland

Thank you for reading this information sheet and considering taking part in this study.

Appendix 2: Participant Consent Form

Participant Consent Form

Title of Study: **Entrepreneurs' Perceptions of University
Business Incubation Programmes**

- ✓ I voluntarily agree to participate in this research study.

- ✓ I understand that even if I agree to participate now, I can withdraw at any time or refuse to answer any question without any consequences of any kind.

- ✓ I have had the purpose and nature of the study explained to me in writing and I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the study.

- ✓ I understand that I will not benefit directly from participating in this research.

- ✓ I agree to my interview being audio-recorded.

- ✓ I understand that all information I provide for this study will be treated confidentially.

- ✓ I understand that in any report on the results of this research my identity will remain anonymous. This will be done by changing my name and disguising any details of my interview which may reveal my identity or the identity of people I speak about.

- ✓ I understand that disguised extracts from my interview may be quoted in dissertation, conference presentation and publication in academic journals.
- ✓ I understand that signed consent forms and original audio recordings will be retained by researcher until the completion of doctoral degree and access to consent form and audio recordings will be limited to the researcher.
- ✓ I understand that a transcript of my interview in which all identifying information has been removed will be retained until the exam board confirms the result of dissertation.
- ✓ I understand that under freedom of information legalisation I am entitled to access the information I have provided at any time while it is in storage as specified above.
- ✓ I understand that I am free to contact the researcher to seek further clarification and information.

Name and signature of research participant:

Date:

I believe the participant is giving informed consent to participate in this study

Signature of researcher:

Date:

